

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

Sfide scientifiche e gestionali per una società resiliente ai rischi ambientali in un clima che cambia

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Rischi geologici ed ecologici, terrestri e marini

AMBITO 1

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Advancing Machine Learning in Volcanic Seismic Analysis: ClusTremor Applied at Mount Etna

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Abstract

In this study, we aimed to analyze seismic data from Mount Etna to detect trends and possible precursors to eruptions using Machine Learning (ML) techniques. ML is revolutionizing earthquake and volcanology research by enabling rapid analysis of complex seismic data, improving hazard assessment, and enhancing early warning systems. In this work, we applied ClusTremor (Zali et al., 2024), an unsupervised machine learning framework designed to analyze seismic signals associated with volcanic activity.

Figure 1: ClusTremor Workflow

Figure 1 demonstrates the architecture of the advanced version of ClusTremor (Zali et al., 2025), which utilizes an autoencoder. Autoencoders (Mousavi, S., 2019) are a type of unsupervised learning technique for feature extraction and dimensionality reduction. They consist of two main components: The Encoder and

The Decoder. The Encoder compresses the input into extracted features using a sequence of convolutional layers, dense layers, and skip connections. These features are then used for the clustering task. This technique known as Deep Embedded Clustering (DEC) helps group seismic data into meaningful clusters. These clusters can enable the identification of patterns, trends, and anomalies in volcanic activity, possibly helping to detect precursors to eruptions. The other component of the autoencoder is Decoder which reconstructs the input from the extracted features, allowing the validation of the feature extraction process.

Our study focuses on a single-station, single-component approach using seismic data from Mount Etna, one of the most active volcanoes in Europe, located in Sicily (Italy). We utilized data from the ECPN seismic station due to its location to the summit craters. ECPN is managed by the Istituto di Geofisica e Vulcanologia - Osservatorio Etneo (INGV-OE) and is one of the reference stations used for the detection and analysis of long period and volcanic tremor events. It is positioned at an altitude of 3,038 meters. For this study, we selected data spanning from November 2020 to November 2021, covering both active and calm volcanic phases. Notably, two significant lava fountain cycles occurred in 2021 (Giuffrida et al., 2023; Proietti et al., 2024), providing an opportunity to evaluate the effectiveness of ClusTremor in detecting the different phases of the Etna volcanic activity.

To prepare the input for the ClusTremor, we generated daily spectrograms using the Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT). We downsample the data from 100 Hz to 18 Hz and apply a band-pass filter within the 0.5 to 8 Hz frequency range to emphasize volcanic tremors and long-period seismic events. STFT applies a sliding window function to the seismic time series, computing the Fourier Transform within each window to capture localized frequency variations. To optimize the visual representation of daily seismic activity, we tested multiple windowing options and selected the most effective configuration. The spectrograms were then fed into ClusTremor, where autoencoders extracted latent features before clustering the data using the DEC method.

As a result, ClusTremor demonstrated high effectiveness in reconstructing daily spectrograms, achieving a relative bias of approximately 4%. The clustering analysis was conducted using four distinct clusters, depending on The Calinski-Harabasz Index (CH). The results showed a strong correlation between one of the clusters and lava fountain occurrences, achieving 95% accuracy in predicting known lava fountain days. Additionally, another dominant cluster was associated with long-period seismic events, demonstrating ClusTremor's ability to distinguish different seismic phenomena.

A third cluster, possibly linked to the pre-eruptive phase, is currently under investigation, suggesting that ClusTremor may successfully identify seismic signals throughout the entire analyzed period, offering valuable insights into their temporal evolution.

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Sinkhole different time-magnitude scenario evaluation using ensemble model and Poisson distribution in R

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Abstract

Anthropogenic sinkholes are a widespread phenomenon in the Italian peninsula, affecting historical cities such as Rome, Naples, and Palermo (Nisio, 2018). Usually characterized by a cylindrical or a funnel-like three-dimensional shape, sinkholes' diameter and depth can vary from sub-metrical up to several tens of meters (Gutiérrez, 2016). Anthropogenic sinkholes are also often related to the presence and/or collapse of underground cavities. These voids can be either directly or indirectly related to human activities. In the first case, mining is one of the primary examples (Singh & Dhar, 1997), while leaking faulted pipes can be the cause of unexpected underground cavities (Dastpak et al., 2023). The following methodology is the one proposed as a tool for the anthropogenic sinkhole susceptibility analysis, and it is aimed at the objectives of WP4 and, in particular, Task 2.4.3. The methodology used in this case is based on a two-step approach. During the first step, an anthropogenic sinkhole susceptibility evaluation of the city of Naples is performed based on sinkhole diameter. Data from the full inventory is extrapolated and divided into three user-defined categories, which, in this case, are: i) equal or less than 2 m; ii) between 2 and 5 m; iii) over 5 m. Three anthropogenic sinkhole susceptibility analyses are performed using an ensemble modeling approach in R (R Core Team, 2024). This approach allows the use of different data and algorithms to evaluate sinkhole susceptibility within an area of interest. In this tool, machine learning algorithms such as Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM), Random Forest (RF), Maximum Entropy (MaxEnt), and Generalized Linear Models (GLM) were implemented to obtain three scenarios related to different sinkhole diameters, which were used as a magnitude indicator for modelization (Figure 1).

Figure 1 – Graphic flowchart of the methodology applied.

The predisposing factors used are: i) aqueduct and sewer network density; ii) distance to aqueduct and sewer network; iii) underground cavities network density; iv) distance to underground cavities network; v) geology; vi) hydrographic network density; vii) distance to hydrographic network; viii) cover layer thickness; ix) land use; x) road network density; xi) distance to road network; xii) slope angle. The weighted mean method is used as the ensemble model combiner, and the weights are obtained based on the ROC score using a 3-fold cross-validation. Following this first step, the Probability of Occurrence is evaluated within four user-defined time periods using the Poisson distribution analysis. These four probabilities obtained from the analysis are used to evaluate the spatial and temporal occurrence of anthropogenic sinkholes based on the magnitude scenarios. The final products of this approach are twelve scenarios related to both magnitude and temporal distribution analysis (i.e. 3 magnitude scenarios × 4 return periods) (Figure 1).

This methodology's objective is the evaluation of different scenarios based on event magnitude (diameter of the sinkhole) and different time scales (from one month up to years). The first step, which uses a statistical approach, can be a useful tool aimed at studying a possible interaction between the sinkhole magnitude and specific zones of the area of interest. Even in the case where the three resulting scenarios appear to be similar, important information can still be retrieved from the products (for example, there are no zones susceptible to higher magnitude events). Combining this first step with the second one, allow the user of this Tool to add the temporal factor to the analysis and study the evolution of the three magnitude scenarios over time. Although it is still a qualitative approach, it is based on statistical analysis like machine learning algorithms and the ensemble model approach. This can be a limitation to the Tool, as a complete and detailed sinkhole inventory is not always accessible or available. The amount of data in the inventory is also an important factor, as the reliability of statistical methods decreases when there is less available data.

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Development and application of a MATLAB-based GUI for ground instability susceptibility assessment: a case study on sinkholes in the Guidonia-Bagni di Tivoli area

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Abstract

As part of the activities carried out within VS2-WP2 "State of the Art and Knowledge Base to Define Impact-Oriented Hazard Indicators", and in line with the main focus of the WP —namely, detecting and analyzing predisposing factors to ground instabilities—a Graphical User Interface (GUI) has been developed to evaluate susceptibility to ground instabilities. This application has been specifically designed to simplify the analysis process, making it more accessible to a broader audience, regardless of their technical expertise in programming or data analysis. By providing a user-friendly interface, the tool allows users to conduct susceptibility assessments without requiring extensive knowledge of coding languages or computational modeling. However, while the GUI increases accessibility, it is important to emphasize that a solid understanding of the geological processes underlying ground instabilities remains crucial for carrying out effective analyses and obtaining reliable, meaningful results.

The development of this GUI was carried out using MATLAB R2024a. The choice of MATLAB over other programming languages such as R or Python was primarily driven by the team's greater familiarity and expertise with this platform. This decision was based on practical considerations, as our proficiency with MATLAB enables us to optimize the tool's functionality and ensure its robustness, rather than being dictated by strict technological constraints.

The GUI provides users with the flexibility to select among different susceptibility assessment methods, tailored to various types of ground instability processes. This adaptability allows for customized evaluations that cater to specific geological contexts and research needs. In this contribution, we focus on the results obtained through the use of the tool and the GUI in a case study dedicated to sinkholes (Gutierrez et al., 2014), specifically within the area of Guidonia-Bagni di Tivoli, Italy.

The results derived from this analysis are systematically compared with those previously obtained by Bianchini et al. (2022), who employed a machine learning approach to assess sinkhole susceptibility. Their study utilized the Maximum Entropy algorithm (MaxEnt), a widely recognized model in predictive environmental modeling. By juxtaposing the outcomes of the GUI-based analysis with those generated through MaxEnt, we aim to evaluate the effectiveness, accuracy, and applicability of our tool in assessing ground instability hazards, particularly in karst settings such as the Guidonia-Bagni di Tivoli area.

This comparison not only helps to validate the performance of the GUI but also provides insights into its advantages and limitations when contrasted with state-of-the-art machine learning models. Understanding these differences can contribute to refining susceptibility assessment methodologies, ultimately aiding in the development of more reliable hazard prediction tools for geoscientific research and risk mitigation planning.

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Preliminary Assessment of Submarine Landslide Susceptibility in the Calabrian Margins (Southern Italy).

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Keywords: Submarine landslides, Slope instability, Susceptibility map, Weight of Evidence, Ionian continental margin.

Abstract

Submarine landslides (SL) are among the most significant marine geohazards, as they can trigger tsunamis, damage submarine infrastructure, and are closely linked to other geological hazard processes (Kawamura et al. 2014). These features are globally distributed and are particularly prevalent in tectonically and seismically active regions, where they find favorable conditions for occurrence. The Calabrian continental margins (Southern Italy) have experienced intense geological activity in the past, driven by the tectonic evolution of the Calabrian Arc (Minelli & Faccenna 2010). This activity continues today, with widespread erosional and depositional processes leading to the extensive development of submarine landslides that actively shape the seafloor. Assessing the hazard posed by submarine landslides is therefore of primary importance, not only to understand individual events but also to gain a comprehensive view of their distribution and the potential damage they may cause (Harbitz et al. 2013). In recent years, only a few studies have been conducted to characterize the susceptibility of submarine landslides in different geological settings (Nian et al., 2019; Avdievitch & Coe, 2022) or at a regional scale (Innocenti et al., 2020).

In this study, a preliminary assessment of the susceptibility of submarine landslides along the Tyrrhenian and Ionian continental margins of the Calabria region has been conducted for the first time. The analysis employs the Weight of Evidence (WoE) method, a robust statistical approach widely used in geohazard assessments. This method quantifies the strength and nature of the relationship between the landslide inventory and various environmental factors, known as “predictors,” which may include topographic and geological variables. By evaluating these relationships, the WoE method enables the identification of the most significant factors influencing the occurrence of submarine landslides. Through this process, we can better understand the spatial distribution of submarine landslides and provide valuable insights into the potential hazards associated with such events in the Calabria region.

A comprehensive dataset of approximately 2,000 submarine landslides, developed within the GeoscienceIR project, has been analyzed to assess the susceptibility of the study area, which spans both the Ionian and Tyrrhenian Calabrian continental margins. The Ionian margin covers approximately 7,880 km², with water depths ranging from 20 to 1,700 m and a landslide frequency of 0.17 SL/km². In contrast, the Tyrrhenian margin extends over approximately 4,500 km², with depths ranging from 20 to 1,400 m and a landslide frequency of 0.14 SL/km² (Fig. 1).

The susceptibility analysis was conducted using eight predictor variables, represented as raster files: Digital Elevation Model (DEM), Slope, Planar and Profile Curvature, Aspect, Earthquake distance, and Fault distance. To characterize the mapped submarine landslides, which serve as the target of the analysis, a Bayesian raster indicating presence/absence (1 or 0, respectively) was generated. This approach enables the identification of

areas within the study region already affected by submarine landslide occurrences, providing a foundation for susceptibility assessment.

Figure 1 A) Map of the study area showing the digital elevation model (bathymetry) and mapped submarine landslides. B1) Close-up view of the susceptibility map for the Tyrrhenian continental margin. B2) Area under the curve (AUC) of the WoE model for the Tyrrhenian continental margin. C1) Close-up view of the susceptibility map for the Ionian continental margin. C2) Area under the curve (AUC) of the WoE model for the Ionian continental margin.

The model contrasts (weights assigned to each variable class) emphasize the key conditions, based on the input data, that ideally predispose certain areas to submarine landslides. On the Ionian continental margin, higher susceptibility is associated with the continental slope and structural high domains, depths between 200 and 1000 m, slopes ranging from 5° to 50°, and distances greater than 10 km from both earthquakes and faults. In contrast, the Tyrrhenian continental margin is characterized by the canyon domain, depths between 200 and 500 m, slopes greater than 5°, and proximity to earthquakes (< 3 km).

The Weight of Evidence (WoE) method yields Area Under the Curve (AUC) values of 0.76 for the Ionian margin and 0.82 for the Tyrrhenian margin, indicating that the models correctly predict the 76% and 82% of submarine landslide occurrences, respectively (Fig. 1).

Overall, the model demonstrates an excellent fit, however, given the inherent challenges in acquiring high-resolution marine information, it is crucial to consider potential biases in the original dataset, stemming from instrumental limitations and data availability, to prevent misinterpretation of the results.

The results highlight the effectiveness of the WoE method in identifying key factors influencing submarine landslide susceptibility along the Calabrian margins. This preliminary assessment provides valuable insights into the spatial distribution of the submarine landslides geohazards along the Calabrian continental margins, offering a foundation for future hazard mitigation strategies and more detailed investigations.

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Monitoring gravitational instability of coastal cliffs and shallow water canyon head systems: a proposal by the RISCHiA-Re project

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Abstract

We recently joined the partnership of the VS2 (Spoke 2 "Ground instabilities") of RETURN project, with the RISCHiA-Re proposal (Rilievo delle Instabilità Sottomarine e Costiere per Hazard Assessment anche da REMoto), a joint venture between public research institution, ISMAR-CNR, and private companies, Leonardo Sistemi Integrati srl e Planetek Italia srl, funded by PNRR.

The partnership will develop five interconnected workflows to deepen the understanding of submarine landslide triggers and the failure susceptibility at canyon heads in shallow water slopes and coastal cliffs. A focus will be placed on Ischia Island, to explore the instability of high coasts and adjacent submarine canyons, considered as a unique geo-morphological system. This choice was driven by the peculiar volcanic and morphotectonic context of the island which has fostered the occurrence of a large number of mass movements on land and offshore over time.

Leonardo SI will develop a feasibility study for a technological solution designed to continuously monitor shallow water slopes using active acoustic devices, installed on the seabed. The ideal sonar system should aim to detect minor morphological changes that may precede mass failures, enhancing our understanding of submarine slope instability triggers.

Planetek Italia will implement algorithms for the automatic feature detection of canyon heads and niches geometries in shallow waters through satellite images. To this end, a semi-guided selection of high-spatial and temporal resolution satellite images (WorldView-2 series) will ensure the best satellite images for features detection over time.

ISMAR is committed to the creation of a geo-database useful for implementing susceptibility models of mass failures in coastal and shallow marine environments of selected sites in eastern Tyrrhenian Sea. This activity could investigate the relations between gravitational instability features, niches and retreating canyon heads, with morphological and stratigraphic discontinuities, proximity to seismogenic structures, wave erosive action on rocky coasts and beaches. Additionally, ISMAR will also explore the potential link between morphological changes in exposed cliffs and the adjacent canyon heads and investigate the causes of instability in high rocky coastlines using a multi-scale, multi-temporal integrated approach, based on satellite radar interferometry (MT-InSAR), high precision topographic surveys (digital photogrammetry, terrestrial laser scanning) and monitoring actions in a selected site of Ischia Island. Trigger-based multiple geohazard scenarios

A key objective of the proposal is also to disseminate knowledge about the risks of submarine and coastal slope instability and raise awareness among stakeholders.

The RISCHiA-Re project, which complements the activities of VS2 in its final stages, aims to contribute to the discussion of tasks 2.4.1 “Multiple geohazards for ground instabilities in near-shore and coastal areas, volcanic islands” and 2.5.1 “Mitigation solutions with respect to ground instabilities”.

Effects of multiple stressors on the ecosystem functioning of Grado lagoon: an experimental assessment using mesocosms

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Abstract

This experimental study, part of Spoke VS4 (T 4.4.1), investigates the risks affecting the Grado lagoon and its resilience to the combined effects of oxygen depletion and mercury (Hg) contamination (**Figure 1a**). Located along the northern Adriatic coast, this transitional environment plays a key ecological role and remains one of the Mediterranean's most well-preserved wetlands (Acquavita *et al.*, 2012), despite urban and industrial pressures (Covelli *et al.*, 2006). The lagoon sometimes experiences hypoxia or anoxia due to high organic matter, nutrient levels, and water stratification in late summer, also promoting mercury production in its toxic, bioaccumulable form (monomethylmercury, MeHg) (Rice *et al.*, 2014). The study was conducted in June 2024 in order to assess the lagoon ecosystem response to multiple stressors (high-temperature conditions + Hg contamination). The experiment was carried out in the most contaminated area of the Grado lagoon, where organic-enriched shallow lagoon areas (< 80 cm) were artificially isolated using mesocosms with a volume of ~0.8 m³, divided in three clusters (R1, R2, R3) (**Figure 1b**). The effects of multiple stressors on planktonic and benthic communities were investigated after 96 hours (T₁) and 10 days (T₂), comparing results with reference areas outside the mesocosms. Each mesocosm was made of two cylindrical galvanized iron frames (Ø approx. 100 cm) and a transparent nylon cylinder (**Figure 1c**), allowing only the vertical fluxes between air-water and water-sediment interfaces, while blocking the horizontal exchanges with the surrounding seawater (Baldassarre *et al.*, 2023). Oxygen concentration, temperature and salinity were monitored daily using a multiparameter probe both inside and outside the enclosures. Passive samplers were used to measure the presence of organic and inorganic contaminants throughout the experiment. At each time point, water and surface sediment samples were collected for the following analyses: inorganic nutrients, chlorophyll-a, phaeopigments, and grain-size and C and N contents, respectively; and to estimate the abundance and composition of prokaryotic, microeukaryotic and macrozoobenthic communities through both classical taxonomy and molecular techniques. Following the oxygen decrease, the concentration of Hg and MeHg was measured both in water and sediments. To evaluate the impact of combined stressors on biological processes and pelagic-benthic coupling, Community Respiration (CR), Gross Primary Production (GPP), and prokaryotic Heterotrophic C Production (HCP) in the water and surface sediments were assessed. Unfortunately, the meteorological conditions did not allow to reach hypoxia inside the mesocosms. Notwithstanding, we observed that the suppression of horizontal exchanges inside the enclosures indeed led to decreased oxygen concentration (- 48.1±7.3%) after 10 days and affected the major microbial groups' abundances and the main biological processes, compared to the initial time point (T₀). At T₂, inorganic nutrients concentrations increased (P-PO₄ + 84.6±6.9%, N-NH₄ + 77.7±1.0%) compared to T₀. This is linked to the stimulated organic

matter remineralization by microbial activity (HCP) that increased in sediments ($+ 20.9 \pm 1.5\%$) inside the enclosures after 10 days. Benthic Net Primary Production (NPP) decreased inside the enclosures ($- 26.6 \pm 4.2\%$ at T_1 and $- 21.4 \pm 2.2\%$ at T_2 , compared to T_0) whereas it increased by 80.7% at T_1 and 80.4% at T_2 outside the mesocosms, highlighting the importance of seawater vivification. Total microphytobenthos (MPB) abundance increased inside the enclosures at T_1 and T_2 compared to T_0 , concurrently with the CR rates. These first results help us understand the possible effects that the next-future climate scenario might have on fragile and semi-enclosed ecosystems like lagoons.

Figure 1. (a) Spatial distribution of total Hg in surface sediments of the Grado-Marano lagoon was obtained by IDW (Inverse Distance Weighted) interpolation, modified from Bettoso et al., 2023. Experimental area in Grado (point A); (b) Experimental design: 18 mesocosms placed in 3 groups of 6 (actual arrangement) to assure sampling in 3 replicates per 3 experimental times; (c) Detail of the mesocosms.

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Multihazard analysis and management of the landslide debris transported downstream

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Abstract

A multi-hazard analysis (seismic, landslide, flood) is conducted to verify the impact on the road network. The ENEA CIPCast platform is an innovative Decision Support System (DSS) used to implement the analyses by using GIS. Using analytical and geoprocessing tools, the hazards were assessed and mapped. Overlapping of different geospatial layers allow to implement a specific hazard map for the road network. GIS-based methodologies are particularly suitable for identifying the portions of land where disasters triggered by natural processes of various kinds may occur. Multi-hazard values were obtained by an appropriate matrix of single values, classified and then summarized into four classes of values. The analyses were conducted at the regional (Campania Region), provincial (Naples Metropolitan City), and local scales (Island of Ischia and Municipality of Casamicciola Terme).

In particular, the landslide event that struck the Municipality of Casamicciola Terme on the Island of Ischia on November 26, 2022, is considered as a case study to determine the impact on road network, infrastructures, buildings and jeopardising inter-municipal connections. The results are mainly visualized through map processing and statistical summaries of the data.

Management of landslide debris, which can contain a multitude of fractions (waste, biomass and vegetation, sludge, soil, and rocks transported downstream by water), was also explored (Figure 3). This is a frontier issue for which international manuals and guidelines as well as national and emergency acts have been examined. A specific protocol for the sustainable management of debris generated by floods and landslides is needed, and discussed in Cappucci et al. (2024), in order to overcome emergencies after catastrophic events (Figure 1A). Debris flow into the shoreface are considered a predisposing factor for ground instabilities in shallow coastal environments due to the sediment input that may generate rapid overload on the seafloor and, eventually, flows/mass movements (Figure 1B). Debris and sludge management activities can be managed applying the principles of reuse, recycling, prevention, preparation for reuse, recovery, and minimizing landfilling. The recovered lithoids have been primarily reused for restoration, extension, or the new construction of dry-stone walls, with the function of protection from landslides and alluvial phenomena. In this way, future hydraulic and hydrogeological risks are mitigated. In Ischia, the debris silted within the harbor were removed by applying the options available for sediment

management. About 25,000 m³ of the dredged material, after characterization, was dumped offshore (Figure 1C4).

Beach nourishment was also considered to protect and nourish the sandy coast by reusing/recycling a compatible fraction of debris, but this option was not pursued. Future work will focus on the impact of rapid spillage of material transported in shallow waters and the ability to trigger ground instabilities in submerged environments.

Figure 1. The debris of the mudflow into the riverbed (a,b), along the road network (c–e) down to the Port of Casamicciola (f), after the 26 November 2022 event (Top left). Graphical representation of the debris composition and management (Grey: metals and minerals; Black: tarmac; Brown: lithoids; Green: Vegetation; Purples: vehicle and liquid wastes; Red: hazardous wastes). Among the artistic and architectural heritage, the personal effects are sometimes included (Top right). Sediment management of the Casamicciola Harbor. The green box represents the dumping area of the dredged sediment (Bottom).

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Distributed Deep Learning Workflow for Seismo-volcanic data (Etna)

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Abstract

The detection and association of seismic phases are crucial procedures in the workflows that lead to the localization and analysis of earthquakes. Waveforms recorded in volcanic environments, with a low signal-to-noise ratio and from different ongoing physical processes can be quite complex. We focus on two main families of seismic events that can be generally recognized: Long Period (LP) events, which are mainly due to the movement of fluids (water, gas, magma), and Volcano-Tectonic (VT) earthquakes, which are caused by brittle failures under stress.

Moreover, data coming from networks of tens of seismic stations and annual records on the order of Terabytes, make the techniques of phase picking and association computationally intensive and time consuming.

Recently developed Machine Learning (ML) frameworks can speed up the phase picking and association steps while demonstrating remarkable accuracy and efficiency compared to those performed manually or semi-automatically. Phases association into seismic events is also achievable using unsupervised ML techniques, based on the Gaussian Mixture Model Association or GaMMA (Zhu et al., 2022), which treats phase association as a clustering problem within a probabilistic framework.

We have assembled a workflow for the detection of VT earthquakes that exploits the automatic detection of phase picking by using a subset of selected DL pre-trained picking models (Zhu and Beroza 2018; Mousavi et al., 2020) available in SeisBench (Wollan et al. 2022) and automatic phase association by using GaMMA.

The workflow is Python-based and can also be executed on High Performance Computing (HPC) platforms, to significantly speed up processing times.

The ML detection results are evaluated by testing different pre-trained models, developed for tectonic and volcano-tectonic data. Continuous waveforms are provided by the Permanent Seismic network installed on Mount Etna area (Sicily, Italy) and managed by the Istituto di Geofisica e Vulcanologia, Sezione di Catania-Osservatorio Etneo (INGV-OE).

We tested the workflow on a standardized sample of the Etna dataset from January 2019 to July 2020, for which manually labelled picks are available (Alparone et al., 2020; Barberi et al., 2020).

The comparison between the ML derived picks and the picks from the verified VT catalog allows us to classify True Positive and False Positive picks when no corresponding manual pick for a VT earthquake is found.

Figure 1 - Time difference distributions, models: PhaseNet Volpick (*pn_volpick*), EQTransformer Volpick (*eqt_volpick*) and PhaseNet Original (*pn_original*). Recall scores for each probability threshold are shown in the upper left corner of each plot.

Fig. 1 shows the distribution of time differences between the manually labelled picks and the picks predicted by the PhaseNet Volpick, EQTransformer Volpick and PhaseNet Original pre-trained models. These three models were declared the best performing ones in the picks detection step, based on the Recall scores and symmetry of the distributions. Recall scores are the ratios in percentage between the True Positive picks and

the total number of manually labelled picks, here calculated in dependence of the probability threshold levels of the picks.

The True Positive events associated by the GaMMA are able to predict >80 % of the VT earthquakes, depending on the probability thresholds (PhaseNet Volpick: 83.33 - 87.38%, EQTransformer Volpick: 86.18 – 88.37%, PhaseNet Original: 84.00 – 86.64%); they also showed striking similarities with the VT earthquakes in terms of spatial and temporal distribution. The workflow is unable to distinguish Volcano-Tectonic from Long-Period events at this stage. The temporal distribution of False Positive events also shows a remarkable affinity to the production of LP events in the area, opening to the possibility for the automatic classification of VT and LP event families.

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Spatiotemporal Dynamics and Anomaly Detection of Land Subsidence in Delta Areas: A Case Study from the Po River Delta Using InSAR Time Series

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Abstract

Deltas are particularly susceptible to extensive land subsidence and consequently face heightened flood risks. Interferometric synthetic aperture radar (InSAR) techniques allow for multi-decadal detection of land surface displacements with a millimetric accuracy, demonstrating its power in revealing dynamics of land subsidence in delta areas. However, achieving a comprehensive understanding of the spatial and temporal patterns of the measured land displacements in these areas and assessing their potential impacts remain a challenge due to the superposition of various drivers of land movement and the high compressibility of the deposits forming these landforms.

In this study, taking the Po Delta (Italy) as a case study, we analyze the spatiotemporal trend, seasonality, and abrupt changes in InSAR time series derived from Sentinel-1 images spanning 2018-2023 (Costantini et al., 2021; Fabris et al., 2022). Particular attention has been given to the displacements affecting the extensive levees system that shields the territory from flooding. Temporally, a regression model is applied to the InSAR time series to track their trend and seasonality, while the Bayesian estimator of abrupt change, seasonality, and trend (BEAST) algorithm (Zhao et al., 2019) is used to detect their abrupt changes. Spatially, we propose a robust estimation method for modelling spatial distribution of land subsidence associated with Holocene sediment ages. Four models, i.e., power, logarithmic, hyperbolic, and exponential functions, have been tested.

Preliminary results reveal that, in the temporal domain, the behavior of the time series can be classified into trend dominated, seasonality dominated, and irregular patterns. Seasonality mainly characterizes the deformation of bridges and transmission towers and has evident either positive or negative correlation with the land surface temperature. Anomalous changes in the time series can be effectively detected, thereby enhancing the alert of levee failures. In the spatial domain, anomalous subsidence, which typically resulted from recent anthropogenic activities (Teatini et al., 2011), can be identified by comparing the observed and modelled subsidence (Figure 1).

The proposed framework shows its potential in improving the organization and interpretation of InSAR time series and thus provides comprehensive spatiotemporal analysis and direct detection of anomalies, helping identify critical areas and planning appropriate mitigation measures.

Figure 1 – Observed vs. modeled subsidence. (a) Observed vertical velocity. (b) Modeled vertical velocity associated with Holocene sediment ages. (c) Difference between observed and modeled vertical velocities. (d-f) Magnified views of the selected areas in (c).

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Back-analysis of a wetting-induced landslide on a physical slope model

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Abstract

A risk reduction strategy for rainfall-induced landslides in partially saturated coarse-grained volcanic deposits can be based on Landslide Early Warning Systems (LEWS), due to the rapidity of the sliding mass movement following full saturation of the deposit (Alfieri et al., 2012; Greco and Pagano, 2017). It is well known that the accuracy of LEWS depends strictly on the precursor variables to be monitored and the model used to set alarm thresholds.

With reference to the former aspect, previous research works (Coppola et al., 2022; 2023) demonstrated that suction and pre-failure deformation following its variation can be effectively used as landslide precursors. To this aim, the Authors performed experimental tests using a physical slope model (Figure 1a) to investigate whether wetting-induced instability is preceded by significant pre-failure deformations, jointly with a reduction in suction. The slope model hosted a soil layer of 35 cm made up of coarse-grained volcanic soil, which was vegetated and wetted. Thereafter, it was subjected to an artificial rainfall until the instability triggering was observed. During the test, suction evolution within the layer and slope deformation were monitored using a device, the tensio-inclinometer, purposely designed and tested to be later deployed in the field to underpin real LEWS.

Figures 1b-c illustrate the first results of a back-calculation of the rainfall-induced instability observed in the model test by a coupled unsaturated approach solved by the FEM method (Plaxis 2016). The approach couples water continuity equation (including Darcy's law and retention properties) with local equilibrium and linear elastic behaviour assumed for the soil skeleton, whose elastic parameters are derived from triaxial tests. The geometrical features of the FEM schematization were defined assuming plane strain-flow conditions across the slope longitudinal section (Figure 1b). A uniform initial suction distribution of 4 kPa observed before the test throughout the sloping layer was reproduced in the model. In terms of hydraulic boundary conditions, water flow was prevented for all the edge lines (A-D, C-D and B-C in Figure 1b). An artificial precipitation rate of 28 mm/h was applied as upper boundary condition (acting on the line A-B in Figure 1b) for two days.

Figure 1c shows the main results of the numerical calculation of the flow process. For sake of simplicity, only the suction evolution of one of the tensio-inclinometers installed during the experimental activity has been considered for the comparison with numerical results. The graph shows the suction trend collected by the tensio-inclinometer deepened 35 cm (yellow dot in Figure 1b). Experimental and numerical trends are consistent with each other. Both show a first part characterized by quite a null variation, then the persistent precipitation determines a decrease in suction ahead of the instability triggering. Such reduction is more severe in observations than in computations.

Based on the findings presented in this abstract, work on the remaining issues is continuing, mainly for what concerns a well-defined characterization of the material, to provide a better fit among experimental and

numerical results.

Figure 1 –a) slope physical model; b) geometry and mesh discretization for back-calculation; c) suction evolution measured through tensio-inclinometer compared to the numerical prediction.

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Natural laboratories of global change: assessing the impact of ocean acidification, warming and metal contaminations on plastic litter and habitat-forming species

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Abstract

Marine ecosystems are increasingly exposed to a combination of multiple stressors that interact and amplify their negative impacts, making them key drivers of biodiversity loss and habitat degradation (Beauchesne et al., 2025). Since the 1960s, the increase in anthropogenic CO₂ emissions has accelerated ocean acidification and water warming, triggering global changes with significant consequences for marine ecosystems. These environmental changes not only affect the chemistry of seawater, but also amplify the toxic effects of pollutants such as microplastics. Under acidic and warmer conditions, microplastics become more hazardous because their chemical stability is impaired, leading to the release of toxic substances that further harm marine life (Rochman et al., 2013). In parallel, heavy metals become more bioavailable under these conditions, increasing their toxicity to marine organisms, including microbial communities that colonize plastic particles (Harvey et al., 2020). These climate-driver stressors also exacerbate the risks to key ecological species, particularly photosynthesizing and habitat-forming species such as *Posidonia oceanica* and *Cystoseira sensu lato*, which play vital roles in marine ecosystems (Vassallo et al., 2013). These species provide important services such as food supply, coastal protection, carbon storage and habitat for economically important species. The degradation of these habitats, accelerated by climate change and pollution, threatens their ability to maintain these essential ecosystem services.

Shallow hydrothermal vents share several factors with global change phenomena (e.g., high temperature and CO₂, low pH and oxygen, toxic chemicals such as sulfite compounds, high trace metal pollution) and provide a unique opportunity to study how marine ecosystems respond to the combined effects of these multiple stressors (Hall-Spencer et al., 2008). In this study, conducted as part of Spoke VS4, the shallow, CO₂ areas of the Aeolian Islands were used as natural laboratories with two objectives: Assessing their impact on plastic debris and habitat-forming species. By focusing on the interactions between acidification, heavy metals and plastic litter, the ecotoxicological risks to marine biota will be assessed, including the impact on microbial communities (plastisphere), the role of plastics as potential vectors for alien species and the risks associated with the uptake and leaching of heavy metals and other pollutants into the ecosystem. The study also aims to understand whether habitat-forming species can survive under these altered conditions and continue to function as *refugia* from global change. The integrity of these species is critical to maintaining biodiversity and safeguarding ecosystem services. The strength of the study lies in the application of established methods

in a novel context, leading to insights of global relevance and helping to develop conservation strategies for marine ecosystems facing the additional threats of climate change and pollution, as well as improving the resilience of critical habitats.

Our field activities began in the summer of 2024, during which we explored 13 sites (Table 1). At each site, we characterized the chemical-physical parameters of the water column using multiparameter probes to measure salinity, temperature, pH and dissolved oxygen, complemented by continuous sensors for real-time monitoring of pH and temperature. Discrete water samples were also collected near the seafloor to assess variations in the carbonate system and microbial community structure.

At the shallower sites, time-weighted average concentrations and freely dissolved levels of heavy metals, including trace metals, arsenic and mercury, were measured using passive samplers deployed throughout the sampling period. In addition, sediment and water samples were collected for ecotoxicological and metal analyzes to better understand potential risks to marine organisms.

Table 1: sampling sites at the Aeolian islands

Island	site	Depth (m)	stressor	Island	site	Depth (m)	stressor
Panarea	Hot/cold	8-10	acidification, temperature of the seafloor, sulfur, metals	Vulcano	Baia di Levante	3-4	acidification, anthropic activities
	Campo 21	16 and 21	acidification, sulfur, metals		Baia di Ponente	3-4	anthropic activities
	Bottaro crater	10	acidification, sulfur, metals		Spiaggia Punta dell'asino	3-4	control
	Lisca nera	7	control		porto	3-4	anthropic activities
Salina	Tre pietre	8-10	control		Lipari	Spiaggia Valle Muria	3-4
	Lingua	20-23	control	Pietra del bagno		12	temperature
	Punta Megna	8-10	control				

At six of these sites (three on the island of Vulcano and three on the island of Lipari), chosen for their different environmental conditions (pH and temperature) and presence of anthropogenic activities, stainless steel containers were deployed, containing four different types of microplastics: two biodegradable (Mater-Bi and PLA) and two conventional (PP and HDPE). In this one- year experiment, samples are taken seasonally for chemical, physical and biological analysis (Figure 1).

The remaining seven sites (four vent sites in Panarea and three control sites in Salina) were selected based on OGS's extensive knowledge of the shallow hydrothermal systems of Panarea. These sites were targeted for an initial sampling campaign to assess the effects of multiple stressors — CO₂, low pH, warming, metals and sulphur — on *P. oceanica* and *Cystoseira sensu lato* as well as their role as refugia from global change for the associated micro- and microbenthic communities.

Interstitial water and sediment samples were also collected to analyse trace metals and changes in microbial community composition. The analysis of all samples has not yet been completed; a further sampling campaign is planned for next spring (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Sampling activities at the Aeolian islands

These two complementary research activities on the Aeolian Islands, through their innovative and holistic approach, aim to fill critical knowledge gaps regarding current and future environmental degradation. They will provide essential data for the conservation of marine ecosystems and support more effective management of the impacts of global environmental change.

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Probabilistic hazard modelling of the gas emission of Mefite d'Ansanto, southern Italy

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Abstract

The emission of gas species dangerous for human health and life is a widespread source of hazard in various natural contexts. These mainly include volcanic areas but also non-volcanic geological contexts. A notable example of the latter occurrence is the Mefite d’Ansanto area in the Southern Apennines in Italy. Here, significant emissions of carbon dioxide (CO₂) occur at rates that make this the largest non-volcanic CO₂ gas emission in Italy and probably of the Earth. Given the morphology of the area, in certain meteorological conditions a cold gas stream forms in the valleys surrounding the emission zone, which proved to be potentially lethal for humans and animals in the past. In this study we present a gas hazard modelling study that considers the main specie, that is CO₂, and the potential effect of the most dangerous, which is hydrogen sulphide (H₂S). For these purposes we used VIGIL, a tool that manages the workflow of gas dispersion simulations specifically optimised for probabilistic hazard applications. We produced maps of CO₂ and H₂S concentration and persistence at various exceedance probabilities considering the gas emission rates and their possible range of variation defined in previous studies.

Figure 1 – 24 hours time-averaged CO₂ concentration at 2 m above the ground at 50% (a), 16% (b) and 5% (c) exceedance probabilities. Redrawn after Dioguardi et al. (2025).

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The explosive-effusive transition during volcanic eruptions at Campi Flegrei (southern Italy): Insights from the Accademia eruption case study

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Abstract

The Campi Flegrei caldera is an active volcanic system in southern Italy and the multi-parametric monitoring data (e.g., seismicity, ground deformation and chemical composition of fumarolic gases) show evidence of an escalating volcanic unrest. The present-day caldera structure is related to the subsidence of the magma chamber roof into the magmatic reservoir during the explosive eruptions of Campanian Ignimbrite (CI; 40 ka BP) and the Neapolitan Yellow Tuff (NYT; 15 ka BP). In the last 15 ka, the effusive character has been rarely documented amongst the over seventy volcanic eruptions at Campi Flegrei. The explosive eruptions have been therefore well investigated to distinguish their impact, but there are few studies on lava emplacement in the literature. In addition, the shift in the eruption style has never been investigated in the study area. To bridge this knowledge gap, we studied the Accademia eruption (ca. 4.3 ka BP) that followed the uplift phase after the Plinian eruption of Agnano-Monte Spina (4.55 ka BP; Smith et al., 2011). Basal scoria-rich pyroclastic layers (Isaia et al., 2009) are overlain by tens of meters of lava dome/flow in this eruption. We reconstructed the eruptive sequence and collected samples from both explosive and effusive products. Observing thin sections of the samples under an optical microscope shows that sanidine, clinopyroxene and biotite phenocrysts are prevalent. Further analyses will include X-ray fluorescence (XRF) spectroscopy and electron microprobe analysis (EMPA). The fieldwork data, petrological characterisation and geochemical analysis will be then used to shed light on: (1) the pre-eruptive topography and erupted volume; and (2) the geochemical evolution, crystal size distribution and viscosity of the eruptive products. This work aims to improve the knowledge about the explosive-effusive transition in an eruptive event and the significance of effusive eruptions during resurgence phases at Campi Flegrei caldera.

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Morphoevolutionary model of a coastal landslide controlled by quaternary sea level fluctuations as a tool for managing climate factors through analytic approaches

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Abstract

Landslide processes are strongly influenced by climatic factors at different temporal and spatial scales (Gariano & Guzzetti, 2016). Although climate and associated hydrogeological factors are key drivers of mass movements, the mechanisms by which climate changes affect landslides remain poorly understood (Croizer, 2010). Among the most accurate approaches to understanding whether the genesis of a landslide is related to climate are: i) the determination of its age and ii) the comparison between its geological and geomorphological model with respect to relative and absolute datings and climatic reconstruction of the study area (Lang et al., 1999; Pànek, 2015). While some data are available for alpine contexts (e.g., Baroni et al., 2014), few are dated landslides in coastal domains, mostly because of landforms preservation in such environments. This limits our understanding of how past climate changes and related sea-level changes influenced the evolution of these kinds of slope instabilities.

This study focuses on landslides in coastal areas, where sea-level oscillations due to climate change are expected to have the most significant impact. Using the Vasto landslide (Central Italy) as a reference, where sea-level rise effects were previously identified (Della Seta et al., 2013), this research investigates the similar case of the Petacciato landslide, a large roto-translational earth slide extending over 2000 m along the coast and causing severe damage to roads, railways, and buildings. The complex evolutionary mechanism of this huge landslide has not yet been fully understood (Gori & Mezzabotta, 1995; Guerricchio et al., 1996; Fiorillo & Guadagno, 2000; Fiorillo et al., 2003; Cotecchia et al., 2004; Doglioni et al., 2012; Doglioni et al., 2015; Fiorucci et al., 2022), especially with regard to the identification of the predisposing, preparatory and triggering factors *sensu* Gunzburger et al. (2005).

A multi-modeling approach integrating engineering geology and morpho-evolutionary methods is here introduced to assess the contributions of different climate-dependent factors in the Petacciato landslide evolution. The geological and geomorphological characteristics of the landslide were determined through field surveys, borehole stratigraphies, and geospatial analyses. Some recognized landforms exhibit spatial continuity across the study area, and detailed analysis has identified three orders of landslide terraces that are progressively less preserved toward the shoreline. Field surveys and remote morphometric analyses have revealed back-tilted strata, counter-slopes, and pond zones that geomorphologically constrain the terraced surfaces, while a continuous scarp-shaped surface was identified at the base of the lowest terrace order. Multi-temporal analysis has helped classify different landforms associated with the landslide process, showing that the drainage network has deepened in response to the landslide mass emplacement. Additionally, sediments accumulated into landslide traps, i.e., geological structures (e.g., depressions produced by landslide's rotation) where material genetically linked with the past activations of the landslide is expected to be preserved, have been collected and dated with the radiocarbon method (C^{14}).

The conceptualized morphoevolutionary model credits the most relevant activations of the Petacciato

landslide to the glacial stages occurred during the last 250 kyrs. In particular, the two most important general mobilization of the whole slope are supposed to have been prepared by the regressive eustatic phases occurred between Marine Isotopic Stage (MIS) 7 and 6. During this period the landslide dynamics exhibited a retrogressive style characterized by a gradual retreat of the main shear surfaces. The more recent landslide activity has been characterized by a multistage dislodgment of the two main landslide blocks. In particular, C¹⁴ results demonstrate that during the last interglacial period the Petacciato landslide exhibited a progradational style that resulted in a rejuvenation of the landslide terraces moving towards the sea.

The presented morpho-evolutionary model will constrain a stress-strain numerical model that is currently being developed. This latter will validate the conceptual reconstruction of the Petacciato landslide, with the aim of enlightening the role of climate change proxies of such kind of coastal landslides.

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Projecting the Invasion of *Caulerpa cylindracea* in the Mediterranean under Climate Change: a novel *MaxEnt* approach

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Abstract

The rapid spread of Invasive Alien Species (IAS) poses a critical ecological and economic challenge that requires the development of predictive models capable of accurately forecasting future distribution patterns under the influence of climate change. Correlative Ecological Niche Models (ENMs) have become a widely used tool in this field. However, they often encounter limitations such as sampling bias, overfitting and difficulties in quantifying uncertainty. Moreover, their reliability is often limited by subjective methodological choices, which can undermine their predictive power and generalisability.

To overcome these challenges, we developed an ENM framework that uses MaxEnt and integrates both standard and location-weighted performance metrics into a multi-criteria decision-making process. This approach was developed to optimise the trade-off between explanatory power and model transferability. To mitigate overfitting, we introduced delta metrics that assess the extent to which model performance depends on the weighting scheme used. We also performed a sensitivity analysis to systematically evaluate the classification uncertainty associated with different probability thresholds. This methodological advance is demonstrated by an application to *Caulerpa cylindracea*, a highly invasive marine species that poses a significant ecological threat in the Mediterranean Sea.

Our selection strategy successfully identified an optimal model characterised by consistently high performance across different weighting schemes and multiple validation datasets (Figure 1). Both the annual projections and the scenario-based analyses indicate a general decline in habitat suitability, with a statistically significant negative trend observed in high suitability areas. These results suggest that, assuming no species adaptation, the future spread of *C. cylindracea* is likely to be restricted to currently invaded regions rather than expanding into new areas (Figure 2).

The robustness of our model is further enhanced by the exceptionally low extrapolation risk: only 0.21% of the predictions fall under the conditions of 'strict extrapolation'. Moreover, the response curves of the model are in good agreement with the known ecophysiology of *C. cylindracea*, further supporting its ecological validity. However, our sensitivity analysis shows a spatially heterogeneous pattern of classification uncertainty that appears to be correlated with invasion stage. The largest uncertainties are observed in regions that have been recently invaded, such as the Northern Adriatic Sea.

From a practical point of view, our framework provides a robust tool for assessing invasion risk while explicitly quantifying uncertainty, thereby increasing the reliability of predictive models. The selection process ensures that the generalisation ability of models is explicitly included in an objective ranking procedure. In addition, the annual suitability forecasts facilitate the temporal prioritisation of control measures and thus enable a more efficient allocation of management resources. Finally, the threshold sensitivity analysis highlights regions where conservative intervention strategies may be warranted, improving both the precision and cost-effectiveness of management measures to mitigate the impact of *C. cylindracea* and similar invasive species.

Figure 1 Kiviati diagram of model rankings for unweighted (a), weighted (c), AICc and delta (b) metrics. The delta metrics are calculated as follows: $dMETRIC = |METRIC_{unw} - METRIC_w|$. Coloured lines represent model candidates, while grey lines represent all other model configurations. The model selected by TOPSIS, highlighted in bold, shows the most consistent overall performance.

Figure 2 Probability Density Functions for the predicted probability of occurrence by the 1240 different MaxEnt models for present (a) and future (b) conditions. The thick lines mark the selected model. Vertical lines represent maxSSS based thresholds used to categorise the probability of occurrence into suitability. Grey shaded areas indicate the threshold range. The suitability maps show how the introduction of threshold uncertainties affects current (left) and future (right) predictions.

"Worst case scenario" (c- d), using: maxSSSmin; "base scenario" (e-f), using: maxSSS; "best scenario" (g-h), using: maxSSSmax.

Uncertainties Involved in Ground Instabilities: What Are They and How to Handle Them?

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Abstract

Natural ground instability refers to the natural tendency for ground movement that can be upward, downward, or lateral, which can lead to geological hazards. Assessing ground stability is crucial because it contributes to sustainable land use through identification of areas prone to landslides, subsidence, erosion, flooding, etc. which can endanger human lives and damage infrastructures. Therefore, appropriate mitigation or prevention measures can be implemented. An effective strategy for assessing ground instability is through the analysis of various types of data, including inventory, in-situ, and remote sensing. Mathematical and statistical models can be applied to process such data to understand how the environmental and climatic factors interact with ground instability.

Input data for assessing ground instability include but are not limited to topographic, morphological, geotechnical and geo-mechanical, land use/cover, geo-lithological, climatological, and hydrological data. Uncertainty in the input data not only arises from the measurement error itself, but from spatiotemporal variability, sampling frequency, and gaps. Gap-filling models, such as temporal, spatial, and spatiotemporal as well as data fusion models could be useful to improve the resolution of the data in time and space; however, each model may provide a significantly different solution. For example, while regression-based models are sensitive to outliers, median-based approaches like Mann-Kendall and Sen's slope are more robust (Ahmed et al., 2023). Identifying the nature of the outliers themselves is also a challenge. For example, a measurement could be acquired accurately but its value is flagged as outlier due to an extreme physical or environmental condition that in fact should be considered for stability analysis; while another measurement could be flagged as outlier due to noise because of sensor error in which case removing the outlier or de-weighting measurement or using a median approach could be beneficial.

Uncertainty arises from the gap between available knowledge and knowledge needed for rational decision making, i.e., as a function of ignorance (Tannert et al., 2007, Pérez-Díaz, et al., 2020). The most used approaches in literature for handling uncertainties are probabilistic methods and sensitivity analysis. Probabilistic methods involve the use of statistical models to represent uncertainty in model inputs and parameters, where all uncertainties are characterized by probability distributions, and model outputs are presented as a range of possibilities with associated probabilities. On the other hand, Sensitivity Analysis is employed to identify which variables most significantly influence the output of a model, thereby aiding in understanding which input data are most critical. Data can be acquired or pre-processed based on specific applications. For studies on the regional scale, a very detailed spatiotemporal resolution of the data may not be as important as for the studies on the local scale. In local, regional, and global scales, there is a trade-off between user accuracy (i.e., showing the reality based on field observations) and producer accuracy (based on

classification point of view). These thoughts should be properly considered when operationally developing the different tool chains that will constitute the project rationale. Toolboxes and standards framework to deal with uncertainty are being proposed in hydrology as well as in geosciences. There exist toolboxes that can provide an insight into uncertainties involved in the data and models, such as Sensitivity Analysis For Everyone (SAFE) which can provide a set of functions to perform Global Sensitivity Analysis (Pianosi et al., 2015, 2016). Our working group has experimented with these methods, the analysis of uncertainty in both the marine and terrestrial environments, allowing us to verify that, even if very different inputs are used, it is possible to obtain important results.

Finally, a comprehensive understanding of ground instability can be achieved through multiple key elements: deep field knowledge, proper equipment and sensor expertise, accurate noise source identification in input data, and thorough analysis using statistical and machine learning algorithms. Tools like SAFE enhance this understanding by revealing how climatological and environmental factors—both preparatory and trigger— influence ground instability. For effective prevention and risk mitigation strategies, we strongly recommend using probabilistic approaches that incorporate both observational uncertainties and error propagation analysis.

Keywords: Climate changes, Ground Instability, Toolchain, Uncertainty

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High resolution tsunami hazard scenarios for multi-risk analysis

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Abstract

Multi-hazard disaster risk analysis in coastal areas requires the integration of data and models concerning hazard, exposure and vulnerability data and models, all developed with high spatial resolution. Indeed, accurate high-resolution models and data are essential for properly assessing the impact of specific hazards that threaten coastal areas, such as tsunamis, floods, landslides, and coastal erosion. Nevertheless, this level of detail remains unachieved for many coastal hazards in various locations. Consequently, critical fine-scale differences in localized risk assessment are overlooked, leading to potential underestimation or overestimation of the actual risk to coastal communities. Addressing this gap is essential in order to enhance the accuracy and reliability of risk assessments.

A key step in tsunami hazard and risk assessment involves the development of inundation maps, specifically maps describing inundated areas and related depths. To date, such maps are not yet available at proper resolution for the coastal areas of the Friuli-Venezia-Giulia Region (FVG). Accordingly, our work aims to enhance the characterization of tsunami hazard in the Northern Adriatic by developing detailed inundation maps and possibly addressing the identified research gaps. Making use of accurate and high resolution bathymetry and topographic data is crucial for reliable tsunami modelling for the FVG coastal areas. To this purpose, bathymetry and topographic data are refined and are used, along with existing databases of tsunamigenic earthquake sources, for modelling tsunami waves propagation and inundation by means of the NAMI DANCE code (e.g. Yalciner et al. 2014).

Existing datasets from open access and local data sources are collected and then refined, particularly addressing inaccuracies in lagoon bathymetry. This involves incorporating high-resolution data and considering small-scale coastal features that can significantly impact tsunami inundation. Multiple bathymetry and topography datasets are used to develop high resolution refined data at 25 meters, and 10 meters resolution. The database of co-seismic seafloor displacement for all individual scenarios, developed based upon the DISS-3.3.0 database (DISS Working Group 2021), is adopted to carry out a reappraisal of tsunami wave amplitude maps (Peresan & Hassan, 2024) and to estimate realistic tsunami inundation maps. Additionally, tsunami sources caused by local earthquakes relevant to the FVG region are investigated, providing local scale maps of wave amplitudes and inundation estimates.

The outcomes from this study provide the basis for multi-scenario tsunami hazard assessment, contributing to the development of high-resolution and comprehensive tsunami hazard maps for the Northern Adriatic coasts. Moreover, along with high-resolution exposure maps, they contribute improving precision and accuracy of related risk assessment, and hence are an important step in preparedness, response, and prevention efforts in the framework of disaster risk management. The computed hazard and risk scenarios provide physical basis for envisaging impacts and for developing storylines, to be discussed along with different stakeholders in the FVG territorial elaboration unit (UTE).

This research is a contribution to the activities of the Spoke TS1 of the RETURN Extended Partnership (European Union Next-Generation EU—National Recovery and Resilience Plan—NRRP, Mission 4, Component 2, Investment 1.3—D.D. 1243 2/8/2022, PE0000005).

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Assessing shoreline evolution and river plume dynamics using multispectral satellite and drone data

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Abstract

One of the primary scientific aims of the DS Spoke is to develop innovative models for quantitatively predicting future climate, weather, hydrological, and marine variables. In early 2024, several impact-oriented hazard indicators were identified and collected for each natural sector defined in the SNPA Report (2021). Among these, shoreline position variation was selected as a key indicator for coastal zones. Shoreline configurations are in continuous change due to both natural factors (e.g., waves, sea level changes, tides, wind, and currents) and human activities (Rajasree et al., 2016), which influence the dominance of erosional or depositional processes. As a result, shoreline reconstruction is a crucial tool for understanding coastal morphodynamics and predicting how coastal areas will respond to climate change (Ranasinghe, 2016; Vitousek et al., 2017).

The Italian coastline spans approximately 8,000 km, with about 58% classified as low or deltaic shores, where urbanization, tourism, and industrial activities are most concentrated. Despite these pressures, coastal dynamics exhibit a slight trend toward greater stability, with an increasing number of advancing coastal stretches (ISPRA, 2023).

The coastal sector encompassing the river mouths of Fiora and Marta rivers, in the northern Latium, is an ideal site for investigating the shoreline morphodynamics and determining the river contribution to shore deposition and accretion. A coastline of about 20 km long has been investigated through multispectral and optical satellite imagery collected by different missions such as Landsat, Sentinel, RapidEye and PlanetScope, offering a unique dataset for reconstructing coastal changes. Three main goals are fixed: i) annual reconstruction of the instantaneous waterline during the summer season since 1984, ii) identification of the prevailing processes (erosion vs deposition) and their relative rates, iii) multispectral characterization and classification of river plumes in the last 15 years.

Through the computation of the Normalized Difference of Water Index (NDWI) combining the Green and NIR spectral bands of Landsat 4, 5 and 8, and of Sentinel 2, 40 instantaneous waterlines were reconstructed and analyzed in the Digital Shoreline Analysis System (DSAS) developed by the USGS. Marta and Fiora rivers represent two important sediment sources for the area and their contribution to the shoreline dynamics has been investigated through the analysis of the river plumes occurred during the autumn-winter season. High-resolution optical satellite imagery from RapidEye (5 m) and PlanetScope (3 m), with medium spectral resolution (5 and 4 bands, respectively), provides a suitable dataset for multispectral analysis and plume classification. Finally, the multispectral drone survey, conducted in winter 2025 using a Matrice 350 RTK equipped with a MicaSense RedEdge-P camera, was integrated for providing high-resolution and spatially detailed data for detecting shoreline indicators such as berms, storm\debris line, high water level, wet\dry line, and instantaneous waterline (McAllister et al., 2022).

The integration of historical multispectral satellite imagery, high-resolution optical imagery, and drone survey provides a comprehensive approach to monitoring coastal morphodynamics and river plumes dynamics. Moreover, this approach can contribute to valuable insights into the long-term evolution of coastal areas and the impact of sediment transport, giving fundamental support for coastal management strategies in the face of climate change and anthropogenic pressures.

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DSGSDs as a source of multi-hazard for risk assessment: hints from the Stiffe-San Martino d'Ocre ridge (Central Apennines, Italy) case study

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Abstract

DSGSDs (Deep-Seated Gravitational Slope Deformations) manifest at the mountain relief scale through a wide variety of morphostructures, such as trenches, scarps, counter-scarps, double ridges, as well as evidence of bulging and landslides, distributed along the slope and mainly dependent on the local geological setting (Discenza & Esposito, 2021). A growing interest in the understanding of such processes has been recorded in the last few decades due to the related hazard and risk conditions. Indeed, as documented in the literature (e.g., Loew et al., 2024), the huge masses involved in an active DSGSDs even if with low rates of displacement can threaten structures and infrastructures located on and in the deforming slopes (Frattoni et al., 2013). Furthermore, the creep process usually featuring a DSGSD can reach the tertiary stage in a part or in the whole deforming slope and lead to generalized and/or localized massive slope collapses (Loew et al., 2024). Moreover, in tectonically active areas, DSGSD can amplify the ground motion, thereby increasing overall seismic hazard and related risk (Martino et al., 2020).

In this frame, the hereby presented case study (Stiffe-San Martino d'Ocre mountain ridge, Abruzzi region, central Italy) is part of a wider project aimed at inventorying DSGSDs and has been selected as it highlights the relevant role played by karst processes that can activate and/or accelerate these deformations. This study also compares the geological model of the ridge, which highlights numerous signs of a DSGSD (Khalaf et al., 2024), with the existing, official geological hazard maps and landslide inventories (Figure 1).

Figure 1 – Geomorphological map of the Stiffe-San Martino d'Ocre ridge (modified from Khalaf et al., 2024): 1) DSGSDs boundaries; 2) presumed DSGSDs boundaries; 3) limit of the detensioned zone; 4) minor DSGSDs; 5) landslide accumulation area; 6) landslide scarp; 7) scarps and counterscarps; 8) main scarps; 9) trench; 10) newly- formed shear surfaces; 11) springs; 12) karst morphologies; 13) debris fan; 14) eluvial and colluvial deposits; 15) rotational slide landslide; 16) complex landslide; 17) slow-flow landslide.

From the comparison between the existing geological hazard mapping (PAI and IFFI) and recent studies on the Stiffe-San Martino d'Ocre ridge (Khalaf et al., 2024), significant discrepancies emerge:

1. According to the official databases (PAI – Geo-hydrological hazard map, and IFFI catalog – National landslide inventory provided by the Geological Survey), the ridge is not classified as a DSGSD;
2. The landslide upstream of the Campana locality, classified as a slow-flow landslide, appears to be a rockfall based on terrain evidence such as deposit features. Moreover, as indicated by damage to anthropic structures and trees below the detachment niche, the landslide is active;
3. The complex landslide near the town of Casentino is also active based on field evidence;
4. Upstream of San Martino d'Ocre, there is a complex landslide fed from upslope by the overthrusting of the Monti d'Ocre, where coarser deposits are incorporated into terrigenous material, which in turn generates rotational slides. The presence of bedrock blocks near anthropic structures and the significant damage to these structures confirm that the landslide is active.

Additional implications for the settlements near the DSGSD-affected ridge stem from the potential triggering or reactivation of dormant or inactive landslides following an earthquake, as the area of interest is within a high seismic hazard one.

The Stiffe-San Martino d'Ocre ridge is therefore subject to multi-hazard conditions due to ongoing intense gravitational deformation and high seismic risk. However, both PAI and IFFI significantly underestimate the actual hazard (and risk) conditions as they do not consider the presence of such a large deformation.

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Pollutants modelling with LTRANS-Zlev

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Abstract

Pollutants at sea, including emerging pollutants, plastic, and oil, present a major threat to the environment. Modelling their fate and dynamics is a challenging task due to their variety of behaviors, buoyancy, degradation rates and mechanisms. However, it is a powerful tool that improves understanding by integrating data from field and laboratory experiments with physical processes driven by forcing and boundary conditions. We present a three-dimensional Lagrangian ocean particle-tracking model, LTRANS-Zlev (Laurent et al., 2020), and the range of pollutant modelling applications that it enables. The model solves the trajectories of particles advected by the oceanographic circulation, relying on the current velocity fields that may be provided by observational datasets or global circulation models using either sigma or Z-grid coordinates. Additional wind and Stokes drift forcings, as well as stranding/bouncing and buoyancy/sinking dynamics can be included to better represent the transport of debris and pollutants. The model also includes the OILTRANS weathering module (Berry et al., 2012) for oil spill simulations.

These topics are investigated within Spoke VS4 of the RETURN project (Figure 1).

Figure 1 – LTRANS-Zlev Lagrangian model for pollutants modelling

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Submarine slope quantitative and modelling analysis: Factor of Safety (FOS) estimate. A learning example studied in Palermo offshore (NW Sicily).

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Abstract

This study analyse submarine morphological structures in the offshore of Palermo city (NW-Sicily, southern Italy).

The importance is related to the cause-effect relationship between pockmarks and submarine landslides observed in the morphobathymetric data. The integration of Multibeam data and Sparker seismic profiles allow us to obtain deep analysis and quantitative measurements of thicknesses, areas, volumes of sedimentary body altered by upward migration of pressurized fluids; presence of preferential sliding surfaces (weak layers), which are likely responsible of landslides associated with pockmark, as well as tectonic alignments linked to recent geological structures (predominantly N-S oriented), along which the fluids escape.

By analyzing the seismic profiles, convergent reflectors are observed, leading towards the central point of fluid migration that correspond to sediments altered by pressurized fluids. The alteration involves the loss of the geomechanical properties (cohesion, internal friction angle, etc.), resulting in sediments prone to movement, especially if, as in the case of Palermo offshore, favorable boundary conditions exist slope of the area, associated landslides and ongoing fluid escape processes.

The identification of areas and volumes of altered sediments allows us to develop not only a qualitative model regarding the potential future retrogressive evolution of these areas but also a quantitative study based on the calculation of the Factor of Safety (Noda et al., 2013; Sultan et al., 2004). This approach enables the study of the controlling parameters for the slope's evolution. In the case study, it is the pore overpressure in intra-pockmark area (Δu_{AFS}), and its threshold value, that determines the equilibrium of the slope.

Figure – 1: Tool chain flowchart.

Bibliographic knowledge reveals that the fluids migrating type in the Palermo offshore, corresponds to freshwater of continental origin (Pennino et al., 2014). Therefore, the activity of the pockmark is not continuous but intermittent, associated with the recharge of the continental aquifer through meteorological events.

The value of the Factor of Safety (FOS) related to the variable Δu_{AFS} , reveals the potential role of submarine landslides whose volume could play a crucial role to generate tsunami waves and consequent coastal geohazard. To quantitatively assess the seabed stability related to the presence of pockmarks, the model proposed by Noda A. et al. (2013) was chosen to compute of the Factor of Safety (FOS). We modified it to suit the case study and to include the injection of fluids from the pockmark feeding system (considered 'external to the system' water column - sediment). The approach from the literature is a one-dimensional infinite slope model:

$$FOS_{mod} = \frac{(\gamma' h \cos^2 \alpha - \Delta u - \Delta u_{AFS}) \tan \phi + c}{\gamma' h \sin \alpha \cos \alpha}$$

The pore overpressure Δu is calculated according to the relationship by Sultan N. et al. (2004): $\Delta u = \frac{10^6 h S}{200}$.

Δu_{AFS} (Active Fluid Seepage) it is the contribution to the pore overpressure from the emission fluids from the pockmarks. For each variable present in the equations provided, a raster was produced to solve the equations in a GIS environment (using the raster calculator in QGIS) and, finally, to create a map of the FOS_{mod} . Regarding the production of the raster related to Δu_{AFS} , whose value is not directly measurable, an iterative process was used to solve the equations. This process involved varying this parameter within a predefined range (based on literature data), with a step size established beforehand (brute force approach).

Figure – 2: Left image: morphobathymetric data of Palermo offshore; red circles highlight submarine pockmarks. Right image represents the FOS values colour coded to clearly highlight the instable areas prone to the occurrence of ground instabilities processes.

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Tool for a multirisk management of landslide displacement effects through geophysical-remote sensing approaches

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Abstract

Multi-risk management of complex landslides events requires a solid understanding of the potential displacement effects through adoption of appropriate investigating methodologies (Mangifesta et al., 2024). In such contexts, the integrated geophysical-remote sensing techniques emerged as a powerful tool (Hussain et al. 2022).

In this study, we present an integrated approach that combines passive seismic and remote sensing techniques to monitor the displacement effect of landslide at San Vito Romano (RM). The general objective is to develop a quantitative tool capable of correlating the surficial/ground displacements detected by satellite interferometry with some geophysical proxies of soil mechanics of displaced volume itself (for some details see further in the text). The project also involves the development of an artificial neural network designed to use, as input, landslide mobility indices along with preparatory and/or triggering factors, and to provide, as output, the landslide displacement. Once trained, this network will enable the simulation of potential landslide movements in response to different forcing conditions, generating predictive scenarios useful for risk assessment.

The selected case study concerns the landslide of San Vito Romano, which affects the entire urban center, an area long subject to widespread slope instabilities and frequent landslide phenomena (Seitone et al., 2025). The landslide under investigation is classified as active, with a retrogressive behavior, slow displacement, and involving the siliciclastic deposits of the Frosinone Formation (Upper Tortonian). The alternation of marl and sandstone layers represents an important predisposing factor for the slope instability, while soil moisture and rainfall are identified as the primary preparatory factors. The main triggering factors, on the other hand, we considered cumulative rainfall and seismic events.

To monitor seismic noise, four velocimeters (SARA Electronic Instruments) were installed: two within the landslide area and two outside of it. The instruments, operating since February 2024, have a frequency of 2.5 Hz and continuously record ambient seismic noise.

The changing empirical Green's function of an active landslide medium can be taken as proxy for monitoring landslide displacement effects obtained with wave scatters as in coda wave interferometry, change in HVSR peak and peak polarization considering the diffuse nature of ambient noise wavefield. However, geophysical results require the separation of unwanted climatological, thermal and other such effects through development of statistical tools. It promotes a deeper understanding of the role of preparatory and triggering factors, such as rainfall and earthquakes, in the evolution of the landslide activity. From the continuous recordings, landslide mobility indices were calculated: the variation in natural period (dT/T), in peak polarization (dP/P), and velocity (dV/V). The first two parameters were obtained using the Python library HVSRpy (Vantassel. 2020), which allows the calculation of the Horizontal-to-Vertical Spectral Ratio (HVSR)

over time. The processing was carried out with a time window of 200 s, Konno-Ohmachi smoothing, and the geometric mean for the horizontal components. To calculate the velocity variation, the data were processed with MSNoise, an open-source software for seismic noise analysis (Lecocq et al., 2014).

Ground displacement was estimated using satellite interferometric techniques, specifically the DInSAR method with the SBAS (Small Baseline Subset) approach. This technique enables the generation of maps showing the average deformation velocity and the monitoring of temporal displacement evolution at specific points within the study area (CNR-IREA). Specifically, images acquired by the Sentinel-1 satellite were used.

From the initial processing of seismic noise, the variation in the natural period over time was obtained by analyzing 11 months of recordings. A variation in the natural period was observed exclusively within the landslide body, alternating between phases with higher peaks and phases with lower peaks. Analysis of the variation in S-wave velocity, revealed a peak change of 2% in August. This result confirms that seismic noise measurements can provide useful information about the ground conditions. In parallel, satellite data from 2022 to 2024 were processed, showing a nearly constant displacement over time.

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Preliminary results from a 3D slope stability analysis along a canyon headwall in the Gulf of Squillace (Southern Italy)

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Abstract

Submarine canyons are complex seafloor features that are recognised worldwide as major conduits for sediments, where landslides characterise their headwall domain. The factors contributing to their evolution, among pre-conditioning and triggering factors (Vanneste et al. 2014), are still poorly constrained due to complex geological settings and lack of in-situ sediment sampling.

The offshore sector of Southern Italy, particularly the Ionian Calabrian Margin (ICM), is severely incised by several submarine canyons with complex multi-branched headwalls. The area is tectonically active, and seafloor features indicative of geohazards have been extensively mapped and qualitatively described (Ceramicola et al. 2024).

In 2023, during the ERODOTO research campaign, a collection of high-resolution data and gravity cores was collected to investigate the evolution and the main factors that generated the retrogressive headwalls of the Squillace submarine canyon.

High-resolution bathymetric and seismic data revealed the presence of multiple landslide scars and seafloor bedforms, indicating active sediment transport and slope instability.

Following a series of geotechnical tests carried out on the gravity cores at the Ifremer Geotech Lab, a 3D slope stability analysis was performed, to assess which factors have contributed the most to destabilize the seabed. The preliminary results suggest that seismic activity might decrease reducing the Factor of Safety (FoS) values below <1 in the study area.

This study provides new insights on the evolution of submarine canyon headwalls in the Gulf of Squillace, with quantitative information from geotechnical analysis and 3D slope stability modelling. Our results provide a valuable contribution to the assessment of critical areas for new offshore infrastructures.

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Utilizing Mid-Infrared Spectroscopy for Monitoring Soil Degradation and Erosion in Forest Ecosystems

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Abstract

Soil science faces significant challenges in acquiring timely and accurate data on soil properties, primarily due to limited laboratory capacity. The growing application of diffuse reflectance spectroscopy, particularly mid-infrared (MIR) spectroscopy, in soil and environmental science is proving to be a transformative solution, providing valuable, quantitative data on soil characteristics. This method has already shown promise in generating actionable insights, including soil organic carbon content and soil texture. However, for MIR spectroscopy to be effectively deployed in laboratory settings, it is essential to establish representative spectral libraries and ensure proper data measurements, as pointed out by Shepherd et al. (2022).

Building on the potential of MIR spectroscopy, this study investigates its application in forest management, focusing on soil degradation and erosion in chestnut forests located in Campania, central Italy. Forest management techniques, particularly coppicing, are common in the region but have raised concerns related to soil erosion and land degradation. To monitor and assess the impacts of coppice management on soil health, this research explores the integration of MIR spectroscopy with remote sensing technologies to provide a more comprehensive tool for monitoring soil quality and erosion risks.

The main objective of this study was to investigate the effectiveness of MIR spectroscopy in monitoring erosion-prone areas. Specifically, it aimed to evaluate how MIR spectroscopy can enhance the detection of soil degradation in chestnut forests by analyzing changes in the spectral response of soil organic carbon, with a particular focus on its relationship to soil erosion. Erosion is a significant concern in clearcut zones, as soil disturbance leads to the loss of essential nutrients and the degradation of soil structure. MIR spectroscopy, known for its ability to detect subtle changes in the soil's chemical composition, was utilized to assess spatial variability in soil properties within the clearcut areas. The spectroscopic analysis provided detailed insights into the soil's vulnerability to erosion, based on its organic carbon content and other critical soil characteristics.

Remote sensing data, including multi-temporal hyperspectral and multispectral imagery from PRISMA, Sentinel-2, and Landsat 8, were used to identify areas affected by clearcutting due to coppice treatments, which are often associated with soil erosion. This remote sensing data was integrated with soil sampling campaigns that focused on active clearcut sites. By analyzing the collected soil samples with MIR spectroscopy, we identified spectral signatures indicative of areas at risk for soil erosion and degradation. MIR spectra were specifically analyzed for changes in soil properties such as organic carbon content, which can be used as a proxy for soil health.

The study found that integrating these technologies allowed for the accurate mapping of clearcut areas, achieving overall accuracies of 80%, 87%, and 92% for Landsat 8, PRISMA, and Sentinel-2, respectively.

The use of MIR spectroscopy was pivotal in identifying areas susceptible to erosion. The spectroscopic data provided valuable insights into how soil organic carbon content varied across the clearcut areas, offering a direct measure of soil quality and its vulnerability to degradation.

By providing a non-invasive and cost-effective method for assessing soil degradation, the integration of remote sensing spaceborne and laboratory MIR spectroscopy can significantly enhance forest management strategies, particularly those aimed at mitigating erosion and promoting sustainable land use practices.

This research also highlights the need for improved integration of spectral data from diverse sources and the development of standardized spectral libraries to enhance the robustness of MIR spectroscopy in environmental monitoring.

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The Susceptibility Index to Failure (SIF) and the Source Affecting Index to characterize rockfall release areas

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Abstract

Rockfalls are widespread phenomena that pose significant threats to people, structure, infrastructures and the environment. They are increasingly occurring both in mountain and marine environments because of the adverse impacts of climate change and global warming. A semi-quantitative practical methodology to produce “weighted” rockfall susceptibility/hazard maps, for different environments and scales of interest, according to the propensity of the unstable rock blocks to detach has been developed (Napoli et al., 2024). To this aim, a rockfall Susceptibility Index to Failure (SIF) is assigned to the detachment areas, which is defined on the basis of the presence and intensity of the major predisposing, preparatory and triggering factors.

The novel approach is also proposed to determine a source affecting index of the rockfall source areas, with reference to specific elements at risk, that can be useful in the framework of risk management and mitigation activities, for example, to optimize close to a transport infrastructure system the positioning of risk monitoring instruments on the rock wall or stabilization systems.

Assessing rockfall hazard and risk implies, among the others, the location of the potentially unstable rock areas to be identified, the block volumes to be estimated and their susceptibility to failure and return time to be evaluated. The estimation of the temporal occurrence of the phenomenon is generally a challenging task, since it requires a detailed historical inventory of the rockfall events that have occurred in the area under investigation. However, available inventories are often absent or very poor. Therefore, relative hazard (i.e. susceptibility) analyses (independent from the rockfall temporal occurrence) are carried out.

The SIF index can be defined according to the presence and intensity of several causative factors, subdivided according to the specific environment (coastal-marine or mountain) and scale (small and medium-large scale) investigated. In association with a suitable method, the SIF Index can be assigned (although with a certain degree of subjectivity) to each rockfall source point to carry out weighted frequency runout analyses and, therefore, produce more reliable rockfall relative hazard (or susceptibility) and risk maps.

The novel approach, implemented in a Matlab routine, can be also applied to determine the affecting potential of the rockfall source areas with reference to specific (selected) elements at risk located within the rockfall invasion area. Such information makes it possible to identify the most effective positions for the installation of monitoring instruments or rockfall stabilization systems.

To show their applicability and validity, the method proposed in this research was applied to the Capo Calavà pilot site, located in the northern coast of Sicily (Italy), where a 3D rockfall runout analysis was carried out in the QGIS environment by means of the QPROTO plugin (QGIS Predictive ROCKfall TOol).

The site is formed by mica schists and phyllites (in the eastern outcrop) and plutonite (in the western outcrop) and is affected by diffuse rockfalls. A 300 m long rockfall sheltering tunnel, net fences and draperies, were installed to protect the SS113 road, connecting the cities of Messina and Palermo. Given the importance of the site and the presence of the SS113 road, this area has been chosen as a pilot site.

Detailed survey campaigns were carried out in the last years by expert geologists and engineers, to (i) evaluate the rock mass structural conditions, (ii) count and measure the detached rock blocks stopped on (or close to) the tunnel and on the beach below the road, and (iii) analyze the degree of damage/deterioration of the existing mitigation structures. The case study of Capo Calavà has been chosen in this research to show an application of the SIF index and its effect on the rockfall susceptibility assessment.

The QPROTO plugin was used to carry out two rockfall susceptibility analyses: the former neglecting the detachment propensity of the rock blocks (i.e. assigning the default value equal to 1 to all source points), and the second considering it (i.e. assigning the calculated SIF index = 0÷1 to each source point). A calibration of the QPROTO input parameters was then conducted considering the spatial arrangement of the rock blocks detached in the past and accumulated along the slope, on the artificial gallery and on the beach, based on the available orthophoto and on-site data survey results.

The results obtained are presented in Figure 1.a, which shows that the most critical detachment zones are the upmost (192 m asl) and central area, while Figure 1.b shows the susceptibility maps obtained by assigning the SIF Index to the release points.

Figure 1 - Capo Calavà (Sicily): a) SIF Index values assigned to each release point, and b) runout frequency map obtained without carrying out a susceptibility to failure analysis, with the default value of the detachment propensity to the source points (SIF=1).

These results obtained indicate that 48.91% of the 3624 source points does not affect the road, 20.5% of the source points have a release activity in the range 0.08%÷2% (i.e. can hit up to 2% of the element at risk), 18.6% of the source points have a release activity in the range 2%÷5%, and that only 131 source points (i.e. 3.6% of the source points) have a release activity greater than 10%. Therefore, the most active release area, with a maximum release activity equal to 13.2%, is relatively small and located in the upper-central part of the slope.

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Eroding edges: Exploring the tectonic forcing on the Italian submarine canyon evolution

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Abstract

Submarine canyon heads close to the coastline could represent significant geohazards along continental margins, with their retrogressive erosion potentially triggering tsunamis and causing coastal retreat. While the relationship between canyon head retreat and active tectonics has been explored through individual case studies, a comprehensive analysis across multiple systems has been lacking. This study presents the first large-scale quantitative assessment of the relationship between active deformation and canyon head retreat susceptibility along the Italian continental margins.

Based on over 70,000 nautical miles of multibeam data collected through the *Marine Geohazards along the Italian Coasts project* (MaGIC, Chiocci et al. 2009), our analysis encompasses over 2,700 detachment niches in canyon heads (Punto Identificativo Canyon Sottomarino, PICS), correlating the distance to the coast of these points with multiple independent variables including uplift rates, instrumental seismicity, and GNSS-derived crustal deformation strain-rates (Rovida et al. 2020; Palano 2015). Through a machine learning approach based on multivariate linear regression models combining stepwise and robust regression techniques, we identify a set of key factors controlling canyon head retreat susceptibility. Our loading analysis reveals that the primary independent variables driving canyon retrogressive evolution are proximity to river mouths and seismic activity, indicating that gravitational processes causing canyon retreat in the study area are predominantly earthquake-induced.

Based on the regression coefficients, we develop a quantitative susceptibility index to create a nationwide assessment of submarine canyon retrogressive evolution susceptibility (Fig. 1). The study identifies the following high-susceptibility regions: the Calabrian subduction zone (near Gioia Tauro and Patti municipalities, S-Italy) southeastern Sardinia and the Ischia volcanic island. Spatial clustering analysis demonstrates significant regional variations in the relative importance of tectonic forcing, with the Calabrian Arc showing the strongest correlation between tectonic activity and retreat susceptibility.

Integrating our susceptibility analysis with demographic exposure data from coastal municipalities (ISTAT data), we identify critical areas where high retreat susceptibility overlaps with significant exposure. These findings provide crucial insights for hazard assessment and coastal management strategies. The methodology developed here offers a reproducible framework for assessing canyon-related geohazards along continental margins worldwide.

This topic is investigated within Spoke VS2 of the RETURN project.

Figure – 1: Spatial distribution of PICS susceptibility and risk exposure analysis. Quantile classification based on the Stepwise susceptibility model (refer colour code in the upper white box for classification).

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Vulnerabilities assessment for multi-risks analysis of the Sardinian pre-Nuragic and Nuragic archaeological heritage

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Abstract

The contribution presents the results of systematic mapping of multi-risk analysis for peculiar cultural heritage built in Sardinia between the Neolithic and the Early Iron Age during the so-called pre-Nuragic (V – III millennium b. C.) and Nuragic (XVIII - VI centuries b. C.) periods.

Considering its uniqueness, wide diffusion in the regional pluri-stratified landscape, morphologies and material heterogeneity, cultural-environmental and social values as well as critical state of conservation, this archaeological heritage has been chosen as cultural heritage to be mapped and monitored through three different scales, territorial/landscape, architectural and material scales, in terms of multi-risk exposure.

The essential starting point is the definition of building typologies divided into nuraghi (corridor, tholos and complex nuraghi), giant's tombs, sanctuaries, Domus de Janas, caves, shelters, menhirs, dolmens and megalithic circles that have been characterised with specific attributes such as dimensions, materials and state of conservation. In fact, for each building typology, materials are defined according to their geological and geomechanical properties; the dimension instead is measured considering the overall proportion (tall, equidimensional, small, subterranean, wide), and the state of conservation, defined due to a qualitative analysis related to assets exposures.

Thus, three matrices have been codified to assess the level of vulnerability according to different hazards: seismic, fire, and hydrogeological. These values allowed the creation of a regional risk map, which provides the basis for the further development of monitoring parameters for cultural heritage. These will indicate the exposure of assets to multi-risks at both site and landscape scales.

Figure 1 – a. Nuraghe Ponte (Dualchi, SS); b. domus de janas in Montessu (Villaperuccio, SU).

Microplastic in soils: insights into the soil-plant *continuum* related to the element uptake

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Abstract

Plastics are widely used and nowadays they represent emergent pollutants that cause deep impacts on the environment. In agroecosystems, plastic mulches are used to enhance crop productivity but their degradation produces microplastics (MPs) that accumulate in soils, modifying the soil properties, influencing the plant physiology and likely causing damages to the human health. Previous research highlighted that MPs in soils can also modify the total concentrations of elements and their availability in soils.

In this framework, the present research investigated the impact of two types of MPs in soils on the element uptake by a common plant species, lettuce (*Lactuca sativa* L.). Moreover, the morphological, physiological and biochemical responses of the plants to the investigated MPs were evaluated. To achieve the aims, lettuce specimens were grown on soils added with MPs (at 1% and 2%) of polyethylene (PE) and biodegradable material (BPs). At the end of the growth period (60 days), the plants were harvested and analyzed for biometric traits, element accumulation in roots and leaves, and photosynthetic activity. In order to investigate the uptake process from soil to plant, multiple nutrient transporters were evaluated. In particular, proteins associated with natural macrophage resistance (NRAMPs), ZRT/IRT-related proteins (ZIPs) and heavy metal P-type ATPases (HMAs). Contextually, total and available contents of many elements (Al, Cu, Fe, K, Mn, Mg, Na, Pb and Zn) in the soils were measured. Finally, the bioaccumulation (BF) and translocation (TF) factors were calculated. The results were compared to those obtained for plants grown in soils where MPs were not added (CTRL).

The results indicated that soil nutrient content was significantly affected by MPs, particularly at the higher concentration of 2%. Compared to the CTRL, soils amended with 2% PE and BPs showed reductions in essential nutrients: nitrate levels declined by 7.5% and 15.5%, nitrite by 65.4% and 46.5%, and sulfate by 13.9% and 31%, respectively. Regarding plant responses, exposure to 2% BPs resulted in a significant reduction in leaf Zn (-96%), K (-39%), and Mg (-33%). Similarly, plants grown in 2% BPs-treated soils exhibited a significant lower growth (-67%) and decreased photosynthetic efficiency (-24). In roots of plants exposed to 2% PE, upregulation was observed for NRAMP5 (+21.4%), ZIP (+7.74%), IRT1 (+2.21%), and HMA3 (+2.64%), while leaves showed increased expression of IRT1 (+3.2-fold). Similarly, in roots exposed to 2% BPs, NRAMP5 (+18.2%), ZIP (+5.81%), and IRT1 (+2.13%). Roots BF increased in 2%PE-treated plants for Al (+9.6), Fe (+2.9) and Pb (+3.0), while in 2%BPs-treated plants, it increased for Al (+3.8), Cu (+3.3), Fe (+1.8) and Pb (+2.0) compared to CTRL plants. A significant reduction in Zn TF was recorded in 1%PE (-65%), 2%PE (-92%), 1%BPs (-67%), and 2%BPs (-96%).

Overall, the study reveals that biodegradable and conventional MPs influence soil nutrient dynamics and plant physiological responses. BPs, often considered environmentally friendly alternatives to conventional plastics, demonstrated significant detrimental effects on plant growth, nutrient assimilation, and photosynthesis. Furthermore, both PE and BPs MPs induced molecular stress responses, as evidenced by increased metal transporter gene expression. The presence of MPs in soil significantly disturbs nutrient dynamics, altering element bioaccumulation and translocation, depleting essential nutrients in leaves, and increasing the accumulation of toxic metals in roots. These findings emphasize the necessity for further research on the long-term ecological risks of MPs in agroecosystems and highlight the potential trade-offs associated with using biodegradable plastics as an alternative to conventional polyethylene-based materials.

Exploring the role of nurse shrubs in a reburned forest

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Abstract

Forest fires are a natural phenomenon in most forests, although alteration of fire regimes may cause landscape degradation, or even shift to non-forest ecosystems. Climate change and anthropic pressure are the main drivers of fire regimes alteration, and understanding the ecological pathways for forest regeneration is increasingly important today, with fast changes in climate and land use.

An increase in frequency of forest fires over the same area may hinder the ability of the forest to recover, due to the reduction of parent trees—and therefore of seeds, the increase of soil erosion, and the alteration of the floristic composition, which may elongate the time needed by the forest to return to a pre-fire condition. Although an important topic, successive fires are still marginally studied, mainly due to the difficulty to find suitable case studies.

The ecological pathways of post-fire forest regeneration have been studied for long, but quantitative evidence on how successive fires affect these pathways is still scarce. One of the most evident post-fire ecological mechanisms is the facilitation provided to young trees by biological legacies (*sensu* Franklin J.F. et al., 2000), like for instance deadwood (Lingua E. et al., 2023) or nurse shrubs (Johnstone J.F. et al., 2016). Nurse shrubs are woody plants that colonise disturbed environments creating better conditions for trees establishment (Castro J. et al., 2021). Their main role is to intercept solar radiation, mitigating the micro-climatic conditions in their immediate surroundings. They may also have a direct effect on soil nutrients and water cycle, and they may prevent browsing from ungulates. Nonetheless, how nurse shrubs facilitate trees seedlings in reburned areas is still little explored.

In this study we took advantage of an area in Liguria, Italy, that experienced a long history of fires (Marzano R. et al. 2012), and specifically of a site burned twice in the last 20 years (in 2006 and 2015). The area was previously covered with a pine plantation (*Pinus halepensis* Mill. and *Pinus pinaster* Aiton), but surrounding natural vegetation is mainly composed of oaks (*Quercus* spp.), other deciduous broadleaves, and macchia shrubs. In February 2025 we performed an intensive sampling campaign to acquire first-hand data on the facilitation provided by nurse shrubs on tree seedlings. A case-control approach was applied, walking over the seven hectares of the study area and identifying all seedlings born after the 2015 fire. Once found, ground cover was estimated both in a radius of 20 cm from the seedling, and at a control area of equal surface 3 m eastwards from the seedling.

The effect of successive fires is evident on the recovery process. In the reburned area, seedlings are sparse and mostly found in close proximity to nurse shrubs (Fig. 1). In the harsh conditions created by the passage of two fires, the importance of nurse objects is highlighted. The importance of biological legacies and nurse objects will become increasingly important with warmer and drier climate, and future forest management will have to leverage their presence to ensure the permanence of forests after disturbances.

Figure 1 – A *Pinus halepensis* Mill. seedling (circled) was born at the edge of the canopy of its nurse shrub (*Pistacia lentiscus* L.), leveraging the enhanced microclimatic conditions.

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Assessing the accuracy of wave model data: A bias correction approach for coastal engineering applications

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Abstract

Coastal flooding risk assessment represents a major challenge for coastal scientific and engineering communities, especially in light of the expected sea level rise and changes in extreme events related to climate change. An accurate and reliable evaluation of coastal hazard scenarios claims trustworthy wave data, which conflicts with the inherent uncertainties of historical and future projection wave time series. Therefore, within the framework of Spoke TS2, in cooperation with Spoke VS1, we aim to analyze in depth the available wave time series—including observations, hindcast, reanalysis, and historical and future projections—and perform a bias correction procedure for wave data that takes into account the behavior of extreme events and the intra-annual temporal variability of waves. Thus, such a work is a fundamental step in evaluating properly the risk of wave-induced flooding on critical infrastructure along the Italian coastline.

Hence, our primary purpose is to examine the reliability of the available meteocean data. In particular, we compare the wave model data (i.e., reanalysis, future projections based on RCPs scenarios, and historical projections) from different sources against observations from wave buoys. The benchmark dataset is provided by the National Wave Measurement Network (RON – ISPRA) and other Authorities, while the model data are made accessible through the E.U. Copernicus Climate Change and Marine Services in collaboration with ECMWF, and the MeteOcean Research Group of the University of Genoa (Spoke VS1-Water).

The comparison between benchmark and model datasets through statistic indices reveals incongruities between observations and hindcast data, so highlighting the necessity to correct such model data. The adopted correction procedure is the Distribution Mapping technique, which is a bias adjustment method characterized by its flexibility and ability to account for the extreme values of the distribution (Teutschbein and Seibert, 2012). In the present work, we apply the DM method to the significant wave height parameter both under a stationary approach and taking into account wave temporal variability (Lira-Loarca, et al., 2023). Specifically, we compare the outcomes of the stationary (i.e. without grouping wave data in different timescales) and temporal-correction approaches, including seasonal and monthly corrections. Such a comparison will allow us the selection of the most suitable approach for correcting the historical and future projections time series. The latter may represent a fundamental resource for coastal management and multi-risk assessment.

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Tools for the assessment of landslide-tsunami hazard in marine and coastal environments

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Abstract

Submarine landslide-generated waves have gained increasing attention within the tsunami scientific community. However, they remain a challenging topic, both for the complexity of the underlying physical phenomena and for their relatively low frequency of occurrence, limiting the number of case studies and benchmarks for model validation. The growing availability of computational power has considerably enhanced the possibility to simulate these processes, improving the assessment of the associated coastal hazard (see the review in Yavari-Ramshe and Ataje-Ashtiani, 2016).

Within the general framework of the PNRR project RETURN, and specifically as a part of Vertical Spoke 2 – Ground Instabilities, a set of toolchains has been identified and studied to quantify the conditions for slope instability across various environments. One of these focuses on the predisposition, preparation and trigger of mass collapses in marine settings, including the evaluation of cascading effects such as the generation of a tsunami and its impact on the coast. These processes can be seen as the final steps in a complex chain of events. Here, we present two specific tools designed to assess tsunami hazard in coastal areas.

The first tool correlates specific parameters describing the geomorphology of the submarine landslides (volume, initial slope, depth of occurrence, distance from the coast) with a quantity representing the tsunami impact on the shoreline, namely, the maximum wave amplitude on the coast. This correlation is derived from simulations of multiple landslide-tsunami scenarios, performed through a well-established set of numerical codes (see some applications and further details about the codes in Zaniboni et al., 2021; Gasperini et al., 2022; Gallotti et al., 2023 and in the references therein). The advantage of this approach is its immediate applicability, as it doesn't require the knowledge of sliding dynamics. However, it has some limitations, including site-specificity and an excessively simplistic evaluation of a complex phenomenon that involves numerous non-linear processes. Despite these drawbacks, this type of tool can be adopted to provide a rough, initial estimate of the hazard posed by a potential submarine collapse.

The second tool, which is linked to the first, computes the flow depth profile along a transect starting from the coastline. The tool is based on the Energy Method (EM) approach, as described in Kriebel et al. (2017), which applies considerations on the energy conservation to model the decay of the water column during the inland flooding. In addition to the topographic profile over which the flooding is computed, the EM requires the water amplitude at the initial point of the transect, which coincides with the coast. This allows for the estimation of water height on the structures placed along the profile, thereby assessing the potential impact of flooding associated to the incoming tsunami. This approach has been implemented into a MATLAB code.

These two new tools will be used to simulate scenarios as a proof of concept, linking marine and terrestrial environments and thus helping to mitigate tsunami hazards along the coast.

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Rischi climatici e connessi all'acqua

AMBITO 2

Initial assessments of topographic variability effects on urban pluvial flood modelling accuracy

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Abstract

Pluvial flooding has become an increasing concern due to climate change and rapid urbanization. While advanced models have been developed to simulate these events, challenges related to the quality of input data, particularly topographic resolution, persist.

A key challenge in urban flood modelling is data availability and integration. Urban drainage systems require precise datasets, including topographical details, land use characteristics, and hydraulic properties. However, access to high-resolution datasets is often limited by interoperability issues and inconsistencies between sources, complicating model development and reducing flood prediction accuracy. Additionally, maintaining continuous data collection is crucial, as disruptions can compromise simulation reliability.

Data quality, accuracy, and uncertainty affect model outcomes. Errors in multi-source input data introduce uncertainties, hindering predictive accuracy. Rigorous validation and calibration techniques are necessary to enhance flood model reliability and improve urban flood management strategies. Another critical issue is the spatial and temporal resolution of available data. Pluvial flood dynamics depend on variables such as rainfall intensity, land surface characteristics, and drainage conditions. However, conventional datasets often lack sufficient granularity, limiting the effectiveness of flood mitigation strategies.

This study assesses the sensitivity of pluvial flood models to the different resolution of digital terrain models. A case study in a frequently flooded neighbourhood in Genoa is analysed using HEC-RAS 2D software to model pluvial flooding scenarios and evaluate the impact of topographic variability on simulation accuracy. The research compares simulations generated with different topographic resolutions, providing insights into the importance of high-resolution data in flood modelling.

Figure 1. Aerial distribution of DEM resolution inside the paper analysed in the literature review.

This research's focus on DEM resolution sensitivity originates from a prior literature review (Acquilino M. et al, 2024)), which highlighted the limited discussion of very high resolutions (<1m, see Fig. 1). The study

examines DEMs from open-access platforms, specifically those provided by the Liguria region and the City of Genoa portals, using resolutions of 5m, 1m, and 0.5m and a synthetic rainfall event, derived from a Chicago hyetograph based on regional Depth-Duration-Frequency (DDF) curves, serves as the input for simulations.

HEC-RAS 2D, with its Rain-on-Grid (RoG) module, is utilized to simulate surface water flow, accounting for infiltration and runoff across grid cells.

Being an initial approach to this methodology, the study systematically varies the resolution of input datasets to evaluate their impact on flood modelling.

The analysis of simulation results is for now focused on some performance metrics, such as:

- **Flood Extent and Depth:** Higher-resolution datasets are hypothesized to improve accuracy in predicting flood boundaries and depths.
- **Computational Efficiency:** Processing time and memory usage are evaluated to determine the trade-offs between accuracy and resource consumption.

This research aims to contribute to enhancing urban flood risk assessment and management strategies by identifying optimal dataset characteristics for pluvial flood modelling. The study underscores the necessity of balancing computational efficiency with high-resolution input data. It provides valuable insights for future urban hydraulic modelling and flood mitigation planning while highlighting the need for further refinement, including microtopographic integration and comparative analyses between Digital Elevation Models (DEM) and Digital Surface Models (DSM).

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Comparison of the single-ring Pressure Infiltrometer and SATURO methods for determination of field saturated soil hydraulic conductivity

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Abstract

The study of physical processes related on water-soil interactions crucial aspect in the context of climate change, for mitigating the relates water risks deriving from flood and drought. Saturated soil hydraulic conductivity (K_s) is a key parameter governing water movement through soil, influencing various processes as infiltration, surface runoff, and erosion. Therefore, accurate measurement of K_s is essential for effective soil and water management in both agricultural and environmental contexts.

Among the various methods for determining K_s in the field, the steady, constant-head infiltration technique using a single ring has undoubtedly a wide diffusion, largely due to the physically based analysis of the process by Reynolds and Elrick (1990).

Practical reasons why single-ring, pressure infiltrometer (PI) experiments have received much interest in the literature include: i) higher reliability of steady-state infiltration data and ii) availability of different approaches for conducting a PI experiment and analysing the data, which gives the methodology a certain flexibility. The most commonly applied steady-state approaches are the One-Ponding-Depth (OPD) approach, that uses a single depth of ponding, H , on the infiltration surface and requires an a priori estimate of α^* (parameter that represents the inverse of the macroscopic capillary length) for determining K_s , and the Two-Ponding-Depth (TPD) approach, that uses two H levels to simultaneously estimate K_s , the matric flux potential ϕ_m and α^* .

Both the classical pressure infiltrometer (PI) method and the recently introduced SATURO device can be used to determine field saturated soil hydraulic conductivity, K_s , by a single-ring, steady-state experiment for two ponded depths of water.

The introduction of this new automated device raised or woke up some questions including the impact of the used data validity criterion on soil characterization, the performances of the new methodology as compared with the classical one and the impact of performing K_s calculations by a literature estimate of the so-called α^* parameter.

Therefore, the general objective of this investigation was to examine factors influencing field determination of saturated soil hydraulic conductivity by steady-state, constant-head, single-ring infiltration methods. With reference to three distinct field sites, the specific objectives were to: i) evaluate the effect of the assumed validity criterion of a Two-Ponding-Depth run on K_s determination with the PI and SATURO methos; ii) establish a comparison between these two K_s determination methods; and iii) compare the K_s values obtained by a literature estimate of α^* with those calculated by experimentally determining this parameter.

Figure 1 – Flowchart for estimating saturated hydraulic conductivity of soil from PI and SATURO methods

For two sandy-loam soils and a clay soil, the K_s validity criterion used by SATURO differed from the classical, and more stringent, criterion by the number of valid measurements (success rates of 47-100%, depending on the dataset, in the former case and 13-87% in the latter case) but not appreciably with reference to the summary statistics of the data (means of $K_s = 65$ -527 and 70-300 mm/h, respectively). The PI and SATURO yielded overall similar means of K_s (81-345 and 78-192 and mm/h, respectively, depending on the soil) even if the latter method tended to yield relatively small individual K_s values more frequently than the former one. Using the first approximation value of the α^* parameter for calculating K_s instead of its experimental value yielded means differing by 1.5 times at the most, depending on the site. The classical data validity criterion should be applied since it assures that physically impossible results are considered invalid. In normal use, applying the two tested methods with similar run durations and water volumes can be expected to yield similar K_s values. The first approximation value of α^* could be used instead of the experimental value of this parameter in several circumstances. SATURO appears an interesting alternative to the classical PI method for determining soil hydrodynamic properties by a single-ring, steady-state infiltration experiment. Although the single-ring, steady-state methodology for determining the soil hydrodynamic properties has been in routine use for at least 35 years, some further investigations, also of methodological nature, are therefore still necessary. Hopefully, the recent introduction of SATURO will give new impetus to these investigations. This device appears an interesting alternative to the classical PI method for determining soil hydrodynamic properties by a single-ring, steady-state infiltration experiment. There is room for improving its performances and also simplifying its application in the field.

This study was carried out within the RETURN Extended Partnership and received funding from the European Union Next-GenerationEU (National Recovery and Resilience Plan – NRRP, Mission 4, Component 2, Investment 1.3 – D.D. 1243 2/8/2022, PE0000005)

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Methodology for field and laboratory investigation of river embankment sections affected by Backward Erosion Piping

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Abstract

Backward Erosion Piping (BEP) is a critical internal erosion mechanism that poses a significant threat to the stability of river embankments, particularly those resting on sandy soil layers. This phenomenon typically develops during medium to high-water events due to seepage forces acting within the embankment foundation.

If the underlying sandy layer is unconfined, BEP commonly initiates at the landside toe at the unfiltered exit area, forming a wetland. Alternatively, when a cohesive roof (or "blanket") layer overlays the pervious sandy foundation, BEP can develop at a localized spot farther from the embankment. In this case, erosion pipes form at the interface between the cohesive cover and the underlying sandy layer, as sand particles are transported by the high-velocity underseepage flow to the unfiltered exit. The accumulated sediment at this point creates distinctive features known as "sand boils," or, in Italian jargon, "fontanazzi" (Fig. 1a).

As the erosion pipes expand in size and progress retrogressively toward the source of the hydraulic load, the risk of embankment failure increases. This mechanism has been observed in several sections of the main embankments along the Po River in Italy and in other major water-retaining systems across Europe and worldwide.

Mitigating embankment vulnerability requires a thorough understanding of seepage processes within the permeable foundation layers, especially near and within the exit vertical pipe of the sand boil. Accurately simulating water dynamics in soil layers affected by BEP is essential and depends on a precise definition of the local soil profile and the calibration of key model parameters, achievable only through extensive data collection. This information is obtained from a combination of laboratory and in-situ tests, a well-designed monitoring system, and field records of past sand boil reactivations.

A step-by-step investigation methodology for embankment sections affected (or potentially affected) by BEP is proposed, with reference to two embankment sections along the Po River, located in Guarda Ferrarese (FE) and Mazzorno Sinistro (RO), where several active and dormant sand boils have been observed and monitored. This methodology is designed to guide both researchers and practitioners in selecting appropriate site tests

— both intrusive (Fig.s b and c) and non-intrusive (Fig. 1 d) — laboratory tests, and field tests, as well as in extracting relevant information from test data. The ultimate goal is to elaborate an accurate geological and geotechnical model of the site, incorporating all necessary data for subsequent numerical modelling of the underlying process in the section. This is essential for designing effective mitigation strategies aiming at minimizing BEP risk and ensuring the long-term stability of embankment structures.

Figure 1 – (a) Photo of sand boil 5_19, located in Mazzorno Sinistro (RO) embankment section along the Po river, during reactivation in November 2019; (b) Continuous coring carried out on the crest of Guarda Ferrarese (FE) embankment section along the Po river; (c) Cone Penetration Testing carried out in 2020 in the embankment section of Mazzorno Sinistro (RO) along the Po river; (d) Electrical Resistivity Tomography survey carried out in the Guarda Ferrarese section in 2018.

New approaches for assessing hydraulic hazard in small mountain basins

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Abstract

Climate change is increasing the frequency and intensity of heavy to extreme precipitation events globally, with small mountain basins being particularly vulnerable (Shea et al., 2021). These basins, characterized by steep slopes, rapid hydrological responses, and intense sediment and woody material transport, are more severely affected than larger river basins by intense but short-lived rainfalls, necessitating advanced modeling techniques for accurate risk assessment (Adhikari et al., 2022).

This study, conducted within the PNRR RETURN Extended Partnership (multi-Risk sciEnce for resilient commUnities undeR a changiNg climate) RETURN-PB, introduces innovative approaches for evaluating hydraulic hazards in small mountain basins through a collaborative effort involving 14 Italian universities and research institutions (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The involved institution of this project

The primary objective is to develop a comprehensive manual with guidelines for hydraulic hazard mapping, focusing on debris flows, sediment-laden flood events, and the influence of woody material. To achieve this, an integrated methodology for assessing and mitigating hydraulic hazards is presented, addressing critical hazards such as debris flows, flood events with high solid transport, river floods, surface runoff alluvial events, and the role of woody material. The methodology employs advanced tools and techniques for hazard mapping, aligning with the EU Floods Directive, and specifically addresses scenarios like bank collapses and bridge occlusions. It also identifies the limitations of current methods in accounting for dynamic riverbed processes, such as erosion, elevation changes, and avulsions, and assesses the impact of woody material transport on critical infrastructure. At the core of the methodology is the RETURN framework, which segments the hydrographic network and evaluates hydrological forcings, solid feeding, and woody material transport. This framework integrates 1D and 2D models to simulate debris flow initiation and flood propagation, emphasizing critical sections. Additionally, the methodology incorporates surface runoff hazard mapping and proposes a structured approach for vulnerability and exposure assessments, along with potential risk mitigation strategies.

The approach is demonstrated through multiple case studies across different basin types, including the Alpine basins with high slopes and debris flows (Cancia and Gatria Basins), Apennine/Mediterranean basins with hyper-concentrated transport (Re della Pietra Basin), basins with pyroclastic phenomena/mudflows (Torrente Castello Basin), and basins with ordinary solid transport (Tegnas Basin), with possible additional case studies like the Sesia Basin focusing on wood propagation analysis. The study further investigates model verification and propagation analysis to improve flood hazard mapping, risk assessment, and management strategies for diverse hydraulic events. The approaches are distributed among 14 institutions, each responsible for a specific aspect of the research: synthesis and preparation of a hazard assessment manual (PoliMI), hydrology (UniPD), sediment production and debris flow initiation (PoliMI, UniPD, UniPA), propagation (UniPD, PoliMI), risk mitigation interventions (UniPD), vulnerability and exposure assessment (UniPD), and transported wood and protective forests (UniPD, UniFI). While, the research team at the University of Bolzano is collaborating with the Civil Protection Agency to evaluate the performance of countermeasures in the South Tyrol region. This study part focuses on the design, maintenance, and application of these countermeasures in various small mountain basins, as well as the methods used for risk monitoring and assessment.

The proposed methods and guidelines are still under development. Further changes will be made as needed to enhance the adopted approach, which seeks to improve the accuracy of hydraulic hazard assessments and contribute to more effective risk management strategies in small mountain basins.

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The Valley of the Nuraghi

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Abstract

The widespread presence of monumental architectural episodes of the Nuragic civilization constitutes a founding element in the identity of the Sardinian landscape. This heritage is now exposed to different categories of risk, including anthropogenic risk, linked to the intensification of tourist pressure, and environmental risk, such as hydrogeological risk and fire, phenomena that are increasingly relevant in the context of climate change.

Our group's research examines the landscape unit of the bottom of the valley of the Nuraghe of Santu Antine (UNESCO candidate) in the territory of Torralba in the province of Sassari, encompassing in a larger perimeter the *Valley of the Nuraghi*, as an area of study in which the very high concentration of protohistoric architecture favors an integrated reflection on risk factors within a coherent territorial framework. The contemporary appearance of this area testifies to the continuity and presence of environmental invariants that unite the Nuragic civilization and later eras, setting up a stratified rural landscape that has become emblematic of the region of Sardinia.

The wealth of layered signs attests to the settlement continuity of the Valley of the Nuraghi and makes the area an exemplary case study for analyzing the relationship between the archaeological heritage and the surrounding landscape, critically assessing site fragilities and identifying mitigation and adaptation strategies.

The intervention explores ways to respond to the vulnerabilities of the area, integrating approaches of active conservation, enhancement and sustainable landscape management. Through a multidisciplinary analysis involving archaeological, landscape and environmental aspects, innovative scenarios for site protection begin to be outlined, considering design actions capable of connecting historical memory with contemporary needs for use and protection.

Architectural intervention does not seem to be able to be limited to the preservation of the artifact, but rather it must extend to the dynamic relationship between the nuraghe and the territory, aiming at management models that modulate the impact of tourist flows, implement hydrogeological risk prevention strategies and adopt fire protection measures.

In this sense, the contribution would introduce to the consideration of how the disciplines of architectural and landscape design can become an effective means of ensuring the resilience and sustainability of Sardinia's cultural heritage.

This contribution is part of the investigations conducted by the University of Cagliari's work unit within Spoke 7 of the RETURN project. The group's research activity centers on Work Package 7.3 [Multi Risk (MR) assessment for Cultural Heritage (CH) and role of CH on resilience] and, specifically, our contribution aims to focus on Task 7.3.1 (Valuing CH exposure to MR, special focus on art cities, intangible social, aesthetic, and spiritual values).

**Progetto RETURN
T7.3.1**

**La Valle dei Nuraghi
02_Inquadramento generale dei
beni nuragici**

Unità paesaggistica di fondovalle in relazione con il Nuraghe di Santu Antine (candidato UNESCO) comprendente in un perimetro esteso la Valle dei Nuraghi.

La continuazione della Valle verso i settori settentrionali è limitata con il segno tratteggiato adiacenti ai centri abitati di Mores e Ittireddu.

In legenda sono indicati i principali beni nuragici e le denominazioni note su fonte GIS Sardegna Archeologica.

- 380 m s.l.m.
- unità paesaggistica
- - - Comune di Torralba
- ☐ santuario
- ⊗ pozzo sacro
- ⌘ tomba dei giganti
- ⊕ protonuraghe
- ⊗ nuraghe complesso
- ⊗ nuraghe complesso misto
- ⊗ nuraghe monotorre
- ⊗ nuraghe non classificato
- ⊗ nuraghe scomparso
- ⊗ insediamento

(Elaborazione a cura dell'Università di Cagliari - DICAAR, elaborazione da Cadimu, Orione 2024.).

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Biological removal of 1,2- dichloroethane from real polluted groundwater laboratory-scale experiments

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Abstract

Groundwater pollution represents a major concern due to the risk of contamination of drinking water with chemicals that cannot be removed by conventional processes available in drinking water facilities. Among others, chlorinated solvents are a subgroup of organ-halogen compounds widely used in various industrial sectors that can be released into the environment and reach the aquifers (De Marines et al., 2023).

In situ remediation technologies such as permeable reactive barriers (PRB) are capable to promote biological degradation processes thanks to reactive materials and mechanisms useful to promote biogeochemical reactions for contaminant removal in groundwater (Sakr et al., 2023).

Biodegradation of chlorinated solvents can take place via anaerobic as well as aerobic routes. Two known metabolic pathways lead to chlorinated solvents aerobic degradation (Cruciata et al., 2024): direct oxidation where chlorinated compounds act as electron donor and growth substrate for microorganisms, and aerobic cometabolism where oxygenases enzymes, fortuitously catalyze the oxidation of the chlorinated compound. When oxygen is not available, biological reductive dechlorination (BRD) is carried out by specialized organohalide respiring bacteria (OHRB) (Song et al., 2023) that convert polychlorinated compounds in less chlorinated by-products, and in non-toxic and conventionally biodegradable products (Amanat et al., 2022). BRD can be enhanced using poly- β -hydroxybutyrate (PHB) that can be hydrolysed simultaneously releasing electron donors and carbonaceous substrates that can support the long-term growth of dechlorinating bacteria (Amanat et al., 2022).

An experimental apparatus made of 4 column-shape plug flow reactors has been used to gain insights about the feasibility of 1,2-dichloroethane (1,2-DCA) removal through biostimulated and bioaugmented biological processes in laboratory-scale PRB using real polluted groundwater. Both aerobic and anaerobic biodegradation pathways have been investigated. The experimental apparatus is depicted in figure 1.

Figure 1 – a) The anaerobic experimental apparatus and the b) aerobic experimental apparatus

In the anaerobic apparatus a dechlorinating consortium (obtained by enrichment culture using a real 1,2-DCA-contaminated groundwater and PHB powder as electron donor)(De Marines et al., 2023) was inoculated in the column-shape reactors that were fed during 81 days with the same real groundwater rich in 1,2 DCA. The four glass columns were filled with sterile silica sand, simulating PRB, and differentiated as follows. The first represents the biotic control, characterized by the inoculation of the consortium of 1-2-DCA-degrading bacteria, the second represented the abiotic control blank while the third and fourth, in addition to the bacterial inoculum, were amended with PHB. In the third line PHB was present in the form of granules and powder, while in the fourth line PHB was embedded within highly engineered and biodegradable scaffolds to be used at the same time as a physical support for the microbial biofilm and as electron donor for the BRD.

The same experimental apparatus was used to set an aerobic experiment using an oxygen release compound (ORC) powder that was mixed with the silica sand used for column filling. In details column 1 was filled with silica and ORC and was fed with groundwater spiked with NaN_3 (sodium azide) used as sterilizing agent. Column 1 was used to investigate whether non biological process could occur in 1,2 DCA removal. Column 2 was filled with silica sand and ORC and was fed with real 1,2-DCA contaminated groundwater. Column 2 allowed investigating the natural attenuation gained thanks to autochthonous bacteria present in groundwater if oxygen was available. Columns 3 and 4 were filled with silica sand inoculated with a 1,2 DCA-degrading aerobic bacterial consortium (Cruciata et al., 2024); ORC was added to column 3. Column 3 and 4 allowed comparing the bioaugmentation effect with the bacterial consortium, with and without the presence of oxygen.

In each period all the columns were fed with a constant flow rate set, in order to maintain the hydraulic retention time of each column close to 24 h. During both periods liquid samples were collected each 10 days from the outlet of each column and 1,2 DCA concentration analyzed by GC/MS equipped with head space sampler. Analytical results showed the higher 1,2 DCA removal efficiency (70%) in column 4 for the anaerobic experiment, while the aerobic system allowed almost complete (99%) 1,2 DCA removal in column 3. The anaerobic experiment revealed also that the PHB presence favored the 1,2 DCA degradation process, indeed in first and second column, where no PHB was present, the 1,2 DCA removal efficiency remained below 30%. While during aerobic experiment it was possible noticing the effect of the degrading aerobic bacteria consortium that increased the 1,2 DCA removal efficiency over 90%.

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Mapping Urban Resilience: A Framework for Indicator-Based Spatial Evaluation

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Abstract

Urban resilience has become a central theme in contemporary spatial planning and studies. Defined as the capacity of cities to withstand and recover from shocks and stresses (Meerow et al., 2016), urban resilience offers a framework for reshaping planning practices while accounting for the impacts of increasing natural and anthropogenic risks.

In particular, measuring urban resilience is essential for implementing effective strategies, making the development of a comprehensive resilience evaluation framework crucial (Sharifi & Yamagata, 2016).

This research aims to create a catalogue of indicators for urban resilience measurement to support spatial planning and policies in different contexts. Through an extensive literature review on Scopus databases, the study highlights how inconsistencies in the definition of urban resilience hinder the adoption of standardized metrics. Many of the indicators found in the literature primarily relate to vulnerability, exposure, or sustainability, rather than directly to urban resilience. Additionally, studies on resilience indicators often lack spatial outputs or clear calculation methodologies. To address this gap, the research gathers indicators from scientific literature and integrates them with those derived from context-specific sources, resulting in a catalogue of 75 relevant, calculable, and spatially mappable indicators. This catalogue serves as a foundational resource that can be tailored to the specific context of an area and the availability of data.

This catalogue of resilience indicators is currently being tested in a real-world case study in the northern part of Turin, Italy. This area encompasses three neighbourhoods characterized by complex and diverse landscapes, both ecologically and socially. This urban context faces various risks and vulnerabilities, including hydrogeological risk, drought, the urban heat island effect, air pollution, and social vulnerability. Key elements shaping the territory include the Po River, the plain-hills interface, Meisino Park, and the abandoned “Manifattura Tabacchi” factory. Additionally, the area is undergoing significant planning transformations, according to both the Municipal Land Use Plan (*Piano Regolatore Generale* - PRG) and the Piedmont Po Nature Park Plan, currently under revision. Notable examples of urban transformation and regeneration interventions include the planned new subway line and its stations, as well as the renovation of Manifattura Tabacchi into a cultural hub and university campus.

The selection of indicators is guided by data availability, the capacity to be spatialized, and their significance at the chosen scale. However, the research faces several challenges and limitations, particularly due to the lack of complete and precise data at the sublocal level. In addition, not all attributes identified in the scientific literature are useful for urban planning representation. Moving forward, the study aims to refine the framework and application of resilience indicators, focusing on their normalization and weighting to enhance readability and replicability, also enabling comparisons with different methods and case studies. A crucial next step involves conducting an integrated critical analysis of interrelated groups of indicators to provide a comprehensive interpretation of the resilience capacity of the territory.

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Assessing Livestock Vulnerability in Floodwaters

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Abstract

Flooding poses significant risks to the livestock sector (Inchaisri et al. 2013), yet the vulnerability of farm animals has received limited attention compared to other exposed categories such as buildings, crops, or pedestrians. This study addresses this gap by providing vulnerability functions for livestock.

A conceptual model identifies the threshold at which common farm animals (e.g., sheep, pigs, and cows) lose stability in floodwaters. Two flow conditions are analyzed: choked flow (moderate Froude numbers) and free outflow (high Froude numbers). For each condition, two instability modes are also considered: toppling (when the destabilizing moment induced by the drag force exceeds the resisting moment due to the animal weight), and sliding (when drag force exceeds the frictional force between the animal and the ground). Numerical simulations are then conducted using a 3D Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) model to estimate drag and lift coefficients for the partially-submerged animals.

Results show that larger animals, such as cows, are generally more stable than smaller ones like sheep and pigs, but all animals become highly vulnerable in high-velocity flash floods.

To provide an intelligible measure of hydraulic hazard, a lumped parameter, W , is introduced to combine water depth, Y , and flow velocity, U , into a single indicator (Lazzarin et al. 2022):

$$W = \left(\frac{Y}{Y_W} \right)^\alpha (1 + \beta F^2) \quad \mathbf{F} = \frac{U}{\sqrt{gY}}$$

with $Y_W = 1.0$ m, $\alpha = 2.9$ and $\beta = 10$.

This lumped parameter for hydrodynamic forcing allows vulnerability to be expressed as $V = V(W)$. By matching iso- W curves with iso-vulnerability curves of Giorgetti et al. (2013) (for intermediate conditions) and by integrating instability thresholds from the conceptual model (for incipient stability conditions), a set of (W , V) couples is derived. These points are interpolated with continuous functions to obtain vulnerability curves in the form:

$$V(W) = \frac{1}{1 + (p/W)^q}$$

with $p = 0.16, 1.05, 0.26$ and $q = 2.5, 2.8, 2.5$ for sheep, cows, and pigs, respectively (Fig.1).

These curves offer practical tools for estimating the probability of damage or loss under different flood scenarios. By combining a conceptual framework, numerical modeling, and available data, the study provides a tool for predicting flood damage in the agricultural sector more accurately. The results can also support flood management strategies by integrating vulnerability curves into early warning systems and evacuation plans, helping farmers to reduce losses.

Although this study represents a first step in proposing vulnerability functions for livestock, further experimental data and ex-post assessments are needed to improve their accuracy.

Figure 1 – Vulnerability curves for three farm animals (sheep, pig, cow)

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Monitoring Adige River Levees with Distributed Temperature Sensing

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Abstract

The Adige Valley has a history of severe flooding, with notable events in 1882, 1966, and 1981. Following the 1981 incident, the Autonomous Province of Bolzano initiated an extensive monitoring program of the Adige river embankments, including various studies and modeling efforts.

In spring 2021, a test site was established on the right-hydraulics side of Adige levees, near the village of Salerno (Figure 1a). This experimental area features a network of five boreholes strategically positioned in a square configuration with 20 m sides: the central borehole (S3) is situated along the embankment's central axis and penetrates to a depth of 30 m (Figure 1b). The other four boreholes—S1 and S2 on the landside, and S4 and S5 on the waterside—reach a depth of 25 m. A comprehensive geotechnical characterization of the site is provided by Fabbian et al. (2024). This note presents and analyzes a selection of data collected over the past four years, offering insights into the monitoring results of the site.

To facilitate the study of seepage patterns within and beneath the levee, different kinds of monitoring devices were installed. Each borehole houses two transducers (T1-T10), positioned at various depths (Figure 1b): each of them measures both pressure and temperature, offering accuracies of 2 kPa and 0.1°C, respectively. Furthermore, a Distributed Temperature Sensing (DTS) cable in optical fiber was installed to capture temperature fluctuations along the entire length of each borehole, with a spatial resolution of 2 m and a temperature precision of 0.1°C (Schenato et al., 2022). All monitoring equipment is affixed to a micro-slotted pipe within the boreholes. To prevent water flow, the corner boreholes were filled with bentonite, while the central borehole was left unfilled to allow for additional testing (Fabbian et al., 2024). The DTS cable, configured in a U-loop design, forms a continuous optical pathway through all boreholes. A total of 21 manual lectures at DTS were occasionally performed up to 18th September 2024. After that moment, the system has been automatically monitored, with a time interval of 2 hours, by an interrogator installed at the hydrometric station 200 m from the site.

Figure 1 – (a) Test site in Salerno - km 122.70 and (b) location of sensors along boreholes (Fabbian et al., 2024).

Over the four-year period of monitoring, three medium-high intensity flood events were observed, providing valuable insights into the monitoring system reliability and the embankment condition. Pressure sensors

demonstrated different sensitivity to river level fluctuations based on their position, while temperature sensors in the embankment foundation layers showed minimal influence from river water or air temperature changes. Even if the DTS records the temperature inside all the boreholes, for brevity, only measurements of boreholes S2 and S4 (Figure 1a) are considered here. The manual measurements taken in S2 at different times are shown in Figure 2a. Seasonal fluctuations due to solar radiation and heat exchange with the atmosphere are evident in the embankment body and the first foundation layer. These fluctuations affect only the surface layers (5-7 m) due to the generally low thermal conductivity of soils. Deeper layers show a nearly uniform temperature vertically, oscillating within a range of about $\pm 1^\circ\text{C}$ around the annual average air temperature of the site (approximately 11°C). The warmest period typically occurs in summer, between June and August, while the coldest period is at the end of winter or early spring. However, the manual and irregular nature of the measurements makes it difficult to pinpoint exact dates for temperature extremes.

Figure 2 – Vertical distribution of temperature measured with DTS: (a) manual lectures occasionally taken in S2 at the landside; (b) and (c) automatic lectures taken every 2 hours along boreholes S2 (landside) and S5 (waterside), between 18 September and 13 November 2024.

Figures 2b and 2c show the temperature acquired in S2 and S5 in automatic in the period 18 September – 13 November 2024. A flood event occurred at 8/10/2024. It caused rapid saturation of surface soil layers, resulting in a temperature decrease of about $3\text{--}6^\circ\text{C}$ in the levee, due either to rain infiltration on landside (Figure 2b) or to seepage from the river on the waterside (Figure 2c). A warm core (warm colors in Figure 2) persisted in the center of the embankment body, slightly expanding towards the countryside side over time (1-5 m depth). This migration is attributed to relatively warmer water moving from inside the embankment towards the countryside along a sandy layer about 10 m below the embankment top. A good agreement between temperatures measured by traditional transducers and the DTS system was observed for all the boreholes. Both systems show no temperature variations beyond 12 m depth below the embankment crest.

The measurements performed so far evidence that the monitoring of temperature can give additional information about the water seepage in the dikes. To this aim the DTS automatic measurements complement and enrich the data acquired by conventional monitoring systems, providing a more comprehensive representation of the temperature field and filtration process and offering insights into temperature changes that manual measurements alone cannot capture.

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Estimates of the probability of unprecedented weather extremes from short observational records

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Abstract

Traditional methodologies for the estimation of large extremes do not make good use of the available observations and are not specifically designed to be applied under changing climatic conditions. Here we illustrate the formulation and application of the Metastatistical Extreme Value Distribution (MEVD), an approach that uses all available observations, rather than relatively few large values. We examine how the MEVD significantly improves our ability to estimate the probability of occurrence of events that are not present in the observational record. Illustrative examples are drawn from daily precipitation at the global scale, flood magnitudes in the continental USA, storm surges in the Northern Adriatic sea, droughts as observed through tree ring records, the unprecedented flood event in the Romagna Region (Italy) in May 2023, extreme Atlantic Hurricanes.

The MEVD (Marani & Ignaccolo, 2015), as applied to rainfall, expresses the cumulative probability distribution of the maximum yearly rainfall depth as:

$$G_x = 1 - T_j = 1 - T F(x; \mathbf{p}_j)^{n_j}$$

Where $F(x; \mathbf{p}_j)$ is the distribution of “ordinary” values in year j , with parameter vector \mathbf{p}_j , while n_j is the number of events in year j . T is the number of years on record. Parameter values are estimated based on all the observed ordinary events, rather than just on yearly maxima, as for the Generalized Extreme Value distribution (GEV), leading to a better use of the available information. This contribution discusses how this formulation leads to a reduction, with respect to traditional approaches relying on the Generalized Extreme Value distribution, of up to 50% in the case of daily rainfall extremes (Zorzetto et al., 2016), of about 70% for extreme Atlantic Hurricanes (Hosseini et al., 2020). The widespread improvements in extreme flood magnitudes obtained in thousands of study cases across the continental US (Miniussi et al., 2020) are also discussed, along with the advantages of the MEVD in applications to storm surges (Caruso & Marani, 2022), to historical droughts, to the estimation of extremes in ungauged locations, as well as in exploring the relative importance of local thermodynamics vs. large scale circulation in determining the mechanisms of climatic changes in the hydrological cycle.

One further advantage of the MEVD is that the probability distribution of ordinary events and the number of events/year appear separately in the MEVD formulation. This property allows the separate estimation of distributional parameters from large datasets from wide areas, while the number of events is computed based on the relatively shorter records at a point of interest.

In closing, summary conclusions are drawn from the large amount of case studies examined, and current and future developments are drawn.

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Signal of temporal changes in ordinary and extraordinary precipitation extremes over Italy

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Abstract

Understanding how rainfall extremes are changing over time is critical for infrastructure planning, hydrological risk assessment, and climate adaptation strategies. However, in a complex geographical setting like Italy, characterized by diverse topography and meteorological influences, detecting trends at the national scale presents significant challenges.

This study was designed to provide a comprehensive evaluation of temporal variations in short-duration (1 to 24 hours) rainfall extremes across Italy by analyzing the most extensive and up-to-date dataset of annual maximum rainfall depths, derived from I²-RED, the Improved Italian - Rainfall Extreme Dataset (Mazzoglio et al., 2020). The dataset consists of more than 5500 time series covering the period from 1916 up to 2022. Unlike studies based on reanalysis data or output of climate models, which may introduce uncertainties due to model ability in reproducing rainfall extremes and coarse spatial resolution, our analysis relies entirely on direct rain gauge observations.

Two complementary techniques were applied: (i) the non-parametric Mann-Kendall test with Sen's slope estimator for at-site trend detection and (ii) a distributed quantile regression analysis for a gridded investigation. The latter method is applied within a moving window approach, pooling data from rain gauges within a defined radius to increase the robustness of the estimates.

Our results indicate that changes in rainfall extremes across Italy are highly heterogeneous, with modest spatial variations. While no widespread national-scale trend is observed, regional-scale patterns clearly emerge in the results obtained by applying the two different approaches.

One of the most interesting findings obtained with the quantile regression is the stronger magnitude of trends in higher quantiles compared to ordinary rainfall extremes. While median rainfall intensities (50th percentile) exhibit only modest changes over time, extraordinary extremes (95th and 99th percentiles) show much more pronounced variations. This suggests that the most intense precipitation events are becoming even more extreme in certain regions, while ordinary rainfall remains relatively stable.

Such results have significant implications for hydrological design and flood risk assessment, as they highlight the necessity of considering not only mean changes in precipitation but also shifts in the most extreme events. From a hydrological design perspective, the evidence of increasing trends in extraordinary extremes calls for updated intensity-duration-frequency (IDF) curves that reflect these changes, particularly in regions where significant increases in extreme precipitation have been detected. Additionally, while negative trends in certain areas may suggest a reduction in design rainfall values, caution is advised in such adjustments due to the inherent uncertainty in future rainfall variations.

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40 years of annual shoreline evolution: the case of the Emilia-Romagna coast

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Abstract

Sea-level rise, subsidence, coastal stiffening due to human activities and land use are major threats to coastal communities, affecting hundreds of millions of people living in low-lying areas nearby the sea (Neumann et al., 2015). Thus, understanding the processes driving coastal evolution is essential for effective management. The 130 km-long Emilia-Romagna (ER) coast, a low-lying sandy shoreline, has undergone significant anthropogenic modifications since the 1950s, reducing its resilience to coastal hazards. Subsidence, rising sea levels, and sediment supply deficit have further increased its vulnerability to flooding. This study addresses some key knowledge gaps by reconstructing annual-averaged shoreline positions of the ER coastal system over a 40-year period (1984-2023) within the framework of activities of Spoke DS8 in the RETURN project.

The satellite-derived shoreline extraction was performed using the CoastSat toolbox (Vos et al., 2019), one of the most advanced methodologies for instantaneous shoreline detection. CoastSat operates semi-automatically by identifying the most likely land-water transition point at each cross-shore transect, set in this study at 50-meter lateral spacing, using the Otsu threshold method. Each transect serves as a fixed reference, measuring shoreline displacement over time. Shoreline positions were extracted from all available satellite images from the Landsat and Sentinel-2 missions. To enhance accuracy, a despiking algorithm and post-processing filtering were applied to minimize false detections and remove interference from coastal rivers and lagoons.

To construct a reliable dataset of shoreline evolution over the 40-year study period, the influence of tides, wind setup, and beach slope was removed during CoastSat extraction. Tidal corrections were derived from high-frequency (1-hour) records from two tide gauges (2000–2023) located along the ER coast, with 69 harmonic components extracted and extended back to 1984. Wind setup effects were estimated using wave data from the ERA-5 reanalysis (covering the full period) and local buoy observations available since 2007. Finally, beach slope was estimated for different coastal sectors using topo-bathymetric profiles from the regional Environmental Agency, covering the years 1984, 1993, 2000, 2006, 2012, and 2018, with elevation data extending from the emerged beach to the depth of closure. After removing seasonality and interpolating intersection points laterally, the final processed annual shorelines for the study period were computed (see example in Figure 1). This dataset covers nearly the entire regional coastline, excluding harbors, small inlets, and the northernmost "Sacca di Goro" sector due to intrinsic limitations.

Preliminary analysis indicates widespread shoreline accumulation over 40 years, primarily driven by the presence of hard defense structures and by repeated nourishment interventions. Longshore sediment redistribution also influenced coastal dynamics, creating localized erosion and deposition, particularly near long piers acting as barriers. Additionally, shoreline shifts occasionally reflect local sea-level variations, with retreat (advance) corresponding to anomalously high (low) sea levels. Generally, the approach enabled, for the first time in the area, the extraction of continuous time series of annual shoreline evolution (Figure 1), providing a direct assessment of the overall tendency of specific coastal sectors and allowing evaluation of

non-linearities over time. The use of satellite-derived shoreline data thus proved to be an efficient, cost-effective tool for coastal monitoring and management.

Figure 1 – (Left panel) Aerial photograph of a portion of the Emilia-Romagna coast showing the position of the 40 annually averaged shorelines. (Right panel) The corresponding time series, illustrating shoreline evolution over time. Shoreline cross-shore displacement in meters (black solid line), with related 1σ (gray shaded area), is referenced to 1984 (set to zero), while the y-axis on the right side represents sediment nourishment volumes ($m^3 \times 10^3$) for specific years, indicated by vertical orange bars. The red hatched line represents the long-term linear trend (0.15 ± 0.22 m/yr in this case), while the black hatched line indicates the theoretical shoreline evolution considering only the effects of sea-level rise and local subsidence. The green-shaded area marks the time span during which defense structures were placed in the nearshore.

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Flood risk mitigation and ecosystem resilience: insights from the Venice Lagoon (Italy)

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Abstract

Low-lying coastal areas, home to approximately 11% of the global urban population, face increasing flood risks due to sea level rise and extreme weather events, threatening the resilience of coastal communities. Over the past decades, adapting to these escalating hazards has required the implementation of hard-engineering structures (e.g., storm-surge barriers and floodgates), resulting in 18 major projects completed worldwide (Mooyaart & Jonkman, 2017). While these structures are essential for protecting and sustaining the socio-economic functioning of coastal cities, they can trigger unintended ecomorphodynamic feedbacks, inducing tidal asymmetries that alter sediment transport processes (Tognin et al., 2022).

This study focuses on the Venice Lagoon, Italy, where a storm-surge barrier system (i.e., the *Mo.S.E. system*, an Italian acronym for “Modulo Sperimentale Elettromeccanico”), has been protecting Venice City and the surrounding lagoonal settlements from storm surges since October 3rd 2020. We performed hydrodynamic numerical simulations to compare different floodgate management approaches, aiming to balance urban protection and ecosystem resilience.

Using a two-dimensional hydrodynamic model (Carniello et al., 2005, 2011) we simulated tidal and wind-wave-induced circulations across the entire Venice Lagoon from 2020 to 2023. The results from the current flood-regulated scenario (“MoSE scenario”) were compared with those from a hypothetical non-regulated condition (“OPEN scenario”). A third scenario was also considered, evaluating the impacts of a more tailored flood-management approach based on the Adaptive Threshold Operative Strategy (AThOS, Mel et al. (2021)), which aims to minimize closure frequencies and durations. Specifically, we investigated how water levels within the lagoon were distributed during floodgate activations to determine the spatial and temporal extent of flooding in Venice City and the lagoon’s salt marshes. Maintaining adequate flooding depth and duration in these marshes during storm surges is crucial for ecosystem resilience, as it ensures mineral sediment deposition and vertical accretion in response to rising relative sea levels (Tognin et al., 2021).

Our analysis reveals a critical imbalance in the coastal management of the Venice Lagoon. While storm-surge barriers effectively reduce flooding risks, we found that during floodgate operation, water levels in major lagoonal settlements (i.e., Venice, Chioggia, and Burano) were maintained, on average, 30% below the local safety thresholds. Although this guarantees total flood protection, frequent and prolonged activations significantly limit—or even prevent—salt marsh flooding, hindering the deposition of mineral sediments on marsh soils (Figure 1). Retrospective analyses based on the optimized AThOS scenario suggest that reducing floodgate operation duration could increase lagoonal water levels by 25%, allowing for sufficient flooding of salt marsh surfaces while still meeting the urban safety thresholds.

The Venice Lagoon emerges as a key case study, offering valuable insights into the challenges of sustainable management of coastal cities and ecosystems in the future. These findings underscore the need for a more tailored approach, demonstrating the feasibility of balanced management strategies that effectively safeguard urban areas from flooding while preserving the ecological resilience of estuarine ecosystems.

Figure 1: Flooding area for Venice city (left) and for salt marshes (right) according to different flood-regulation management scenarios (i.e., OPEN, MoSE, and AThOS).

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Global landslide survey in permafrost regions using molards as a geomorphological landmark

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Abstract

This study presents the first global inventory of landslide deposits with permafrost molards. Climate warming is inducing permafrost thaw in Arctic and mountain areas worldwide, resulting in increased loss of stability in hillslopes and consequently a rising frequency of landslides. These landslides are particularly hazardous due to their unpredictability, and can lead to cascading events such as tsunamis, river damming, and glacial lake outburst floods. Until now, there has been no global inventory of landslides associated with permafrost degradation, and this limited our understanding of global landslide responses to climate change in permafrost regions.

The detection of permafrost molards in landslide deposits has emerged as an effective method for identifying degrading permafrost in landslide detachment zones. Permafrost molards are conical mounds of loose debris found in periglacial terrains, formed by the degradation of ice-cemented blocks which have been transported downslope by landslides. These blocks are fragments of the frozen material from the landslide's source area. So far, permafrost molards have been considered rare and with only local significance.

In this study, we analyse the permafrost, geological, and geomorphological settings of 101 landslides featuring permafrost molards. Our findings reveal that these molards are widespread across terrains with various permafrost types, from continuous to isolated. The source materials of these landslides primarily consist of loose debris or mechanically weak bedrock, which are conducive to hosting ground ice. These findings are a crucial backbone for identifying other terrains in permafrost environments that could be prone to failure. 70% of these landslides have occurred recently and are located in areas where permafrost is modelled to be present, indicating that in periglacial environments landslides with molards can serve as local indicators of permafrost presence and its recent or ongoing degradation.

Our research demonstrates that landslides with permafrost molards are far more common than previously thought. They provide valuable insights into the state of permafrost conditions and help quantify the relationship between landslide occurrences and climate variations in periglacial environments on a global scale.

Climate Change Information through Climate Indicators: examples of applications to ecosystems and socio-economic sectors in Italy

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Abstract

One of the major objectives of the DS spoke is the identification of impact-oriented hazard indicators relevant for both national natural environments and economic sectors. Among these indicators, those based on climatic data are related to hazards liable to be affected by climatic change. So, it is important to understand if and how much of the projected climate change under different scenarios can significantly modify the risk assessment with respect to the current situation, and how to deliver this information to the users.

In this work we present some preliminary results, for selected applications and test cases, of climate indicators based on temperature and precipitation climatic variables derived from new high-resolution (5 km) climate projections over the Italian peninsula, for both present climate and future scenarios (SSP1-2.6, SSP2- 4.5 and SSP5-8.5), as obtained by downscaling the corresponding global ERA5 and MPI-ESM1-2-HR driven CMIP6 experiments (Struglia et al ,2025).

We import the indicators into a GIS environment to facilitate their visualization at different levels of aggregation based on territorial and administrative boundaries. This approach may also be useful for comparing climate indicator information with other information layers (e.g. presence of critical infrastructures or maps of hazard for which the climate factor may be a predisposing or triggering factor) also in synergy with other spoke activities and in the perspective of the realization of a Decision Support System.

Figure 1 – From climate data to information

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Blue Carbon Potential of Venice Lagoon Marshes: Challenges and Opportunities for Coastal Management

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Abstract

Coastal areas are crucial for human development and economic activities, providing essential ecological functions and a wide range of ecosystem services that enhance human well-being (Barbier et al., 2011). However, these ecosystems are increasingly threatened by anthropogenic pressures and climate change impacts, such as flooding and coastal erosion, which are causing significant economic and social damage. This growing vulnerability highlights the urgent need for risk mitigation and damage prevention through effective adaptation strategies.

In this context, the protection and restoration of coastal ecosystems have gained attention as effective Nature-based Solutions. For example, restoring or protecting coastal wetlands can enhance resilience to storms by acting as natural barriers while also supporting biodiversity, promoting fisheries, and creating opportunities for tourism. Additionally, vegetated coastal ecosystems—such as mangroves, tidal marshes, and seagrass meadows—are increasingly recognized for their capacity to sequester and store large amounts of carbon, playing a potentially significant role in climate mitigation strategies (Macreadie et al., 2019). These ecosystems exhibit exceptionally high carbon burial rates per unit area, making them valuable for blue carbon initiatives (McLeod et al., 2011). Carbon markets offer a potential funding mechanism to support the conservation and restoration of coastal wetlands and their associated functions. However, before blue carbon projects can be effectively implemented, it is essential to quantify the carbon stored in these ecosystems and identify the environmental conditions that optimize carbon sequestration.

In this study, we analysed soil organic carbon (SOC) content, carbon stocks, and carbon accumulation rates in various marshes of the Venice Lagoon (Italy), one of the largest and most ecologically significant transitional ecosystems in the Mediterranean. Over the centuries, the Venice Lagoon has undergone substantial human-induced alterations, leading to a significant reduction in salt marsh habitats. In response, several marsh restoration projects have been implemented since the late 20th century to mitigate these losses (Quintana et al., 2018).

Our estimates suggest that the studied marshes can accumulate an amount of carbon equivalent to that absorbed by 130,000 trees, highlighting the economic value associated with their protection and restoration (Puppini et al., 2024). However, we also observed that restored marshes do not always exhibit the same blue carbon content as natural marshes, emphasizing the need for further research into the environmental factors that enhance carbon accumulation in marsh soils (e.g., vegetation characteristics, sediment properties, and geomorphological dynamics). Additionally, our findings suggest that flood regulation measures implemented to protect the city of Venice—which limit the vertical accretion capacity of marshes—could significantly reduce their carbon sequestration potential, with losses exceeding 30%. These insights provide valuable guidance for improving coastal management and marsh restoration strategies, optimizing their effectiveness as Nature-based Solutions to enhance blue carbon potential.

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High resolution km-scale modeling of the Northern Adriatic region

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Abstract

The Northern Adriatic region (proof-of-concept Return WP2 Spoke 8) is an area located in the northern-eastern part of the Mediterranean region characterized by the presence of significant steep orographic features, strong air-sea interactions and the Po basin river network that is one of the major freshwater sources of the Mediterranean Sea.

Here we introduce and describe the configuration of five different modeling tools of increasing complexity over the Northern Adriatic region: (i) the hydrological model CHyM (Coppola et al., 2007) with an horizontal resolution of approximately 1 km, (ii) the atmospheric regional model RegCM v5 (Giorgi et al., 2023) with an horizontal resolution of 3 km and 41 vertical levels (convection permitting configuration), (iii) the ocean model MITgcm (Marshall et al., 1997) with an horizontal resolution of approximately 700 m and 59 vertical levels (non hydrostatic), (iv) the ocean-biogeochemical model MITgcm-BFM (Cossarini et al., 2017; Vichi et al., 2023), (v) the Regional Earth System Model RegCM-ES (Reale et al., 2020) made by RegCM online coupled with CHyM and MITgcm-BFM. These five different modeling tools have been employed to simulate the features of the recent climate of the Northern Adriatic area (evaluation runs) by using state-of-art reanalysis available for the region as initial/boundary conditions: the ECMWF ERA5 reanalysis for the atmosphere and the Copernicus Marine Service physical reanalysis for the ocean. Similar configurations for the climate run under different emission scenarios (RCP8.5 and SSP7.0) are currently under preparations.

In general, the comparison between the “standalone” RegCM5, MITgcm, CHyM models and the regional Earth System Model RegCM-ES highlight in the latter an improvement in the representation of the precipitation regime (Figure 1), the sea surface temperature (Figure 2), and the Po river discharge temporal variability. However some overestimation of precipitation over the Alps is observed together with a dry bias in the Po Valley (Figure 1) .

Overall, all these modeling tools offer several indications that they can be used to study the factors driving the climate dynamics of the region, and will soon produce high resolution climate projections for the region.

Figure 1 Daily precipitation (in mm day⁻¹) in the period September–November 1989–1995 according to EURO4AM (left panel), and differences (in %) between daily precipitation (in mm day⁻¹) in the period September–November 1989–1995 simulated by RegCM (central panel) and RegCM-ES (right panel) and EURO4AM. Dots mark the points where these differences are statistically significant with $p < 0.05$ according to the Mann-Whitney test.

Figure 2 Daily Sea Surface Temperature (SST, in °C) in the period September–November 1989–1995 according to the dataset L4 SST reprocessed (first panel from left), average error in the observations (ERROR, second panel from left) and differences with respect to L4 SST reprocessed (in °C) of the daily SST of the Copernic Marine Service Reanalysis in the period September–November 1989–1995 (central panel), RegCM-ES (second panel from right) and MITgcm (first panel from right).

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Call for case studies: learning from infrastructure failures caused by water-related hazards to enhance risk mitigation

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Abstract

In recent decades, the increasing frequency and intensity of water-related hazards have posed significant threats to infrastructures worldwide (Nirandjan et al., 2024). These hazards may occur as compounded, consecutive, or combined to other hazards, exacerbating their impact and challenging disaster risk management (DRM) frameworks (Claassen et al., 2023; Haer and de Ruiter, 2024). Despite advancements in structural and non-structural mitigation measures, infrastructure failures due to extreme hydrologic events result in severe economic, social, and environmental consequences (Kreibich et al., 2020).

We are now launching an initiative to identify key gaps in the management of water-related hazards affecting infrastructures, investigate the interrelationship between different hazards, and assess the effectiveness of mitigation strategies in reducing losses and enhancing resilience.

The study aims at systematically mapping water-related hazards that have impacted infrastructures, evaluating the extent of damage from minor impairments to complete structural failures. By analyzing past case studies, we assess the presence or absence of mitigation measures and their effectiveness in preventing further losses. Structural solutions such as flood barriers, and resilient engineering designs, as well as non-structural measures like early warning systems and land-use planning, are examined to determine their role in mitigating water-related risk.

Disaster risk management (DRM) in the context of hazard-infrastructure interactions remains fraught with challenges. Infrastructure failures disrupt essential services, cause cascading failures in interconnected systems, and exacerbate economic and social vulnerabilities. Our research explores feedback mechanisms between society and extreme events, identifying causal loops that may exacerbate impacts (Matano et al., 2022). For instance, inadequate urban planning and increased development in high-risk zones amplify exposure, while the loss of critical infrastructure hinders emergency response and prolongs recovery (Zampollo et al., 2023). Understanding these feedback loops is essential for designing adaptive and proactive DRM strategies.

The infrastructure recovery process is a critical aspect of post-disaster management. This study aims at evaluating the restoration of physical assets and the recovery timelines. Additionally, we aim at examining the broader societal recovery, considering the socioeconomic impacts of infrastructure failure, disruptions to livelihoods, and the role of social resilience in overcoming long-term consequences.

Ultimately, this study aims to derive lessons from past experiences to improve infrastructure resilience and inform policy recommendations.

By identifying success stories in risk mitigation, we seek to determine whether lessons learned can be effectively applied across different geographical and socio-economic contexts (Kreibich et al., 2020). Strengthening infrastructure resilience against water-related hazards requires an integrated approach that incorporates engineering solutions, governance strategies, community engagement, and climate adaptation measures.

To this purpose, we are calling the scientific community to join our initiative and contribute with case studies that may be suitable for the analysis.

We aim at collecting examples of water-related hazard events that have impacted infrastructures (e.g., dams, levees, diversions, water distribution systems, bridges), resulting in their failure (total or partial, e.g. levee breach, overtopping, seepage, bridge collapse, erosion at the bridge piers, failure of water management structure, dam breach). The call for case studies submissions is now open. You can find more details and submit your contributions by following the link provided through the QR code in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Scan the QR code to access the questionnaire and express your interest in joining this initiative. We aim to collect case studies on water-related single- and multi-risk events (e.g., isolated, triggering, compound, consecutive) that have impacted infrastructure. The brief survey takes just 5 minutes to complete.

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Mercury in the Venice lagoon from sources to receptors: a modelling study

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Abstract

Understanding the fate and transport of pollutants is crucial for assessing and predicting ecosystem exposure. The exposure of humans and ecosystems to mercury (Hg) raised concern after the Minamata disaster in the 1950s. It was later discovered that Hg in the aquatic environment is transformed into the neurotoxic bioaccumulative species methylmercury (MeHg), with methylation potential depending on environmental conditions that control Hg bioavailability and microbial activity (Heyes et al., 2006; Mason et al., 2012).

Numerical models simulate the main processes and the non-linear interactions that determine the evolution of system variables and are therefore valuable tools for studying the environmental dynamics of pollutants. In Spoke VS2 of the RETURN project, we investigate mercury dynamics in the Venice lagoon (Mediterranean Sea) from sources to receptors by coupling a fate and transport model (SHYFEM-Hg) with an individual-based model for the bioaccumulation of Hg in the bivalve *Tapes philippinarum*. The Venice lagoon is contaminated with mercury due to a past discharge from a chlor-alkali plant in the Porto Marghera industrial area, leading to significant Hg enrichment in its sediment (Rosati et al., 2020).

The finite element model SHYFEM-Hg (Rosati et al., 2024) was developed to simulate mercury biogeochemistry and transport driven by sediment dynamics and hydrodynamic in coastal-marine environments at a very high spatial resolution (from 10 m to 1 km). The model solves the photochemical and microbial transformations of Hg species, gaseous exchange, partitioning and exchanges of Hg and particles between sediment and water. Modeled concentrations of Hg species show high temporal and spatial variability in the lagoon, consistent with available observations (Bloom et al., 2004), exceeding those of the open Mediterranean Sea by two orders of magnitude in some areas (Figure 1). Due to sediment contamination, inorganic Hg in water is closely related to sediment resuspension, which is significantly reduced by the presence of benthic vegetation.

Figure 1 – Graphical representation of the main features of the SHYFEM-Hg model showing the unstructured model mesh, the key processes involving mercury species and sediment resolved by the model, and model output of yearly

average Hg and MeHg concentrations in lagoon water.

Dynamic temporal series of Hg and MeHg concentrations in lagoon water and organic particles (POC), as well as water temperature and POC concentration available as food for clams, were extracted from the SHYFEM-Hg at selected stations and used to force a zero-dimensional bioaccumulation model for clam (Figure 2). The latter is developed building on an existing bioenergetic model validated for the growth of *T. philippinarum* in the Venice lagoon (Solidoro et al., 2000, 2003). The bioaccumulation model was calibrated based on experimental data from previous work (Sfriso et al., 2008) by varying the excretion rate and assimilation efficiency.

Modeled concentrations of Hg species in the Venice lagoon water and clam tissues agree reasonably well to field observations. The integration of the two models provides a tool that can be used to assess the distribution of mercury species in the lagoon and their evolution based on environmental changes, estimate Hg levels in commercial shellfish, and select suitable areas for clam farming that also minimize risks from mercury exposure.

Figure 2 – Graphical representation of the off-line coupling between the high-resolution model for fate and transport of mercury and the bioenergetic/bioaccumulation model for clams. The dotted lines represent the time evolution of total Hg concentration in the clam at the two stations San Giuliano (upper panel) and Fusina (lower panel) modeled varying the assimilation efficiency. The 3d plots show the growth rate as a function of water temperature and food availability (concentration of organic particles).

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The record of past fluvial deposits to interpret the effect of climate variations on landscape dynamics: a case study from the Marche Piedmont Zone of the Apennines

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Abstract

Fluvial terraces represent continental records functional to gather information about the history of a drainage system. It has been largely documented that these landforms and their associated deposits provide key insights into the impact of varying climate, base level changes and tectonic activity on landscapes (Merritts et al., 1994). As such, they represent impact-oriented indicators of middle and long-term climatic oscillations. Studying fluvial terraces is crucial for understanding the impact of such changes on fluvial dynamics and for correctly establishing a robust framework to contextualize shorter-term scenarios, directly supporting the objectives of the extended partnership RETURN (multi-Risk sciEnce for resilienT commUnities undeR a changiNg climate).

Our study focuses on a well-preserved staircase of fluvial terraces located in the piedmont zone of the Marche Apennines (central Italy). This has developed from the Middle-Late Pleistocene due to the cyclical alternation of fluvial aggradation and incision, in response to the combination of low-rate tectonic uplift and the climate oscillations occurred during the Quaternary (Nesci et al., 2012). The area is mostly characterized by depositional fill terraces, which are strongly influenced by climatic variations (Lewin and Gibbard, 2010). The already available chronological record from the fluvial deposits of the Marche Region was gathered and analyzed in-deep, concluding that while numerous valleys of the Adriatic piedmont had already a known chronology (see Delchiaro et al., 2024), there was the necessity to expand the geochronological constraints to the older terrace levels. Indeed, the acquisition of reliable and detailed climatic signals from terrace deposits is essential for understanding the long-term relationship between fluvial deposition and incision and climatic variations with a quantifiable approach, providing the basis in modelling scenarios for short-term dynamics. By analyzing the fluvial records of the Tenna, Aso and Tesino Rivers, located in the southern Marche region, the climatic history of the area has been expanded and reviewed.

Geomorphological field surveys have been integrated together with semi-automatically extracted data on the altimetric and along-valley terrace distributions. The terraces have been localized and identified by a semiautomatic extraction of their upper surfaces, isolated with the support of the Surface Classification Model (SCM) and Relative Elevation Models (REMs) converted from 1 m/pixel Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) collected from a 1x1 LiDAR dataset. The SCM model allows the tracing of the terrace features by analyzing the slope and the roughness of the landscape, then the REM elevations are used for preliminary classification as a function of the terrace height above the modern channel thalweg. Infrared Stimulated Luminescence (IRSL) data on terrace chronology have then been obtained and incorporated. These provided geochronological constraints for the cyclical formation and development of the Quaternary fill terrace staircases within the slowly uplifting Adriatic piedmont of the Apennines.

Our findings confirm that the main phases of fluvial aggradation coincided with colder periods, followed by river incision and floodplain-channel abandonment during inter-glacial periods. These results validate previous chronological data from the last fluvial aggradation-incision cycle (Late Pleistocene) and furthermore demonstrate the persistence of this same formation mechanism in the older (Middle Pleistocene) terraces. The use of multiple dated fill terrace staircases allowed the delineation of a long-term

model of the dynamics of fluvial deposition and climatic variations, providing a foundation for numerical modeling to assess the landscape response to modern climate change. Nevertheless, further efforts are required to refine predictive models for actual and future scenarios.

Ultimately, the obtained results showed that the analysis of the fluvial staircases of the Marche piedmont zone of the Apennines and their Middle-to-late Pleistocene deposits as a constrain align indeed with the Italian National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) goal, funded by Next Generation EU, to strengthen research on environmental, natural, and anthropogenic risks related to climate change.

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Flood Susceptibility Mapping using Random Forest with flood inventory and geomorphic features

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Abstract

Flood is one of the most disastrous natural hazards, which is causing enormous economic loss and human casualties, and destroying the environment and cultural heritage. The delineation of the flood prone area and the flood susceptibility mapping are the sufficient methods to address a comprehensive flood risk management. For flood prone area delineation, the development of remote sensing techniques provides a chance to produce the continuous and up-to-date data. And for flood susceptibility mapping, the machine learning technique provides the possibility to mapping flood susceptibility utilizing as much as possible the available geomorphic and hydrological information, such as slope, elevation, precipitation, etc. In the present research, a flood inventory was established using remote sensing data (i.e., Copernicus Emergency Management Service), along with historical flood event records and permanent water areas. Then, Random Forest (RF) was selected as the model to assess the flood susceptibility of the Italian territory. Twenty-four predict factors were evaluated and optimised using the novel Average Merit of Information (AMI) approach and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF), to balance the performance and the efficiency of the model. Eventually, the RF model constructed by the optimal predict factors (includes maximum daily precipitation (MDP), the Geomorphic Flood Index (GFI), horizontal distance from the nearest river (HDNR), elevation, lithology, organic matter, NDVI, land use, and silt) produced the result flood susceptibility map (Figure 1), which shows superior performance when compared with the official flood hazard maps (AUCROC greater than 0.9). It worth to mention that the GFI present a significant role in improving estimation accuracy in most of the areas, though shows limited performance in extensively flat areas as the geomorphic indicators are less distinct. In conclusion, the present study underscores the importance of up-to-date data and the advanced models in flood risk management, provides hints to risk management policies and practices.

Figure 1 – Flood Susceptibility Map of the entire Italian territory, featuring six insets that provide detailed views and zoom-in perspectives of example areas

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Water shortage hazard on urban water distribution users, under current and future climate scenarios

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Abstract

The research is included in the transversal spoke TS2 and addresses the critical issue of water scarcity in urban areas and its impact on water distribution systems. The study focuses on water managers' challenges during unexpected water shortages and the standard practices adopted to mitigate these issues, such as pressure reduction, intermittent supply, and public use containment. While effective in the short term, these practices can create inequalities among users and have detrimental effects on consumers and pipe assets. The study's primary objective is to assess water shortage hazards within urban areas by defining and computing water supply equality indices and user vulnerability to shortages based on structural, topographical, and topological aspects. The methodology integrates water shortage scenarios derived from analysing water sources and supply pipes with advanced modelling of water distribution networks under continuous and intermittent supply conditions (Kumpel et al., 2016; Yepes et al., 2001).

The study highlights the prevalence of Intermittent Water Supply (IWS) in Mediterranean countries, which often results from a lack of natural resource management and network maintenance plans. IWS is characterised by cyclical filling and emptying periods, which significantly impact water quality and service reliability. The research emphasizes that users in IWS systems often resort to private reservoirs and pumps to collect water during distribution periods, leading to very high peak flows and inequity in water resource allocation (Vairavamoorthy et al., 2001; Wagner et al., 1988).

To analyse the equity of water distribution during intermittent operational conditions, the study proposes two performance indices:

1. The ratio between the water volume supplied to users in a service cycle and the user demand (EQ1).
2. The ratio between the water flow discharged to the user during a service day in intermittent and continuous distribution conditions (EQ2).

These indices help identify disadvantaged users who receive less water than their needs and those who have access to volumes exceeding their requirements. The EQ2 index is handy for analyzing network behaviour at different operational periods, such as at the start or end of distribution service after a 24-hour stop (Batish et al, 2003).

The methodology incorporates a pressure-consumption relationship to predict outflows at various nodal heads, considering the presence of private reservoirs and pumps associated with each node. This approach allows a more accurate representation of user behaviour in intermittent distribution systems (Reddy & Elango, 1989). The study employs hydraulic network solvers, such as EPANET 2, to implement the proposed algorithms and model the distribution network. The model includes private reservoirs under the roof and

pumps associated with each node, providing a comprehensive representation of intermittent distribution networks (Figure 1).

The research emphasises the importance of designing and managing water distribution systems according to their operational conditions to improve system performance and equitably deliver available water resources. It highlights that intermittent distribution networks require a fundamentally different design approach than systems delivering water 24 hours daily. Future activities that will be carried out in the application phase to Return real and synthetic case studies include:

1. Evaluating how water scarcity and intermittent service affect water consumption patterns.
2. Developing more sophisticated models to predict user behavior under various shortage scenarios.
3. Investigating the long-term impacts of intermittent supply on infrastructure and water quality.
4. Exploring innovative solutions to improve equity in water distribution during shortage events.
5. Assessing the potential impacts of climate change on urban water supply systems and developing adaptive strategies.

This research contributes to the understanding of urban water shortage hazards and provides valuable tools for water managers to identify and address inequalities in water distribution during scarcity conditions. By focusing on the equitable distribution of limited water resources, the study aims to improve the resilience and sustainability of urban water supply systems in the face of increasing water stress and climate change impacts.

Figure 1 – Numerical scheme of the water distribution supply node.

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The LanDam project: Characterization, Prediction and Emergency Management

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Abstract

The LANDAM project is included as a proposal for the Cascade Call Spoke 2 - RETURN (PNRR). The operating units coordinated by the University of Perugia consist of the Universities of Chieti-Pescara, Pavia, Sannio, Urbino, and the external unit MapSAT.

The interference between fluvial and gravitational slope dynamics processes is a complex issue. The two components, relating to rivers and landslides, respectively, have always been considered separately in the assessment of hazard and consequent risk. The scenarios that can result from these relationships are, in general, complicated and not always easily predicted and defined (Cencetti et al, 2001): they range from debris production from the slope, resulting in increased solid transport in streams, to partial or total occlusion of the riverbed, resulting in diversion of the stream within the floodplain, if present, up to complete damming of the valley, i.e., landslide dams s.s. (LSDs), involving, generally, the formation of a lake reservoir (dam lake).

The consequence of a LSD is a noticeable increase in the extent of the area exposed to the hazard resulting from the complex phenomenon of interference between the two processes, in terms of: i) submergence of the areas located upstream of the landslide barrage due to the formation of a natural reservoir; ii) possibility of overflow and rapid erosion of the landslide body, or even collapse of the barrage itself, with formation of an abnormal flood wave downstream due to the rapid emptying of the reservoir.

The project involves a series of interrelated activities, divided into phases, each with a precise work program (WP).

WP1) Characterization of the phenomenon. It consists of the census and analysis of significant LSDs case histories from the collection of data in the literature, both Italian and foreign, including older cases (e.g., Almagià, 1907 for Italy) and more recent ones (e.g., Schuster, 1986; Costa and Schuster, 1991; Pirocchi, 1991; Canuti et al, 1998; Pacino, 2002; Coico et al., 2013; Tacconi Stefanelli et al., 2015; Wu et al., 2022), implemented with data from the experiences gained by members of the research.

WP2) Prevision of the phenomenon. This phase consists of: 1) identifying active slope landslides, which make their interaction with river dynamics likely; 2) comparing the two systems (landslide-river) from the “energy”

point of view: for the landslide, it is a matter of defining, in addition to the geotechnical characteristics of the affected material, its kinetic energy; on the other hand, a landslide that mobilizes a few thousand cubic meters of material, and therefore of modest volume, but fast (debris flow) could cause the occlusion of even important streams with considerable discharge, if the morphology of the valley allows it; 3) identifying the sectors of the riverbed - alluvial plain system that can most likely be reached by materials that have been mobilized by slope instability phenomena.

This second phase of the project, to be applied to a test basin, will lead to the development of a forecasting model that succeeds in relating the variables of the two systems (geometric and morphometric on the one hand, energetic on the other), so as to predict whether or not a landslide riverbed occlusion is likely to occur.

WP3) Emergency Management represents the third phase of the project. After the prediction of the phenomenon and its characterization in geometric terms for the purpose of defining its intrinsic hazard to be eroded, overflowed or prone to collapse, a classification will be drawn up that can be useful as a “guide” for the interventions to be adopted. An aim of the project, in this sense, is precisely the drafting of intervention guidelines according to the type of landslide dam considered. The “guidelines” are intended for civil defense structures to define the methodologies to be adopted in the study of LSD phenomena and in the management of the resulting emergency. They will be accompanied by interpretive and guidance sheets and procedures for defining the state of the sites. They will enable operators to use a uniform approach that, starting with the identification of the most susceptible sites and pre-existing landslide dams, will lead to the determination of a “class” of attention according to the possible risks. In fact, this analysis will make it possible to get a preliminary assessment of hazard and associated risk with the aim of directing toward the definition of the most suitable interventions aimed at avoiding the possibility of occlusion or, in the case of occlusion in progress, at avoiding the overflow of the dam, for the mitigation of the resulting hydraulic risk.

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Quasi Convection Permitting climate simulations over Italy

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Abstract

We present the results (Struglia et al., 2025) of downscaling the most recent global climate projections to local scales for the Mediterranean and Italian regions aiming to produce high-resolution climate information for the assessment of climate change signals and related impacts, with a focus on small-scale phenomena and extreme events. Using the Weather Research and Forecasting model with the Advanced Research core WRF-ARW (Skamarock et al., 2008), we first performed a hindcast experiment driven by the ERA5 reanalysis over the period 1980-2014, aiming to evaluate the model results. Then, we dynamically downscaled the global CMIP6 MPI-ESM1-2-HR (Eyring et al., 2016; Gutjahr et al., 2019) historical and future climate simulations up to the end of the century for three different emission scenarios (SSP1-2.6, SSP2-4.5, SSP5-8.5).

For each experiment, a double nesting approach is adopted to dynamically downscale global data to the regional domain of interest, firstly over the Europe (EURO) CORDEX domain, at a spatial resolution of 15 km, and then over Italy and north-western Mediterranean, at a resolution of 5 km. The resolution of the inner domain falls in the so-called gray zone for the representation of deep convection. The gray zone spans the 4÷10 km range, where the performance of convection parameterization is critically scale dependent, scheme assumptions violations can potentially be induced and the optimal resolution at which it is preferable to turn it off needs to be assessed. Although one should be cautious in order not to run into ambiguous results due to the use of parameterizations that are not suitable for the simulation resolution, this choice enables us to cover relatively wide-size domains of regional interest and still allows for transient simulations, whether historical or projections, that are long enough to give some robustness to the statistics of extreme events.

For the representation of deep convection, we chose the cumulus parameterization proposed by Grell-Freitas (Freitas et al., 2021) which is a scale-aware parameterization. By comparing the results of the precipitation field at 15 km and 5 km (hindcast simulations) against reanalysis and observations, we show that the 5km hindcast reproduces a more realistic variability, also showing that at this resolution the cumulus scheme tend to be deactivated, turning toward an explicit representation of the deep convection. This suggests that the model at 5 km grid-scale and due to the scale-aware behavior of the Grell-Freitas scheme mimics a convection-permitting model, smoothing the transition toward the km scale.

The analysis of the scenario simulations shows that for all the scenarios and seasons there is a projected general warming along with an intensification of the hydrological cycle over most of the continental EU and mean precipitation reduction over the Mediterranean region accompanied, over the Italian Peninsula, by a strong increase in the intensity of the most extreme precipitation, particularly relevant for the SSP5-8.5 scenario during autumn.

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Climate change impact on the discharge of the Italian river network using Convection Permitting climate models

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Abstract

Projecting the impact of climate change on the Mediterranean hydrological cycle and its extremes can be challenging, notably in regions of complex topography like the Italian peninsula. For the medium ($\leq 71.000\text{km}^2$) to small basins ($\leq 30\text{km}^2$), kilometer scale resolution climate projections are needed to obtain high resolution spatio-temporal information and capture possible changes in local hydrology.

A regional climate model ensemble for the Great Alpine region was made available, at the convection permitting (CP-RCM) resolution ($< 3\text{ km}$), by the CORDEX Flagship Pilot Study on Convective phenomena at high-resolution over Europe and the Mediterranean (FPSCONV). The CETEMPS hydrological model CHyM has been used coupled off-line with the different CP-RCM ensemble members under two different configurations: using temperature and precipitation from the driving CP-RCM or directly its runoff.

The results project a 10-25% decrease in yearly mean discharge by the end of the century, with a 25-50% decrease in summer mean discharge in most of Italy. Extreme events also increase, with 25% more discharge for the 100-yr return period and 25% less discharge in the 10-yr return period discharge. Compared with hydrological ensembles at lower resolution, the main differences are found over complex topography, where, for example, the CP-RCM ensemble shows a lengthening of the hydrological year and more intense extremes. This study highlights the importance of high-resolution climate projections to assess future hydrological changes in Mediterranean regions, showing reductions in mean river discharge, intensification of extreme events and change of the characteristic of the hydrological year by 2100.

Unlocking Mediterranean Paleoclimatic Signals from the Last 20,000 Years: The PaleoMED20 Marine Sediment Cores Database

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Abstract

Paleoclimatic data from Mediterranean marine sediment cores are essential for understanding past climate dynamics in the absence of modern recording instruments. The strategic location of the Mediterranean Sea between the Atlantic Ocean and surrounding lands provides valuable insights into the interactions between oceanic and terrestrial climate systems. Its relatively small size allows for a rapid and amplified response to past climatic changes (Chiggiato et al., 2023). Reconstructing past climatic variables by analyzing biotic and geochemical indicators (proxies) preserved in marine sediment cores is crucial for forecasting future climate scenarios, especially in light of human-induced impacts such as extreme weather events, carbon emissions, and ocean acidification. Here, we present PaleoMED20, a comprehensive paleoclimatic database that uses nearly six decades of Mediterranean research and spans the last 20,000 years, from the Last Glacial Maximum to the present. The extensive PaleoMED20 dataset integrates data from over 1,500 marine sediment cores, including metadata related to oceanographic cruises and cores, as well as the presence/absence of paleoclimatic data for each core. These paleoclimatic records were compiled through a systematic literature review, incorporating data from publicly available archives such as PANGAEA, NOAA, SeaDataNet, ISMAR, and many web search engines and scientific libraries, including the Scientific Ocean Drilling Bibliographic Database and the UNESCO Digital Library. For each core, we included information on past environmental variables—organized into 11 categories—and their associated quantitative and/or qualitative proxies, categorized by geographic areas within the Mediterranean Sea.

To assess the technical quality and suitability of the database, a subset of 36 well-studied and strategically significant cores was selected to represent various Mediterranean sub-basins and water depths from both the western and eastern Mediterranean, including the Adriatic Sea. This analysis demonstrates how PaleoMED20 serves as a valuable tool for identifying key variables and proxies over the last 20,000 years, while also highlighting existing knowledge gaps.

Moreover, PaleoMED20 facilitates basin-scale comparative climate analyses, offering deeper insights into the spatial and temporal coverage of the main climatic variables across the Mediterranean Sea. Additionally, it can support the strategic planning of future oceanographic expeditions in under-explored areas and serves as a crucial resource for informing decision-making processes, guiding future research to bridge existing knowledge gaps.

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Rischio sismico, rischi legati a strutture, infrastrutture e aree urbane

AMBITO 3

High-Resolution Exposure Models for Multi-Risk Assessment in Northern Adriatic Coastal Cities

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Abstract

Effective multi-hazard disaster risk reduction and mitigation require high-resolution exposure models that accurately capture the characteristics of assets at the local scale, and incorporating hazard-specific vulnerability indicators. Likewise, high-resolution exposure models can enhance the precision and accuracy of risk and damage assessments. The spatial resolution of exposure data, often aggregated at broader scales and lower resolutions, may not align with the spatial variability and extent of certain coastal hazards (e.g., tsunamis, floods, landslides, and coastal erosion). However, multi-hazard disaster risk analysis requires the integration of exposure information developed at variable spatial resolutions and scales. Past efforts in exposure modeling were focused on assessing data independently for specific hazards. However, multiple hazards can occur simultaneously or trigger cascading effects, increasing expected impacts and risks.

In this work, we propose a methodology for developing high-resolution exposure models for population and residential buildings, to be used for multi-hazard risk assessment and mitigation at the city or municipality scale (Figure 1). To achieve this, we integrate three different geospatial datasets: national census data for buildings and population (ISTAT, 2011 & 2021), Meta population datasets (<https://dataforgood.facebook.com/dfg/>), and digital building footprints (<https://eaglefvg.regione.fvg.it/>). These datasets provide exposure-related information relevant for multi-risk analysis in coastal areas, including earthquakes, tsunamis, floods, landslides, and coastal erosion.

The development of the population exposure model integrates high-resolution Meta population data, available globally at 30m grid intervals, with the latest national population census data aggregated at the census unit level. This approach leverages the accuracy of national census data while benefiting from the high spatial resolution of global datasets. The developed population exposure layer contains information about the total population number and other demographic characteristics (e.g. age, gender, educational level, citizenship and employment status).

Also, for the development of the building exposure model, the building census data is complemented with exposure indicators extracted from digital building footprints from CTRN and OSM, which are missing in census data (e.g. replacement cost or height and plan regularity). The methodology involves extracting geometric information from footprints and incorporating it into existing exposure layers, thus achieving higher spatial resolution and enhancing the description of exposed asset characteristics. The developed residential building exposure layer contains information about building age, number of floors, construction material types, average built area, total built area, vertical regularity, and plan regularity, replacement cost, all classified following a well-defined multi-hazard taxonomy (GED4ALL Global Exposure Database for Multi-Hazard Risk Analysis; Silva et al., 2022) developed by the Global Facility for Disaster Reduction and Recovery (GFDRR). This taxonomy was complemented with a new, national-scale multi-hazard taxonomy developed

by multi-Risk sciEncE for resilientT commUnities underR a changiNgclimate (RETURN, Pittore et al., 2023) and with new indicators to account for building geometric characteristics.

Figure 1 - Flowchart illustrating the development of high-resolution population and residential buildings exposure models.

The final exposure layers are assembled at two resolutions: 100 meters and 30 meters, with information also provided at the census unit level. We discuss the development and use of these layers for multi-risk assessment and their potential combination with artificial intelligence. This method has been tested for a selected coastal area in the upper Adriatic, exposed to multiple hazards including earthquakes, tsunamis, meteorological events and coastal erosion. Given that the data used in this work has been collected in almost every nation across the globe, we can assume the current methodology can be applied to other coastal areas worldwide.

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Near-Real-Time application of NESTORE to Italian seismicity

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Abstract

NESTORE (NExt STrOng Related Earthquake) is an algorithm for the probabilistic forecasting of strong events after a major event. It has been developed and applied over the last ten years, and its public domain software (NESTOREv1.0) has been available on GitHub since 2023: <https://github.com/StefaniaGentili/NESTORE> (Gentili et al., 2023). The software calculates nine features to describe the characteristics of seismicity in increasing time intervals after the occurrence of the mainshock and analyzes them using a machine learning and statistical validation approach.

The purpose of NESTORE is to determine the probability that a main event of magnitude M_m is followed by an event of magnitude $\geq M_m - 1$ within a predefined spatio-temporal window associated with the seismic cluster. If such an event occurs, the cluster is classified as “Type A” (potentially more dangerous), otherwise as “Type B”. NESTORE provides the probability that the cluster is a type A.

NESTORE utilizes supervised machine learning, featuring a training module that computes nine seismicity features for clusters and determines corresponding thresholds to ensure that the feature values of A clusters exceed these thresholds. A testing module then evaluates the reliability of these thresholds in forecasting type A clusters. NESTORE has been successfully used in Italy, Northeast Italy, Western Slovenia, California, Greece and Japan (Brondi et al., 2024, Gentili and Di Giovambattista 2022, Anyfadi et al., 2023, Gentili et al., 2024). In Italy, the training and testing have been carried out at both national and regional level (Brondi et al., 2024). The Italian applications are being studied as part of Spoke VS3 of the RETURN project.

The regional scale is monitored directly by the OGS through its network and includes Friuli Venezia Giulia, parts of Veneto and Western Slovenia. The data comes from the OGS catalog. The training dataset comprehends events between 1977 (the year the OGS network went online) and 2010. For the national applications, the INGV catalog is used and the training dataset includes events between 1980 and 2009. At both scales, the testing datasets span from 2010 and 2020. The differences in the completeness of the two catalogs lead to different minima for the main earthquake magnitudes considered: 3.7 for the regional scale and 4 for the national scale.

In view of the overall satisfactory results achieved worldwide, a near-real-time probabilistic forecasting module (NRT module) was developed in 2021-2024. Unlike the testing module, the NRT module does not include a posteriori classification of clusters that have already occurred. Instead, it provides the probability that an ongoing cluster is of type A from 6 hours after the main event. To this end, NESTORE was retrained on the entire datasets up to 2020 to broaden its statistical basis as much as possible. The location of the clusters on which the NRT module was tested in Italy are shown in Figure 1. The success rate was 90%. Three of the clusters analysed at the national scale were also evaluated at the regional scale, together with one cluster with a smaller mainshock magnitude. At the regional scale all clusters were correctly classified.

Figure 1 – Italian sequences on which NESTORE NRT was applied in the period 2021-2024. The corresponding forecasted class is shown in the left image, and the performance of NESTORE in the right one. In one case only NESTORE misclassified the cluster class.

At regional level, the NRT was initially launched manually starting six hours after the main event. In March 2024, it was connected to the OGS seismic warning system and is now triggered automatically 6, 12 and 18 hours after main events of magnitude $ML \geq 3.7$. The automatic method was developed as part of the PNRR RETURN Spoke VS3 project with the involvement of several OGS employees and researchers, and is currently being tested. It has also been accessible to developers via a password from a dedicated website since March 2024.

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From Vulnerability Assessment to Building Risk Mitigation

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Abstract

Building envelope elements, including cornices, plasters, and roof coverings, are exposed to a wide range of natural hazards such as geophysical, meteorological, and chemical factors. These hazards can lead to the degradation or collapse of such elements, posing significant risks to both the functionality of buildings and the safety of their surroundings. The Italian Fire Brigades database highlights the relevance of this issue by documenting the frequency of safety interventions on building elements. The database analysis reveals that building envelope elements, especially plasters, roof coverings, and cornices, are the most susceptible to damage elements. Despite the critical importance of this issue, research specifically focused on the vulnerability of building envelopes and related risks to people remains limited. Studies indicate that technical elements' vulnerability is influenced by technological characteristics and physical condition. As a result, it is essential to identify technological solutions that minimize vulnerability to specific hazards and implement proactive monitoring of these elements' condition. This research aims to provide guidance on how to assess the vulnerability of building envelope elements and the resulting detrimental consequences for people and urban context.

First, the researchers have identified key natural hazards and damage mechanisms associated with building envelope elements, contributing to the development of a preliminary set of vulnerability factors. These factors represent characteristics that heighten the likelihood of damage in response to environmental stressors. Building on these findings, an assessment tool has been developed to rapidly assess the vulnerability of building envelope elements. The tool is based on a semi-quantitative approach that considers the elements' technological characteristics and their degradation conditions.

Damaged envelope elements can cause harm to people, economic losses, and obstruct escape routes during emergencies. For this reason, vulnerable envelope elements can be considered as a hazard for urban contexts. By integrating urban exposure and vulnerability analysis with the characterization of the hazard posed by damaged envelope elements it is then possible to assess the resulting risks in the urban context. This specific risk has been referred to as the Building Risk. Case studies conducted in the Bagnoli district of Naples, an area prone to low-intensity seismic events, demonstrate the applicability of this approach in identifying high-risk zones and guiding risk mitigation strategies. Ultimately, this research findings can support property managers and public authorities in making informed decisions to reduce building risk and enhance urban safety.

Figure 1 – Building envelope elements vulnerability and potential risks for people and environments

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Development of semi-analytical Fourier-domain ground motion prediction model for rapid earthquake hazard scenario calculation

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Abstract

The choice of ground motion estimates used for seismic impact scenario calculation plays a key role in determining how well post-event impact estimates can be constrained. A common solution is to use synthetic waveform simulations, which are analytically accurate but usually have the disadvantage of using limited frequencies below 1 or 2 Hz and are computationally time consuming.

As a complementary approach, we aim to produce ground shaking estimates in the Fourier domain using a semi-analytical modelling technique to describe the Fourier Amplitude Spectra (FAS) in terms of their source, propagation and site components. The resulting FAS models obtained with this methodology contain information from a wide frequency range and require less computational time than fully analytical simulations (e.g. Bora et al. 2015). It is also possible to subsequently combine these results with an additional model of the corresponding phase spectra, to obtain realistic time-domain ground motion estimates. This activity is carried out in synergy with the RETURN Task 4.4 of VP3, which is dedicated to the improvement of real-time risk mitigation measures.

To improve the accuracy of the ground motion estimates, the spectral model must be carefully calibrated in advance by inverting observational data. A test area in north-eastern Italy was selected, where many regional monitoring institutions provide good data coverage (e.g. Bragato et al. 2021). A dataset of 1191 events that occurred in the area between 2016 and 2024 was selected and processed to create the spectral database used for the calibration. The calibration process aims on the one hand, to validate the theoretical choices made for the analytical model components and, on the other hand, to estimate the empirical components to be included in the forward model for the hazard calculation, namely the regional attenuation function and the site response functions. Once these components are empirically estimated for the region, the analytical model can be improved, for example by including a more complex seismic source description. The expertise gained in the application of the whole methodology to this test area will be then available to set up its application to other areas of interest.

Additionally, the calibrated model components can be used in near-real time to estimate the apparent source spectra from the observed FAS of new data. A timely and automatized fit of the source spectra for new events would produce near-real time estimates of the source parameters, such as seismic moment and stress drop, which would become available as input for other, more complex analytical simulations.

Figure 1 – Outline of the workflow with its main phases: data collection and processing to create the inversion database, inversion of FAS data and subsequent analytical FAS model improvement, generation of ground motion estimates by combination of FAS and phase models. The possible near-real time application to obtain estimates of seismic source parameters is also illustrated.

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Assessment of technical open data for multi-scale probabilistic risk assessment of built environment

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Abstract

One of the key aspects in seismic risk assessment of urban areas are the fragility functions referred to clusters of buildings or single buildings. The fragility curves correlate a measure of intensity of the event of interest (in most of case the earthquake) with the exceedance probability (e.g., Cumulative Density Function, CDF) of a given performance threshold (i.e. Limit or Damage State) [1]. Basically, to perform fragility assessment no specific structural analyses are required, but it is necessary to associate the cluster of buildings of interest to specific typological classes characterized by a given level of fragility [2].

The crucial role in risk assessment is played by availability and consistency of technical and seismological data. Depending on data availability and its level of detail, the fragility assessment of urban areas can be performed according to a multi-scale approach, i.e. the risk assessment encompasses areas defined with Regional or sub-Regional boundaries, cluster of buildings or a single structure (or infrastructures). In the case of large- and medium-scale risk assessment, less detailed and consistent structural and seismological technical data are required. Whereas the level of detail of the data increases in the case of specific analyses on single-scale building, especially when data on the non-structural components need to be included into risk assessment [3]. Nevertheless, in a general framework of risk assessment, multi-data can be also exploited for other purposes related to risk quantification from a global standpoint: active prevention policies, rational management of emergency as wells as an empowerment and refinement of reconstruction processes to increase the resilience of the communities affected by significant earthquakes.

The ongoing research of the ATTENTIONS project focuses on *a*) recognition and analysis of existing database, whose data are useful at supporting probabilistic multi-scale risk assessment of built environment, *b*) studying the interoperability among the database into integrating the contained data *c*) analysis of data fusion potentialities (Figure 1). The main objective is to assess the availability of homogeneous databases, fundamental to achieve a homogeneous level of knowledge of the territory and to perform reliable and comparable multi-scale analyses of the existing built environment.

To this aim it has been critically analyzed the architectures of the main existing Italian databases (e.g., IRMA, CARTIS [4], ISTAT, Da.D.O. [5], National Dataset provided by DPC [6], etc.) with the aim of identifying the homogeneity level of data collected (in the different databases) and their validity in the perspective of multi-scale risk applications. It has been evaluated the versatility of data to be used for probabilistic structural safety evaluations, as well as the correctness and validity of exposure and geotechnical data. As regards a proof-of-concept is concerned, regarding the use, the exploitation and the fusion the available open data, memorandum understanding are going to be signed with the municipalities of Termoli, Oratino and Civitacampomariano (province of Campobasso).

The ongoing research activity showed that the analyzed databases contain significant and often complementary data that fit the requirements for probabilistic risk assessment primarily at a large to medium scale of analysis. They are also heterogeneous and point out the need of interoperability procedures able permit an exchange, integration of missed information for the development of more complete and consistent data collections for risk analysis.

Figure 1. Conceptual map of the ongoing research

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A Dynamic Simulation Framework for Multi-Risk Assessment in Critical Infrastructure

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The resilience of critical infrastructure is increasingly threatened by climate-driven natural hazards. Although the necessity of improving preparedness is widely recognized, no comprehensive assessment currently exists that fully addresses the climate-related vulnerabilities of critical infrastructures and their potential damages. Moreover, because such protracted exposure to extreme natural events is extraordinary compared to events experienced in the 20th century, they are not yet incorporated in infrastructure management principles and practice. For decades, risk assessments have been conducted in isolation, focusing on singular hazards without accounting for the complex interplay between different threats. Traditional approach fails to address the complexities of emerging multi-risk scenarios, where cascading failures can amplify systemic disruptions.

The current state of the art in infrastructure resilience assessment is exemplified by the Hazus methodology developed by FEMA (FEMA, 2024). However, Hazus has notable limitations, as clearly stated in its reports: it does not account for direct utility outages, cascading effects, or detailed system performance, nor does it address interdependencies between different infrastructure sectors.

This research presents an advanced, modular simulation framework that integrates domain-specific simulators with a multi-risk approach, enabling a more comprehensive analysis of cascading failures and system-wide disruptions. The structured workflow for assessing the impact of various natural hazards on critical infrastructure is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – Workflow for assessing the impact of natural hazards on critical infrastructure.

The framework builds on industry-trusted tools such as InfoWorks WS Pro for water networks and OpenTrack for railways. These simulators offer valuable insights but were originally designed for long-term planning rather than real-time emergency response. As a result, they fail to fully capture the systemic disruptions caused by climate-driven disasters. To overcome this limitation, we introduce interfacing mechanisms that dynamically inject failures and control event evolution. This integration enables a more holistic assessment of natural hazard impacts, capturing not only the physical vulnerabilities of individual components but also their operational disruptions at a systemic level. By allowing external layers to manipulate failures and cascading effects, the framework transforms static infrastructure planning models into dynamic risk assessment instruments.

Fragility curves serve as the foundation for quantifying infrastructure vulnerabilities. Derived from empirical data, numerical simulations, and expert judgment, these curves estimate the probability of failure for various components under different hazard intensities. The framework incorporates widely recognized fragility models that have been validated against past damage data. However, fragility curves can be updated or replaced with more advanced models, including AI-driven approaches and non-linear finite element methods, ensuring continuous improvement in predictive capabilities.

Data availability remains a persistent challenge in risk modeling, as missing, outdated, or inconsistent data can significantly affect simulation accuracy. However, this research demonstrates that even partial datasets can provide meaningful insights. Rather than waiting for perfect data, domain-specific simulations extract valuable intelligence from existing infrastructure records, fragility curves, and historical failure data, which in turn can encourage further data collection efforts. Initiatives such as SINFI (Italy's Federated National Information System of Infrastructures) highlight the growing movement toward standardized and accessible infrastructure data, which could greatly enhance resilience modeling in the near future.

The modular architecture of the framework ensures that improvements—whether through enhanced fragility curves, real-time monitoring, machine learning-driven failure predictions, more refined models of natural hazards, or increased data availability on infrastructure—can be seamlessly integrated. This adaptability prevents obsolescence and allows the framework to evolve alongside advancements in resilience modeling. Furthermore, the ability to simulate the effects of a wide range of hazards, from earthquakes and flooding to drought-induced infrastructure stress, makes it a highly versatile tool for diverse environmental and operational conditions.

The implementation of this simulation environment has the potential to significantly enhance resilience planning by:

- Evaluating infrastructure responses to varying hazard intensities and combinations.
- Accounting for cascading failures triggered by successive disasters (e.g., an earthquake causing pipe ruptures, followed by flooding that exacerbates contamination risks).
- Assessing the effectiveness of mitigation strategies in a virtual environment before real-world implementation.

This document presents a rethinking of how infrastructure resilience can be modeled and measured, with a structured, trusted methodology for quantifying risk, ensuring that investments are directed toward the most critical areas.

In the final phase of the RETURN project, this simulation environment will be applied to assess how resilience can be actively managed, offering a practical tool for infrastructure operators to navigate evolving risk landscapes.

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Finite element model updating based on ambient vibration tests for damage detection in Gerber half-joint bridges

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Abstract

The integrity and durability of civil engineering structures, particularly bridges, are paramount to ensure public safety and maintaining resilient transportation networks. Over time, these structures experience deterioration due to environmental factors, weathering, and increased loading, all of which can lead to damage that compromises structural performance and safety. In this context, Ambient Vibration Testing (AVT) provides a powerful means of refining numerical models, thereby enabling a more accurate understanding of structural behavior (Ewins, 1986). A fundamental motivation for using Finite Element Model Updating (FEMU) based on AVT lies in its ability to detect and quantify damage (Friswell et al., 1995). Such damage typically manifests through variations in dynamic properties—namely shifts in natural frequencies and alterations in mode shapes (Salawu, 1997). By analyzing these changes, FEMU allows engineers to: (i) localize damaged zones by comparing updated model characteristics to baseline conditions, (ii) quantify the extent of damage via calibrated stiffness parameters that mirror observed dynamic deviations, and (iii) monitor damage progression over time to facilitate predictive maintenance and extend the structure's service life (Huang et al., 2008).

This study aims to develop and implement damage detection strategies by exploiting FEMU and AVT for a set of eight Gerber half-joint prestressed reinforced concrete (PRC) bridges constructed in the 1970s (Figure 1). Despite sharing similar geometrical and structural layouts, these bridges exhibit varying levels of deterioration. The methodological approach encompasses two main phases: (a) the acquisition of modal parameters (e.g., natural frequencies, mode shapes) through dynamic testing, and (b) the application of damage detection techniques to identify, localize, and quantify structural damage. Complementary investigations included material characterization, geometric surveys, and Level 1 visual inspections (LV1) in accordance with Italian Bridges Guidelines (Consiglio Superiore dei lavori Pubblici, 2020).

The Finite Element (FE) models were calibrated using a targeted updating strategy to improve the correlation between numerical predictions and experimental results while avoiding overfitting. This approach allowed the identification and quantification of structural damage by capturing variations in stiffness. The analysis revealed significant reductions in stiffness, particularly in the half-joints, confirming the presence of localized deterioration and aligning with observations from visual inspections. The integration of model updating with experimental data proved effective in distinguishing different levels of damage severity, providing a more refined assessment of structural conditions.

These findings reinforce the reliability of the proposed methodology for structural health monitoring, supporting data-driven maintenance decisions and optimizing intervention strategies. By offering a comprehensive evaluation framework, this study contributes to the long-term preservation of bridge infrastructure.

This research is conducted within the framework of Spoke 6—TS2 “Multi Risk Resilience of Critical Infrastructures”, Task 4.4—“Advanced Strategies for Infrastructure Modelling and Vulnerability Assessment”, with a specific focus on DV 4.4.b—“Identification and Model Updating of Critical Infrastructure Components”.

Figure 1 – View of the eight Gerber half-joint PCR bridges.

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NESTORE application to Japan seismicity

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Abstract

In this study, the advanced machine learning algorithm NESTORE (Next STrOng Related Earthquake) was applied to the Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA) catalog from 1973 to 2024 to forecast strong aftershocks in ongoing earthquake sequences (Gentili et al., 2025). NESTORE calculates the probability that aftershocks will reach or exceed the magnitude of the mainshock minus one, classifying clusters as type A or type B based on a probability threshold of 0.5. The algorithm has been successfully tested in Italy, western Slovenia, Greece, and California (Brondi et al, 2024, Anyfadi et al, 2023, Gentili and Di Giovambattista, 2022) and a free MATLAB version (NESTOREv1.0) is available on GitHub at the address <https://github.com/StefaniaGentili/NESTORE> (Gentili et al., 2023).

Japan is characterized by a high level of seismicity and the JMA provides a very high-quality catalog to work with. However, the high and complex seismic activity in Japan required the development of additional algorithms to complement NESTORE. A hybrid method for cluster identification was introduced, combining ETAS-based stochastic declustering with deterministic graph-based selection, replacing the window-based approach used in NESTOREv1.0. The analysis was performed as part of Spoke VS3 of the RETURN project. We trained NESTORE on a set of 50 seismic clusters (7 type A and 43 type B clusters) that occurred from 1973 to 2004 and tested it on 31 clusters (4 type A and 27 type B) from 2005 to 2023 (Fig. 1). NESTORE is a supervised algorithm: the class of the clusters is used for the training to define the parameters. During the testing, the classifications are compared with the actual class of the clusters. Due to the large class imbalance between type A and type B clusters, we have developed a new algorithm called REPENESE (RElevant features, class imbalance PERcentage, NEighbour detection, SElection) to detect outliers, addressing the imbalance between type A and type B clusters.

Figure 1 – NESTOREv1.0 dataset for Japan: (left) training set after outliers removal and (middle) test set. For each cluster, the position of the o-mainshock is shown. (right) Results of the forecasting. All the plots refer to forecasting period $T_i=6h$.

The method correctly forecasted 75% of type A clusters and 96% of type B clusters, achieving an overall accuracy of 94% and a precision of 0.75 six hours after the mainshock. The 2011 Tōhoku cluster was also correctly classified. In addition, we successfully tested the Near Real Time (NRT) module of NESTORE after the M6.6 Shikoku earthquake on April 17, 2024. NESTORE correctly identified the following sequence as a type B cluster, 6 hours after the mainshock. The results highlight the potential of NESTORE algorithm in forecasting strong aftershocks in regions with high seismicity and class imbalance. The high recall, precision, and accuracy values achieved in the test phase demonstrate the effectiveness of this approach in improving aftershock forecasting and seismic risk assessment.

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Probabilistic Risk Assessment of isolated areas due to forest fire events

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Abstract

Probabilistic risk assessment (PRA) provides a comprehensive view of potential hazards by considering both high-impact rare events and frequent lower-impact ones. It incorporates all risk components—hazard, exposure, and vulnerability—while accounting for uncertainties, including those arising from climate change. PRA is particularly useful for evaluating unprecedented events and worst-case scenarios, aiding in preparedness and decision-making. This study aims to assess the risk of isolated areas due to forest fires using a probabilistic approach: while isolation due to natural events has been studied through classical network analysis, few studies have examined it probabilistically.

To assess risk probabilistically in a scientifically robust manner, a set of scenarios that are collectively exhaustive and mutually exclusive have to be generated. The scenario generation process consists of two main components:

- Event Definition & Selection – Identifying meteorological conditions (e.g., wind speed and humidity) that could trigger wildfires. The region is divided into homogeneous hazard areas (HHAs) to optimize risk calculation.
- Probabilistic Event Generation – Using a multivariate statistical approach to simulate both observed and hypothetical wildfire events while preserving spatial correlations and statistical properties.

This probabilistic approach, which applies Gaussian transformations to enhance correlation modeling, enables the simulation of unprecedented wildfire events. The result is an event catalogue covering thousands of years of potential wildfire conditions. To assess hazard, the event catalogue is merged with a wildfire hazard map, which combines a susceptibility map (indicating fire-prone areas) with fuel type data (derived from land cover maps). A contingency matrix classifies wildfire hazard levels from very low to extreme.

Figure 1 – example of wildfire hazard map (Fiorucci et al., 2024)

Once climate conditions indicate a potential fire, vulnerability curves are used to estimate the impact on exposed assets, accounting for different structural and physical characteristics. Direct losses are calculated for each event, allowing for the assessment of standard risk metrics such as Average Annual Loss (AAL) and Probable Maximum Loss (PML).

The study goes beyond direct impacts on infrastructure to analyze the effects on road network functionality. Road networks are a critical component of Critical Infrastructure (CI), essential for the transport of goods, people, and services. For isolated locations, it is crucial to evaluate the network's ability to maintain connectivity and functionality under specific hazardous events. The process involves addressing the following sub-problems:

- Identification of potentially isolated locations, based on the road network analysis.
- Identification of centroids representative of service providing locations
- Identification of optimal paths between pairs of origin and destination nodes
- Assessing the Impact of Road Segment Loss on Network Connectivity and Functionality
- Inclusion in the probabilistic risk assessment process

The analysis focuses on the subset of the network composed of the K-shortest paths for each origin-destination pair. Disruptions to these paths because of forest fire events are evaluated to measure their direct and indirect effects on network performance.

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Stability of underground caves subjected to seismic actions: from geophysical investigations to analytical tools

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Abstract

In the Mediterranean areas, many countries have numerous natural and anthropic underground caves, used for different purposes over time (water storage, shelters, archeological sites, secret pathways). In Italy, these cavities are common in many cities and are part of the historical and artistic heritage (de Silva et al., 2024; Faraone et al., 2023). However, the caves represent a potential geotechnical hazard for civil construction and urban development, especially in historic centers and seismically active areas.

The main source of risk is due to two different phenomena: i) the stress induced by the earthquake can exceed the resistance of the ground surrounding the cave, causing its instability; ii) the cave alters the seismic wave in terms of frequency, amplitude and duration, influencing the ground motion near structures and infrastructures (Fabozzi et al., 2024).

For this reason, the scientific community is focusing on the presence of caves with specific attention to urbanized areas; in this regards, several geological and geomorphological studies as well as engineering-geological analyses have been performed so far, aiming at a higher comprehension of the ground instabilities related to rock mass failures in correspondence of caves.

In this study, several caves have been examined, both in Italy, such as Battifratta Cave (RI) and in the Maltese Archipelago, as Ghar il-Kbir Cave, Calypso Cave, Tal-Mixta Cave and Ghar il-Latnija Cave, as well.

Above all, in the Maltese Archipelago, many of these caves affected by karst phenomena have been evolved into sinkholes, and for this purpose, a database on QGis platform has been created, aiming at the reconstruction of a highly fragmented knowledge to provide more detailed information and description about sinkholes in the Maltese Archipelago. This work was possible starting from previous studies, with the integration of what was already on the Geological Map of the Maltese Islands (1993).

Moreover, an attribute table has been associated with each mapped sinkhole, containing all recorded parameters. These have been divided into categories: (i) Geological parameters; (ii) Geometric parameters; (iii) Geographical parameters. Moreover, new parameters have been added to provide a more comprehensive description of sinkholes.

The final goal is to use this inventory as a basis for statical analysis aimed at identifying a prevalent distribution cluster of these phenomena based on the considered parameters.

Furthermore, a combination of multi-physics techniques, such as passive seismic surveys and numerical modeling, has been conducted to study the dynamic behaviour of caves by identifying their resonance modes. Data acquisition involves multiple surveys of seismic ambient noise measurements at selected points, in array configuration, using a compact ultra-low power digital seismometer.

In particular, the results obtained for the Ghar il-Latnija Cave (Grechi et al., 2024) have been reported. Subsequently, photogrammetric surveys and drone flight have been combined to obtain a detailed 3D model

of these structures, useful for defining their geometry and their evolution in time and space, as in the case of Ghar il-Latnija Cave.

For this specific site, a qualitative retro-deformation analysis was carried out to reconstruct, through arbitrary surfaces, the original roof of the cavity, considering the actual slopes of the area and the volumetry of the deposits present inside the cave itself.

The same techniques experienced in the Maltese archipelago will be applied to Italian case studies, as tool for performing back-analyses of cave evolutions in order to calibrate engineering-geological models reliable to perform forward analyses.

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Application of Loss-Based Earthquake Engineering in design process

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Abstract

Eurocode 8 allows force-based seismic design and safety assessment of buildings as if they were indefinitely linearly elastic. However, to implicitly account for their inelastic deformation capacity, Eurocode 8 allows the reduction of the design values of seismic forces through the seismic behavior factor. In turn dissipative members are designed to undergo plastic deformation dissipating energy. This design procedure should consider the damage for those dissipative members and then their impact on the expected annual loss due to their damage, replacement and/or retrofitting. The paper provides a procedure to confirm a structure, designed according to the capacity design approach, to be economically competitive with respect to a low- dissipative building, designed to remain in elastic field.

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A Dynamic Traffic Flow Simulation Framework for Abnormal Condition Assessments

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Macroscopic traffic flow models play a crucial role in traffic surveillance and the planning of road networks, as they provide a reliable representation of traffic conditions. Typically, in planning applications, these models are applied under the assumption of steady-state conditions. However, the occurrence of abnormal events, including extreme weather, natural disasters, road maintenance, or the failure of a bridge or network segment, can significantly impact both the supply and demand within the network. Consequently, these factors may alter the operational performance of the system from what is typically observed under normal conditions. The impact of unusual events on a network is largely determined by its resilience, essentially, the network's ability to maintain an adequate level of functionality under uncertain conditions, which can be quantified by a specific probability of occurrence. To effectively evaluate network reliability, it is crucial to focus on several aspects of network functionality. These include network connectivity, travel times between origins and destinations, the accessibility of different zones, and network capacity.

Ensuring network connectivity is a fundamental requirement for guaranteeing the availability of at least one route between traffic zones, making it a critical component of any reliability analysis. Additionally, travel times significantly influence the quality of these connections and thus determine the accessibility level for both individual origin-destination pairs and the broader area. The concept of "reliability of network capacity" was introduced by Chen et al. (1999) and is defined as the probability that the network's capacity will meet a specified demand level with a predetermined level of service. Consequently, it is crucial not only to maintain network connectivity but also to ensure that the necessary capacity is available to meet demand requirements.

Typically, statistical distributions of link performance are essential for examining how variations in link performance affect overall network performance. However, deriving these distributions can be challenging due to data limitations. In such scenarios, we recommend adopting a machine learning-based strategy that associates zones and links with similar features with respect to accessibility conditions. This approach leverages characteristic similarities and positioning to estimate link performance, providing a viable alternative when conventional data is scarce. The discussion emphasizes the necessity for a traffic model that accurately reflects traffic conditions across both space and time. It must adapt to scenarios involving reduced capacity from various events, effectively evaluate alternatives during network failures, and provide precise estimates of network resilience when other infrastructures are compromised.

To address this need we propose a dynamic traffic assignment and simulation model that incorporates an internal origin-destination (OD) estimation procedure, enabling it to adjust demand and supply parameters according to specific hazard scenarios, ensuring essential elements for assessing the system's reliability and must be consistently met by any planning strategy. The methodology begins by adapting the OD and network connectivity to reflect the defined scenario. Thus, it captures the user optimal time dependent paths chosen by the user and proceeds with traffic simulation that adheres to criteria for minimum connectivity and capacity reliability. The simulation outcomes are assessed using weighted reliability indicators for each

network zone. The effectiveness of the model's output is assessed based on the satisfaction of the defined indicators. The structured workflow for assessing the impact of abnormal events on road infrastructure is shown in Figure 1.

This simulation model can be integrated with other simulation models targeting different infrastructures to create a comprehensive system for evaluating transportation resilience against natural disasters. Additionally, it can be employed to preemptively address disaster prevention and planned maintenance. Optimization of the model is achieved by comparing the alternatives generated by the model with predetermined desired scenarios for network connectivity and capacity. This approach ensures that the model not only predicts and reacts to changes effectively but also aligns closely with strategic objectives for network functionality and reliability.

Figure 1 – Workflow for assessing the impact of natural hazards on critical infrastructure.

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From the idea to the PoC: the construction of the first coastal RETURNVILLE

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Abstract

Virtual reality applied to urban systems in multi-hazard conditions constitute an effective driver for technology transfer and knowledge sharing due to the implementation of modeling and simulations of urban settlements and the definition of measures for risk mitigation and adaptation of exposed assets.

In the framework of the Spoke TS1-Urban and Metropolitan Settlements activities, the testing of a digital model referred to RETURNVILLE has been set to simulate multi-risk processes in representative parts of urban and metropolitan settlements in the Italian context. Relying on the visualization of what-if scenarios, the objective is to assess the impacts of alternative Disaster Risk Management (DRM) and Climate Change Adaptation (CCA) strategies and solutions.

The configuration of RETURNVILLE stems from Aldo Rossi's model of the analogous city, a collage presented at the 1976 Venice Architecture Biennale that inquired into the significance of urban elements and parts in the type-morphological construction of an imagined territory, to be intended as the representation of memory and experience.

The first experimentation on a coastal RETURNVILLE has been carried out by assembling fragments of cities, meant to be representative of different type-morphological layouts. The aim is to convey, although its virtual dimension, the complexity of Italian urban systems in relation to multi-hazard conditions. In this first experimentation, reference was made to a Tyrrhenian orientation of the city; urban parts with an average of 20,000 inhabitants has been selected and isolated in several cities of the Italian context, whilst retaining their original orientation.

Each fragment was selected as representative of recognizable urban parts in terms of urban fabric (historic center, nineteenth-century fabric, scattered settlement, industrial area), and, to some extent, due to specific evolutionary or functional phases of the cities. Accordingly, the cities of Naples, Taranto, Trapani, Genoa, Livorno, Trieste and Torre del Greco were considered. Each of the urban parts considered is known to be originally located in a context characterized by the presence of specific environmental, natural and anthropogenic hazards. The assemblage of the various urban parts provides a composite settlement of about 100,000 inhabitants, capable of representing the complexity and reporting the co-presence of potential risks

derived from real conditions in the urban and metropolitan contexts of reference. Similarly, natural, infrastructural and facilities systems extracted from existing coastal cities were also assembled in the same spatial context where the built-up fabric fragments are located.

Therefore, the paper presents the methodological approach adopted to set up the experimentation of the virtual city RETURNVILLE, which is being further implemented also in relation to other cities typologies. Moreover, it presents the founding principles that constitute the assemble process, conceived to be reportable for other types of cities in order to obtain simulations in urban and metropolitan settings of impacts arising from composite or cascading risks and thus possible mitigation and adaptation strategies.

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SMEs in Tourism: Turning Seismic Risks into Opportunities Through Digitalization

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Abstract

The tourism sector, a pillar of the global economy, represents a fundamental component for economic growth, job creation, and social development in many regions (Zhang et al., 2021). However, its dependence on natural resources and infrastructure renders it particularly vulnerable to adverse natural events, including earthquakes (Xiao et al., 2022). Seismic risk, defined as the probability of negative consequences or expected losses arising from seismic events and the vulnerability of affected areas (Jena et al., 2020), poses a significant challenge for tourist destinations located in seismically active zones. The impacts include job losses, decreased tourist flows, and damage to the destination's reputation (Akamavi et al., 2023). Furthermore, tourists' perceptions of risk play a crucial role in their travel decisions, directly influencing the competitiveness of destinations (Akamavi et al., 2023). In this context, the adoption of digital technologies offers significant opportunities to address these challenges by facilitating the development of innovative strategies aimed at enhancing the resilience of tourist destinations. Advanced technologies such as sensor-based early warning systems and GIS models for risk assessment enable the identification of the most vulnerable areas and improve preparedness and response capabilities to seismic events (Lagap & Ghaffarian, 2024). The process of digitalization not only improves risk management but also revolutionizes the tourism sector by providing tools to strengthen the competitiveness of SMEs. Technologies such as data analytics and artificial intelligence enable SMEs to better understand customer preferences and adapt their offerings to meet the needs of an ever-evolving market, thus increasing tourist satisfaction and loyalty. The use of social media and unified digital platforms not only amplifies destination visibility but also contributes to gathering valuable feedback for optimizing services (Di Virgilio, 2021). For instance, AI-powered Chatbots are technologies that offer interactive 24/7 client assistance by answering frequent guest questions, giving customized suggestion, proposal, and help, and even managing various booking requests. The adoption of this tool can optimize customer service and decrease response times, thus empowering client experience, loyalty, and satisfaction.

This study aims to explore the intersection between digitalization, seismic risk, and tourism management, focusing on the question: how can digitalization contribute to mitigating the effects of seismic risk on tourism and promoting the resilience of tourist destinations? An innovative aspect of this study is the proposal for a digital tourism portal designed to provide real-time updates on post-earthquake conditions while supporting local SMEs in economic development. This tool would not only improve communication with tourists by reassuring them during emergencies but also collect useful data to identify new trends and develop targeted marketing strategies that ensure sustainable growth for the tourism sector. In conclusion, digitalization represents a strategic lever for addressing the challenges posed by seismic risk in the tourism sector. By integrating advanced technologies into risk management strategies, it is possible to reduce the vulnerability of tourist destinations, enhance emergency preparedness, and promote sustainable development. This research will provide a solid foundation for formulating innovative policies that make tourism safer, more resilient, and future oriented.

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Out-of-plane seismic behavior of infill panels: the experimental campaign

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Abstract

The vulnerability of old infill walls, constructed between the 1960s and 1980s and not designed to provide high thermal or mechanical performances, is the focus of this research activity which has been developed along two different lines. The first one involved numerical analyses of the most common infill walls in the Neapolitan area, where seismic activity may be linked to volcanic phenomena and buildings serve also as essential shelters. The second one focused on designing dynamic tests on panels, to validate numerical models. These analyses aimed to derive reliable variables for comprehensively modeling the infill walls, considering different calculation approaches and varying geometrical and mechanical parameters.

As the bricks strength varies with the load direction, showing a resistance ratio of approximately 3, numerical simulations with a Drucker-Prager failure criterion were calibrated to match manufacturer-declared failure loads when applied to full-wall modeling.

The mortar was modeled with a dual approach: an elastic-plastic model with a Drucker-Prager failure criterion and a concrete-damaged plasticity model implemented in Midas Gen® (Lubliner et al. 1989). The first approach considers variable cohesion and failure at the brick-mortar interface but does not account for stress redistribution after yielding. The second approach incorporates different compressive and tensile strengths, damage evolution, and cyclic loading effects.

Three restraint conditions between the masonry panel and the surrounding frame were analyzed: (a) fully supported, (b) separated by lateral and upper gaps, and (c) separated by an upper gap. (Di Domenico et al 2020)

To validate the above numerical findings, experimental tests were designed to verify the behavior of a specimen made up of an infilled Reinforced Concrete (R.C.) frame. Such full-scale single-story frame has infill walls with single-leaf hollow clay bricks and it is designed to withstand multiple tests without damaging. Two sides of the single-story frame will be fully infilled, while the remaining two will have a central opening for a more comprehensive analysis. In Figure 1 a 3D view of a typical model of the shaking table tests specimen is shown.

A 4x4 m six-degree-of-freedom shaking table will apply a sequence of seismic loads, starting with low-intensity input to evaluate the dynamic behavior of the specimen before gradually increasing the load to assess damage. The tests will be conducted under in-plane and out-of-plane loading.

A 3D motion optical system will monitor the behavior of infill panels until failure. (De Canio et al. 2016)

Moreover, to provide information on the R.C. structure, a quick and easy on-the-field non-destructive testing (NDT) methodology involving ultrasonic and sonic wave propagation (Polimeno et al. 2018) will be performed

before and after the seismic tests on order to investigate the modifications induced by the seismic load on RC buildings.

After damage, the infill walls will be strengthened using lightweight, easily applied reinforcement systems suitable for post-disaster interventions.

In addition, thermo-hygrometric measures will be carried out with the aim to evaluate the infill wall performances, with and without the reinforcement systems, before and after the application of the seismic loads, by using thermal-camera and humidity sensors.

In this way, the experimental campaign will be aimed not only at investigating the behavior of the infill walls, including their thermo-hygrometric performances, under selected seismic events but also at monitoring any variation of the mechanical characteristics of r.c. members.

Figure 1 – 3D View of a typical model of the shaking table tests specimen

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Impact of Structural Defects on the Performance of Masonry Arch Bridges: A Probabilistic Framework for Large-Scale Assessment

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Abstract

Masonry arch bridges constitute a significant portion of the European transport infrastructure. It is estimated that approximately 40% of the existing railway bridges in Europe are masonry arches, with 85% of them being single-span structures (Bowen L. et al., 2024). The majority of these bridges are still in service on both secondary and main railway lines, although they are no longer utilized for high-speed rail networks (De Santis S. et al., 2014). Given their long service life, these structures are increasingly subject to degradation due to environmental exposure, material aging, and cyclic loading. Typical defects include mortar joint erosion, block detachment, and surface exfoliation, all of which can adversely affect the structural integrity and load-bearing capacity of the bridge. The assessment of these aging structures is therefore essential for ensuring safety and optimizing maintenance strategies. However, given the vast number of masonry arch bridges still in service, a simplified methodology capable of efficiently evaluating their structural capacity while incorporating deterioration effects is required for large-scale assessments.

This study proposes a probabilistic framework for assessing the structural response of masonry arch bridges, explicitly accounting for defects commonly observed during visual inspections of existing structures. These defects are modelled on the surfaces of the bridge that are in direct contact with the surrounding environment. The primary defects considered in this study include mortar joint loss, block detachment, and surface exfoliation, which are among the most frequently documented forms of damage in masonry bridges. It is crucial to take these defects into account as they not only reduce the geometric section of the masonry but also decrease the surfaces through which internal stresses are transferred, ultimately reducing the structure's load-bearing capacity. All these defects are geometric in nature and are modelled as such to accurately capture their effect on the bridge's performance. A limit analysis approach is used for these studies, allowing for an efficient evaluation of the structural behaviour under different damage scenarios (Gilbert M., 1993; Zampieri et al., 2016). A Monte Carlo simulation approach is then employed to introduce probabilistic variations in defect severity, enabling the evaluation of multiple deterioration scenarios (Cavalagli et al., 2017). The methodology also incorporates standard traffic loads and representative bridge geometries to assess the effect of different damage levels on the collapse load multiplier. By adopting this approach, it becomes possible to determine the statistical distribution of structural capacity reduction and identify the most critical factors influencing the performance of masonry arch bridges.

Figure 1 illustrates the loss of load-bearing capacity, expressed as the collapse multiplier α calculated through limit analysis, for three distinct types of defects. This analysis was conducted for two case studies of masonry bridges, with net spans of 6 m and 16 m, respectively. As expected, the results demonstrate that higher defect intensities lead to more significant reductions in load-bearing capacity, with smaller-span bridges showing greater sensitivity to damage. Furthermore, the findings highlight that defects such as the loss or breakage of bricks result in the most significant reduction in load-bearing capacity, as they directly reduce the effective cross-sectional area and overall structural integrity. However, all three types of defects—loss of mortar, brick

detachment, and surface exfoliation—affect the collapse mechanism, leading to a decrease in the load-bearing capacity of the structure. Future work will focus on extending the probabilistic model to account for the interaction of multiple defect types and evaluate their combined effects on structural stability. Additional refinements will consider variations in material properties and arch geometries to enhance the applicability of the methodology. The proposed approach provides an effective tool for large-scale assessment of masonry arch bridges, aiding in the development of optimized maintenance and conservation strategies for aging infrastructure.

Figure 1 - Representation of the loss of load-bearing capacity (α) as a function of four defect intensity levels for (a) brick loss, (b) surface exfoliation, and (c) mortar joint material loss.

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Earthquake-tsunami combined effect on bridges: fragility curves and mitigation strategies

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Abstract

Considering their service life, coastal infrastructures may be affected by various natural combined actions. In this context, earthquakes triggering near-field tsunamis are events with severe consequences that make meaningful specific vulnerability assessments. Recently, some attention has been devoted to bridges under sequential earthquake-tsunami loads. Numerous studies have been focused on developing valuable methodologies to estimate the probability of damage and consequently to design appropriate strategies to mitigate potential losses. Nevertheless, an efficient predictive framework able to generate damage probability models appropriate for different structural types and tsunami scenarios, which simultaneously accounts for the potential impact of previous earthquake damage, is still missing.

FEMA proposed a methodology for combining damage-state probabilities in earthquake tsunami sequential events, but earthquake and tsunami damage states are considered statistically independent. Park et al. (2012) improved this method assuming the earthquake-damaged state of a structure as an initial condition for analyzing the impact of the tsunami, adopting a too schematic model. Attary et al. (2019) developed fragility curves for steel frame structures using successive nonlinear analyses under earthquake-tsunami sequential events. Petrone et al. (2020) developed and compared fragility functions for a RC frame structure under tsunami only and earthquake-tsunami in sequence. Fragility analysis for bridges under earthquake-tsunami sequential events is generally limited.

Additionally, mitigation strategies, available in the literature and mostly related to reducing the seismic vulnerability of structures, rarely of infrastructures, emphasize the importance of energy dissipation devices, but reveal a consistent gap in effectively addressing the limitations of traditional methods applied to bridges.

Fluid viscous dampers are effective in dissipating energy, but present challenges in design because of the dependence of the damping forces on the frequency content of the external input more than the intensity of the input itself. Friction dampers, representing a more cost-effective solution than FVDs, have the disadvantage of exerting an initial friction higher than that exerted during the movement.

On this background, an advanced tool that could be useful for the mitigation of the impact of successive earthquake-tsunami events on the societies and economies of high-risk coastal regions has been here proposed. Analytical fragility curves are generated adopting a procedure based on Monte Carlo simulations: first a random generation of the involved parameters characterizing bridges and loads, then time-history dynamic analyses for seismic actions followed by push-over analyses for tsunami loading are carried out.

In detail, the proposed approach, illustrated in Fig. 1, consists in five simple key steps: random parameters for the definition of the geometry are generated, each so-modeled single structure first goes through a gravity load analysis and, right after, is subjected to a seismic dynamic action via a non-linear time history analysis; depending on the structural condition, collapsed or not, the procedure respectively starts again, analyzing a new model, or proceeds to a tsunami push-over analysis on the damaged model, to evaluate its response under post-shock tsunami loading; finally, once the model collapses due to tsunami action, the corresponding

inundation depth value (h) is stored. Following the procedure described in Oddo et al. (2024), it is eventually possible to obtain analytical fragility lognormal functions for a fixed peak ground acceleration.

Figure 1 - Framework for constructing multi-hazard (earthquake-tsunami) fragility curves

Once the assessment of vulnerability is performed, the improvement of each single bridge is proposed basing on a novel solution consisting in a special Friction Dampers (VFD), in which the friction is variable due to the special geometry. Differently from a classic friction damper, the internal and external plates surfaces are inclined to each other by a certain angle, so that the sliding plate is forced to a convex funnel-shaped channel and the greater the relative displacement of the components of the device is (in connection to the lateral seismic response) the greater the friction force becomes, because of the increasing of compression on the sliding plate itself.

This means that the proposed device provides an energy dissipation consistent with earthquake intensity and governed by two components: the first one, pure friction, is constant, while the second component is a linear law that increases the dissipative force as the displacement increases and vice versa until it reaches zero for zero relative displacement.

This approach allows a reduction of damage due to earthquakes and, consequently, a higher capacity at the impact of the following tsunami wave.

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Building classification in a GIS environment and seismic impact assessment in the Centro-Ovest district of Genoa

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Abstract

This study presents a GIS-based approach for building classification and seismic impact assessment in the Centro-Ovest district of Genoa. The methodology involves classifying buildings based on key vulnerability parameters, including construction material (masonry, reinforced concrete, or mixed), period of construction, and number of floors. Each building is assigned a fragility curve using a heuristic-macroseismic model (Lagomarsino S. et al. 2021) calibrated with observed damages from past Italian earthquakes, such as L'Aquila (2009) and Irpinia (1980). Exposure parameters, including built area, number of residents, and family units, are incorporated to estimate seismic consequences at both the individual building and census section levels.

The impact assessment evaluates structural damage probabilities, including immediate inaccessibility, prolonged unavailability due to necessary interventions, and potential collapse. Additionally, consequences for the population are quantified, estimating the number of displaced individuals (both immediately and in the long term), homeless households, severe injuries, and fatalities. Economic losses are calculated by associating repair costs with different levels of structural damage, considering the total built area and property values.

A crucial component of this study is the data collection process, which integrates multiple sources with different levels of data processing. Data availability and extraction complexity were categorized as follows: Low – readily available and requiring minimal processing, such as ISTAT census data and geoportal information, Medium – partially available but requiring manual extraction, including remote surveys, cartographic material, and building manuals, and High – requiring expert judgment and manual acquisition, such as on-site surveys and stakeholder interviews. By combining these diverse datasets, the study ensures a robust classification of buildings and a reliable seismic risk evaluation.

The aggregated data is analyzed within a GIS environment to visualize the spatial distribution of expected damage and risk indicators. This approach enables the identification of high-risk areas and the relative impact of different building typologies. Maps can be generated to display both absolute and normalized values, offering insights into seismic vulnerability, exposure, and population density. The integration of high-detail manual inputs with large-scale, readily available data enhances the accuracy and reliability of the assessment, supporting informed decision-making for risk mitigation and urban planning.

Figure 1 – Representation of building density at the census tract scale in the Centro-Ovest district.

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Classifying and assessing good practices for urban and metropolitan risk management: a methodological and evaluation framework

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Abstract

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A multi-level framework to the assessment of the robustness and resilience of critical infrastructures

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Abstract

The built environment is often endangered by man-made or natural hazards (avalanches, floods, earthquakes, and so on), which can cause remarkable human and economic losses, including severe damage to buildings and critical infrastructures. The latter are supposed to withstand such unexpected scenarios – denoted in the literature as Low Probability High Consequences (LPHC) events – which are not typically accounted for in the ordinary design stage of the construction. Under these circumstances, the response of such systems should be analyzed both at the structural level, by considering the potential damage due to the overload, and at the network level, considering the potential global disruption of the infrastructure.

During the last decades, several research studies have been conducted in this field (Kiakojoury et al., 2020). Numerous metrics have been proposed to quantify structural robustness, which include stiffness-, damage-, or energy-based measures (Starossek and Haberland, 2011), and considerations on the complexity of the structural system (De Biagi and Chiaia, 2013). Even though some of these approaches have made their own way in design code or recommendations, also implemented in Italy (CNR-DT 214/2018), a common agreement regarding a unified metric has not been reached yet.

In this work, a multi-level framework is proposed, in which the robustness and resilience of infrastructures is assessed. The approach, even though its general validity, is discussed with reference to bridge structures, due to their key-role in transportation and mobility sectors (De Biagi et al., 2022).

By the structural point of view, bridges can be intended as structures made of multiple components, arranged in such a way that external loads can be effectively transferred from the application point to the ground, by means of the foundation system. In this sense, the approach is based on a sort of hierarchy in load transfer across the bridge, whereby the structural robustness assessment is the cross-result of two distinct contributions: the robustness of each component of the bridge and that associated to the static structural scheme of the bridge.

Regarding the first contribution, i.e., at the component level, different examples can be done. Let us consider the case of a prestressed beam, in which different tendons are present at the cross-section level. In this case, the robustness of the component is provided by the redundancy in the number of tendons, which allow load redistribution at the cross-section level, when one (or more) tendon becomes ineffective. The latter condition is typically due to degradation and environmental phenomena, such as corrosion. Another example regards the case of a bridge deck, made of longitudinal and transverse beams, over which a slab lays. The latter, if properly designed, ensures an effective load redistribution between the elements by transferring the load from the potentially damaged elements to those still “safe”. A similar discussion holds in the case of beam grillage. It should be noted that, in all cases, a certain degree of robustness can be associated to each

component of the bridge, related to its “internal” capacity of load redistribution due to a damage, i.e., providing Alternate Load Paths (ALPs).

In addition to this, the structural robustness is strongly affected by the global structural scheme of the bridge, in which the role played by each component can be analyzed by using the concepts of statics. In this sense, a local damage produces a variation in the static scheme and in the corresponding load paths. In the case of statically determinate structures, such as bridges made of simply supported beams, local damage cannot occur without creating a mechanism. Therefore, such systems are characterized by a zero degree of robustness, although damage propagation and global collapse are prevented by segmentation of the deck. On the other hand, statically indeterminate scheme, such as continuous beams, are inherently characterized by a certain degree of robustness, since a local damage would produce load redistribution, rather than a collapse. As a conclusion, it can be said that, depending on the static scheme, the related degree of robustness needs to be evaluated.

The final level of the approach takes into account the global resilience of the network systems (Miani et al., 2024), that is intended as the capability of the system to withstand local structural failure without experiencing a global disruption. In this sense, the above-discussed structural robustness of the bridge can be intended as a “local” vulnerability, with respect to the “global” vulnerability of the network. In this approach, the resilience of the infrastructure is assessed by considering the presence of alternative routes, which are able to effectively compensate a local disruption of the system.

The proposed framework is still under development. Further analyses will be carried out, with particular reference to the definition of indexes and metrics able to synthetically describe the robustness and resilience of the above-mentioned systems, thus encompassing their features at the different levels of analysis.

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The CEDAS project: challenges and opportunities in engaging citizens and stakeholders in exposure data collection

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Abstract

Communities play a central role in all phases of disaster risk reduction, from response to recovery and preparedness. Since strong earthquakes can have severe impacts, ranging from physical damage to casualties and socio-economic losses, it is paramount to engage a wide range of citizens with different expertise. One way to do this is to organize participatory activities to collect the available risk-related information, in particular on exposure.

Since 2021, within the CEDAS project (building CENSUS for seismic Damage ASsessment) students and teachers from schools in northeastern Italy have been engaged in collecting information on the characteristics of buildings in selected study areas (Scaini et al., 2022). We have been testing an online form that allows students to map the characteristics of exposed assets, buildings in particular, both remotely and on the field (Peresan et al., 2023). The form has been gradually enhanced to include indicators useful for multi-hazard exposure assessment, and to accommodate different information depending on the specific context.

The experience collected during the CEDAS project shows that crowdsourcing and citizen science activities can contribute to both enhancing the exposure data available for the scientific community and increasing risk awareness among young students in the region. Currently, the project is in process of being implemented with different types of societal stakeholders, such as citizens and practitioners (Scaini et al., 2025). The CEDAS project aims not only at data collection but also at increasing citizens' awareness and willingness to contribute in risk mitigation actions. We discuss the challenges and opportunities of engaging citizens and stakeholders into the CEDAS activity and foster their active role in disaster risk reduction.

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Challenges and Partnership in DRR. Reconstructing the Third-Sector Network in IX Municipality of Naples.

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Abstract

Introduction

Political, economic, and social processes significantly influence vulnerability (Wisner et al., 2004; Zakour & Gillispie, 2013), affecting individuals' social capital, and resource allocation mechanisms during emergencies. The lack of planning for the protection of the most vulnerable groups increases the likelihood of greater damage in crisis management (McEntire, 2007).

The literature on this topic identifies vulnerability at the community level, linking it to demographic, cultural, and ecological characteristics (Sherraden & Fox, 1997). Communities are particularly vulnerable when they have limited access to essential services and organizations capable of responding to emergencies or when coordination among them is inefficient (Maglajlic, 2019).

In this context, third-sector organizations (ETS) play a crucial role within local communities, contributing significantly to both emergency prevention and management (Allegri, 2015).

The literature review analyzed 30 publications on Soccavo and 85 on Pianura across various disciplines. Soccavo studies focus on housing policies, urban regeneration, environmental resilience, and historical memory, particularly INA-Casa's role in its transformation. Research on Pianura covers geology, hydrogeological risk, agricultural changes, and urban expansion.

Methodologically, the literature adopts an interdisciplinary approach, combining quantitative and qualitative studies, including statistical analyses, GIS tools, predictive risk models, ethnographic research, and resident interviews.

This study is focused on the context of Naples' IX Municipality, a zone characterized by urban, social, and environmental challenges, with significant implications for sustainable territorial planning. Particularly, the context is characterized by hydrogeological and bradyseismic risk, influencing social vulnerability. This work aims to reconstruct the third-sector network operating in the neighborhoods of Soccavo and Pianura, shedding light on the key actors, their interconnections, and their role in addressing local vulnerabilities. By mapping these relationships, the study seeks to provide insights into the extent of collaboration among stakeholders and their capacity to respond to environmental and social risks, ultimately contributing to more effective policy interventions.

Methodology

The research was conducted in three phases.

The first step involved a social network analysis (SNA) carried out using indirect sources, such as social media pages and organizational websites, to map the relationships between no profit organizations. This approach allowed for the identification of key connections and collaboration patterns among third-sector organizations.

In the second phase, the actors at the core of the network were (or will soon be) interviewed to gain deeper insights into the nature of their partnerships and their perception of the impact of environmental risks on these neighborhoods. The interviews follow a semi-structured format, covering themes such as resource-sharing dynamics, barriers to collaboration, and strategies for crisis management and community resilience.

The third phase analyzed the preliminary data alongside the findings from the interviews. The connections and interactions identified through interviews with associations confirm the preliminary findings derived from indirect sources, such as social media pages and institutional websites. Additionally, the interviews have uncovered the presence of further associations that were not initially identified, expanding the network and offering new insights into the dynamics of collaboration in the area.

Results

A network emerged from each phase.

Source: Our elaboration on web data

Fig. 1 – First phase: connections and collaboration patterns among third-sector organizations

Source: Our elaboration based on interviews

Fig.2- Second phase: third-sector organizations interviewed or to be interviewed.

Source: Our elaboration based on interviews

Fig.3- Total network

Conclusions

In the next phases of the research, the pending connections within the network will be further explored through upcoming interviews with the remaining associations.

Furthermore, the focus will be on gaining a deeper analysis of the collaboration mechanisms within the network, particularly by examining the factors that facilitate or hinder partnerships among ETS. Additional interviews with key stakeholders will provide further insights into the nature of these relationships, the challenges they face, and the strategies they employ to navigate disaster risk reduction and disaster risk management.

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Designing sustainable transition in multi-risk contaminated sites: the RETURN co-design Urban Living Lab methodology for the area of Bagnoli-Coroglio, Naples, Italy

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Abstract

In the framework of the RETURN project, tasks 5.5.2 and 5.4.4 aim to define a more inclusive and sustainable planning methodology for the transition of multi-risk contaminated sites toward a more circular city. Undoubtedly, stakeholder engagement is essential to activating a sustainable transition process (Innella et al., 2024). To this end, tasks 5.5.2 and 5.4.4 have set an Urban Living Lab (ULL) methodology and tested it through some city-scale exercises in the Site of National Interest (SIN) of Bagnoli-Coroglio, Naples, South of Italy. The methodology is designed to support the definition of circular, sustainable, and inclusive strategies for risk mitigation in multi-risk contaminated sites.

According to Bulkeley (2019) ULL may be strategic, if they are led by the State; civic, with local oriented institutional partners such as universities; and finally organic if they are grassroots and organized by nonprofit associations. The RETURN ULL Bagnoli-Coroglio is a Civic ULL coordinated by the Department of Architecture (DiARC) at the University of Naples Federico II. It is organized in three phases: co-exploring, co-design, and co-testing. Rather than being a physical laboratory, the ULL workshops operate across different locations, moving between the Bagnoli area and the city of Naples through workshops, interviews, and fieldwork involving experts, citizens, and stakeholders. As such, the RETURN ULL can be described as an entity that transcends geographic, demographic, and organizational boundaries throughout the project (Ebbesson et al., 2024).

This methodological characteristic is particularly relevant in an area such as the SIN Bagnoli-Coroglio, where physical barriers – such as the three-meter wall enclosing the former industrial area – separate local communities from official administrations (the state, the commissioner, and Invitalia), and where soil contamination continues to impact accessibility and the regeneration process. In this context, a multi-stakeholder approach can facilitate dialogue among institutions, residents, and private stakeholders, reducing conflicts and improving decision-making process (Baccarne et al., 2016). Moreover, applying ULL methodologies can shift the focus from purely technical remediation analysis to fostering relationships among the actors involved (Ascione et al., 2021).

Following co-exploration meetings held in February 2024, this contribution focuses on the organization of the co-design phase, outlining the methodology for the design activities scheduled from March to May 2025. Building on the assessment of existing and perceived risks explored in the initial phase, the co-design aims to identify more inclusive and sustainable regeneration actions for contaminated sites, adopting a systemic approach and emphasizing co-creation.

The RETURN ULL co-design meetings will bring together a diverse range of stakeholders, including Academia and research (Postgraduate students, experts and researchers acting as facilitators); Public sector (Municipal urban planning councilors and local school managers); Private sector (Representatives from the tourism

industry and local businesses); Civil society (Local activist organizations), using serious games, visual collaboration tools, and a work-in-progress booklet. These meetings will contribute to defining guidelines for the circular regeneration of multi-risk urban areas.

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Data-driven numerical modeling of water infrastructure

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Abstract

Data-driven numerical modeling includes multiple dimensions, closely connected due to the systemic nature of the water distribution networks: *topological dimension*, that can be addressed based on graph theory; *structural dimension*, with models representing the state of degradation of the infrastructure; *hydraulic dimension*, reproduced by means models that represent the fluid motion; *environmental dimension*, based on the representation of boundary conditions; *social and economic dimension*, based on models representing water demand by quantifying current and future needs. This approach aims to connect the different dimensions of modeling by communicating data and models for an approach oriented to an analysis able to support a global vision of water distribution systems.

The proposed methodology uses information about the infrastructure and the monitoring of hydraulic parameters, water consumption and water quality. If overall assessments of the impact of environmental changes are introduced, including those related to climate and the economic and social context, numerical modeling can provide indications from the overall to the local, both in terms of impact understood as the criticality that is generated, and in terms of efficiency of actions that can be implemented at a structural, managerial level or intended to impact on water demand. Numerical modelling can therefore support the process of identifying interventions, allowing the creation of scenarios and the evaluation of impacts; in fact, planning and design are intrinsically multi-criteria and multi-phase (Cunha et al., 2019).

Water Distribution Systems (WDS) can be modeled in the topological dimension as complex graphs whose development took place in successive stages to characterize a network and identify the connectivity as a measure of resilience from the infrastructure point of view. If the network as a whole is seen as a connected graph, each edge has a different importance within the real system. Given the undirected weighted graph $G = (N, E)$, the Primary Network (PN) is identified by means the algorithm proposed in Zingali et al. (2024) in which PN is defined as a connected sub-graph which meets some criteria: (i) given the strategic relevance of primary nodes, PN is request to connects the subset $NP \subset N$ by means the minimum weighted path; (ii) PN is a non-tree subgraph to guarantee a certain degree of redundancy; (iii) PN must transport a proper fraction of the water consumption within its edges. The criteria (i) and (ii) are mainly direct to the interconnection of primary nodes; all the criteria (i), (ii) and (iii) are mostly applied to sustain an eventual WDS sectorization.

In the modeling of the structural dimension, identifying the key factors that influence the pipe failure is a key task in developing reliable prediction models. According to a recent review, these factors can be generally grouped into three types according to their attributes in WDS: physical, operational, environmental, social and economic (Fan et al., 2023; Taiwo et al., 2023).

The hydraulic analysis is based on the Water Network Tool for Resilience (WNTR) that is an EPANET compatible Python package designed to simulate and analyze resilience of water distribution networks (Klise et al., 2017). The official WNTR software repository is hosted in the U.S. EPA's GitHub organization (USEPA/WNTR). The PDD model is that proposed by Wagner et al. (1988):

$$d = \begin{cases} 0 & p \leq P_0 \\ D_f \sqrt{\frac{p - P_0}{P_f - P_0}} & P_0 < p < P_f \\ D_f & p \geq P_f \end{cases}$$

where d is the actual demand delivered to customers (m^3/s), D_f is the customers expected demand (m^3/s), p is the pressure (Pa), P_f is the pressure above which the customer should receive the expected demand (Pa), and P_0 is the pressure below which the customers cannot receive any water (Pa). P_f and P_0 can be defined at each node and can be modified by the user.

Parma WDS was identified as case study within the area managed by IREN SpA. An advanced hydraulic (physically-based) model of a real-world water supply network has been implemented in WNTR Python package able to perform multiple analysis (Figure 1). The pressure-driven model will be used on long-term simulation under changeable water resources and water demand scenarios. The results will be able to be included in the assessment of a realistic vulnerability and in the validation of possible interventions for the mitigation of the associated risk.

Figure 1 – WNTR results: maps of average pressures and relative percentage distribution at the nodes of the Parma water distribution system model, respectively in (a) and (b).

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Definition of a Seismic Vulnerability Index as a support for seismic indicators in multi-risk analyses: the case study of Campi Flegrei

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Abstract

In the context of the RETURN project, analyses are underway for the definition of a multi-hazard model that can define, for a defined area, the expected impact of each of the phenomena considered or by a temporal chain of events. Within this context, it is necessary to define indicators that are able to compare the risks deriving from the different phenomena, in terms of expected impact. In this abstract, a methodology for the definition of a seismic vulnerability index and its application developed in the context of the Campi Flegrei is presented. The seismic vulnerability index is a synthetic parameter with a value between 0 and 1, which considers both the quality and quantity of the exposed elements (ordinary buildings); the index can be considered a preparatory indicator for the definition of the risk of the investigated area.

The localized estimation of the vulnerability index was developed and calibrated within the framework of the "Extraordinary Plan for the Analysis of Vulnerability in Areas Affected by the Bradyseismic Phenomenon", approved in February 2024, in line with D.L. No. 140 (October 2023). The plan focuses on areas with significant seismic and ground uplift activity since 2015, beginning with a survey of structural characteristics and vulnerability classification of private buildings at the territorial level.

The PLINIVS Study Centre, coordinated by the Civil Protection Department, conducted a survey of 12,000 buildings using a standardized form (PLINIVS form). Professionals collected data on the seismic and volcanic characteristics of buildings using the QGIS tablet application. The survey was completed by July 2004, and the data were processed to generate vulnerability assessments by grouping buildings into 250m x 250m cells. Vulnerability was classified using the SAVE procedure (Zuccaro and Cacace, 2015) and the CAESAR II analysis model, with results categorized as very low, low, medium, or high vulnerability index.

Based on the complete analysis and territorial vulnerability assessments, the Civil Protection Department will be able to investigate the vulnerability of individual buildings, starting from the most vulnerable areas. A final report, detailing financial costs and mitigation plans, has been submitted to the government for further action.

Figure 1 – Seismic Vulnerability Index for Campi Flegrei area

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Rischi ambientali, sicurezza sociale, comunicazione e salute pubblica

AMBITO 4

Evaluation of the Ecotoxicological risk in the Bioremediation of Hydrocarbon-Contaminated Soil

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Abstract

Soil contamination with hydrocarbon is quite common during processes of transport and storage. Bioremediation is considered a safe, economical, and environmentally friendly approach for contaminated soil treatment (Giovanella et al., 2021). However, beyond pollutant degradation, it is crucial to assess the ecotoxicological impact of bioremediation strategies to ensure real environmental recovery (El Fantroussi et al., 2005). Bioaugmentation offers significant advantages over other remediation techniques: by introducing specific microbial populations, the degradation process can begin immediately, potentially reducing long-term toxicity. One of the key challenges in hydrocarbon bioremediation is the persistence of toxic intermediates, which may pose risks to soil health and biota. The use of biosurfactants can enhance hydrocarbon degradation by increasing solubility, mobility, and bioavailability (Cameotra et al., 2010), but their interactions with soil microbiota and ecosystems require thorough ecotoxicological evaluation. A microbial consortium was formulated using nine different species of selected indigenous hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria and applied in bioaugmentation tests on hydrocarbon-contaminated soil. Evaluation of the biodegradability of pollutants and the attenuation of toxic effects was evaluated with chemical, microbiological and respirometric analysis. The microbiological and chemical effectiveness of the process has been previously demonstrated, confirming significant hydrocarbon degradation and microbial activity. In particular, this work focuses on the long-term ecotoxicological effects of bioaugmentation in hydrocarbon-contaminated soils. Ecotoxicological tests were carried out on either the solid fraction and aqueous and organic extract of TPH soil at different bioremediation stages. The ecotoxicological assessment was performed using a battery test with model organisms belonging to different trophic levels and biological complexity: plants *Lepidium sativum*, *Sinapis alba*, and *Sorghum saccharatum*, a bacterium *Aliivibrio fischeri*, a microalga *Chlorella vulgaris*, and crustacean *Daphnia magna*.

The results showed a general reduction in soil toxicity over time. However, toxicity peaked at T15 in bioaugmented samples, particularly for *Chlorella vulgaris*, which remained highly sensitive throughout the experiment, possibly due to secondary metabolite formation. By T90, toxicity levels for *Daphnia magna* and plant species decreased significantly, indicating soil recovery. This study highlights the potential of bioaugmentation combined with biosurfactant-producing strains for remediating petroleum-contaminated soils. Future work will incorporate *Pseudomonas glycinis* A2-5 biosurfactant into the microbial formula to further enhance bioremediation efficiency and to increase the exposure times up to 120 days. Ecotoxicological tests using multiple species proved effective in assessing soil health and recovery.

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Exploring the overall sediment environmental status through a statistically multi-variate approach.

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Abstract

Anthropic pressure in a river basin can take on different forms linked to urbanization, the various types of existing industrialization, and agricultural activities. The larger the catchment basin, the more anthropogenic contamination processes are possible. Contamination phenomena can feature their source areas or, more frequently, broader sections of the basin downstream of the immission point due to fate and transport processes linked to the natural dynamism of the stream waters. The study of the level of contamination of running surface waters is relevant for analyzing the state of contamination associated with active processes. At the same time, along the path of the watercourse, changes in the slope, roughness and width of the river bed, as much as bank height and other parameters, can influence the stream water energy and lead to significant accumulation of sediments in some sections of the mainstream. If the sediment accumulates in a contaminated environment, it is obvious to expect that a certain quantity of contaminants present in the water can adhere to solid particles and settle at the bottom of waterways.

Sometimes, sediments can be mobilized after accumulating in the riverbed following flood waves and intense meteoric processes. On such occasions, which are increasingly frequent in the context of climate change, the dispersion halo of the contamination process can reach downstream river sections very far from the source and, in case of flooding, soils close to watercourses can become receptors of contaminated materials even if not directly in contact with the primary source.

Based on these premises, the chemical analysis of stream sediments is a tool that can return key information on the source, intensity, and historical continuity of contamination processes affecting a catchment basin or a part of it.

A comprehensive geochemical survey was carried out in the framework of the RETURN project to explore the environmental impact of multiple anthropic stressors on a changing environment. The Sarno River, in southern Italy, sadly identified as one of the most contaminated waterways in Europe, was chosen for the purpose.

Twenty-four sampling points were selected along the whole river course (including the Solofrana and Cavaiola tributaries), and at each point, stream sediments and waters (when available) were collected.

Waters were analyzed at the Environmental Geochemistry lab of the Department of Earth, Environment and Resource Sciences (University of Naples Federico II) using the Palintest 7500 photometer.

ENEA (IMPACT Division) analyzed sediments, assessing the concentration of a selection of potentially toxic elements and some additional metals (which we will conventionally report as PTEs+) and organic compounds (including PAHs, PCBs, OCPs, organotin compounds, and others). Ecotoxicological tests were also carried out at ENEA on both sediments and waters.

The total content of PTEs+ (Be, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, As, Cd, Pb, U, V, Hg) in the sediments was obtained by solubilizing the samples using the microwave-assisted acid digestion procedure according to the EPA 3052 method.

We present preliminary results relating to the distribution of PTEs+ in the Sarno River sediments. An attempt, based on applying a multivariate statistical analysis technique (PCA) in a version specifically designed for compositional data (Comas-Cufí and Thió-Henestrosa, 2011), to identify the primary historical sources of contamination in the river basin was also made.

Regarding single elements, it is a fact that total Cr shows a markedly higher presence in the upper part of the river basin near the industrial centre of Solofra, where there is a high concentration of tanneries that use chromium salts for tanning in their production process. On the opposite, the highest Cu concentrations characterize the lower section of the basin, toward the river mouth, where anthropogenic contributions proceeding from agricultural activities are widely documented.

The PCA performed on a selection of highly correlated elements allowed us to classify samples into two main groups, one predominantly affected by the industrial pressure exerted by the tannery pole (Upper course) and one mainly influenced by agricultural activities and urbanization (Lower course) (Fig. 1b). We also considered the potential influence of the sediment grain size on metal accumulation with no firm evidence of correlation.

The upcoming activities will include integrating the existing PTE+ database with data on the concentration of organic compounds within the same samples. The joint use of organic and inorganic data to run inferential statistics in a multivariate perspective could lead to an improved definition of the chemical profile of complex contamination sources and a better understanding of the underlying risks.

Figure 1 – a) Biplot showing the result obtained by PCA with samples (observation) classified according to their grain size (Sand, silt and clay [Gravel < 10%]; GS= Gravelly sediments) (Schlee, 1973) and the pelitic fraction content (hp= high pelite; lp= low pelite) b) Distribution of the scores assigned to samples by the first component (PC1) (+[Co, v, Cr, Ni, V] vs. –[Hg, Cu, Pb, Zn]) extracted by PCA.

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Implications of valuing cultural heritage for multi-risk management in an urban context

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Abstract

Cultural heritage in urban areas is uniquely vulnerable to natural hazards due to its intangible values and strong ties to economic activities and community resilience. This study introduces a participatory, quantitative framework for assessing the exposure of cultural heritage assets to natural hazards, integrating physical risk indicators (Nobile et al., 2025) with cultural significance metrics. Conducted in Florence, Italy, the research focuses on flood and seismic risks, utilizing innovative methodologies to prioritize heritage conservation based on community-driven insights (Arrighi et al., 2025).

The approach combines hazard-specific metrics—such as flood depth and peak ground acceleration for earthquakes—with social value scores derived from pairwise comparison surveys (Masi et al., 2024). This dual analysis identifies culturally significant assets at risk, offering a new perspective on traditional exposure assessments. Community participants, including citizens and cultural association members, ranked heritage sites by relative importance, revealing that museums generally hold greater social value than places of worship.

Figure 1 – Social value of cultural heritage and flood depths modelled for a recurrence interval of 500 years in the

municipality of Florence (Arrighi et al., 2025).

By incorporating flood and seismic risk assessments, the framework adapts to multi-hazard contexts. Overlaying hazard maps with social value maps highlights a mismatch between the sites facing the highest physical risks and those of greatest cultural importance, emphasizing the need for targeted mitigation efforts. Correlation analyses reveal significant links between social value and factors such as ticket prices, visitor numbers, and building type, with canonical correlation analysis achieving a predictive accuracy of $r=0.75$. However, intangible aspects like spiritual and aesthetic values remain difficult to quantify and evolve over time.

The findings demonstrate that integrating social and physical metrics reshapes priority areas, shifting attention from conventionally high-risk zones to culturally significant yet less physically vulnerable sites. This framework offers a scalable model for disaster risk management, enabling policymakers to incorporate societal values into mitigation strategies. Future research could further refine this approach by exploring additional intangible cultural values, expanding community engagement, and addressing a wider range of hazards.

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The Impact of Climate Change on Occupational Populations

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Abstract

As well known, climate change has significant implications for human health. Rising temperatures, extreme weather events, and air pollution may affect both the general and occupationally exposed populations. For these reasons, two systematic literature reviews have been performed: a systematic review and meta-analysis on the general population and an umbrella review on occupational population. Both reviews aim to assess the health effects of climate change and highlight preventive strategies, with a particular focus on urban settings. In this work, we focused on the principal outcomes from the literature review conducted on the evaluation of the climate change effects on the occupationally exposed population.

In particular, the umbrella review screened 6,531 articles across three databases (Scopus, Web of Science, and PubMed). After eliminating duplicates and applying exclusion criteria, 103 systematic reviews were analyzed.

The findings highlight that certain occupational groups are particularly vulnerable to climate change, including agricultural workers, fishermen, construction laborers, miners, transportation personnel, and healthcare providers (Table 1a). These workers experience a range of health risks, from heat-related illnesses (e.g., heat exhaustion, dehydration, kidney disease) to respiratory and cardiovascular conditions, mental health challenges, and increased workplace injuries (Table 1b). Socioeconomic factors, pre-existing health conditions, and poor workplace ventilation further exacerbate these risks (Table 1c). Moreover, principal results show that the interaction between environmental, individual, and occupational variables is crucial in understanding climate-related health effects. High temperatures, humidity, and urban heat islands significantly impact outdoor workers, while individual susceptibility factors such as age, gender, pregnancy, and chronic diseases further modify risk levels. Occupational conditions, including physically demanding labor, inadequate cooling measures, and lack of workplace policies, contribute to heightened vulnerability (Table 1d). This review also identifies preventive, adaptation, and mitigation strategies to reduce climate-related health burdens. Implementing cooling infrastructures, ensuring hydration access, modifying work schedules, and enforcing stronger occupational health policies are essential measures. Additionally, early warning systems, protective equipment, and worker education programs can mitigate risks.

In conclusion, climate change poses severe health threats to both the general and occupationally exposed populations. The findings of this study emphasize the need for integrated public health and occupational safety interventions. Policymakers should prioritize climate adaptation strategies tailored to urban environments and high-risk occupational groups to safeguard public health in the face of ongoing climate challenges.

WORKERS MOST EXPOSED TO THE EFFECTS OF CLIMATE CHANGE

- Farmers and Agricultural Workers
- Fishermen and Maritime Workers
- (a) Miners and Heavy Industry Workers
- Construction Workers*
- Transportation and Logistics Workers*
- Healthcare Workers and First Responders*

HEALTH EFFECTS

- Heat-related Illnesses *Heat exhaustion, heatstroke, dehydration, kidney diseases.*
- Respiratory and Cardiovascular Issues *Worsened asthma, heart strain, hypertension.*
- Chronic Conditions *Kidney disease, cardiovascular and respiratory diseases.*
- (b) Mental Health Impacts *Anxiety, depression, increased psychological distress.*
- Maternal and Fetal Health Risks *Preterm birth, low birth weight, pregnancy complications.*
- Infectious Diseases *Vector-borne diseases (e.g., Lyme, dengue, West Nile virus).*
- Injuries and Workplace Accidents *Increased risks of slips, falls, burns, fractures.*
- Reduced Productivity *Fatigue, cognitive decline, decreased work efficiency.*

SUSCEPTIBILITY

Category	Susceptibility factors	Type of Susceptibility
(c) Vulnerable groups by age and gender	Older adults	Demographic and Socioeconomic
	Young workers (<25 years)	
	Female workers	
Migrant and low-income workers	Pregnant women	Demographic and Socioeconomic
	Migrant and immigrant workers	
Socio-economically disadvantaged populations	Low-income workers	Demographic and Socioeconomic
	Marginalized communities	
	Indigenous populations	
People with pre-existing health conditions	Asthmatic patients Individuals with pre-existing health conditions (diabetes, cardiovascular diseases)	Health-related

	People with pre-existing chronic diseases	
Workers exposed to extreme environmental conditions	Outdoor workers Workers in extreme climates	
Workers in physically demanding sectors	Agricultural workers Construction workers Miners Physically demanding jobs	Environmental and occupational
People in poorly ventilated environments or with limited access to resources	Workers in poorly ventilated environments Individuals with limited access to hydration resources	
VARIABLE INFLUENCECS		
Environmental variables influence	Individual variables influence	Occupational variables influence
(d) High temperatures	Age	Type and location of work
Heatwaves	Gender	Working conditions
Humidity	Pregnancy	Poor workplace ventilation
Solar radiation	Body weight	Reduced cooling measures
Air pollution	Physical fitness	Long working hours
Urban heat islands	Pre-existing health conditions	Lack of breaks
Vector-borne diseases	Genetic predisposition	Physically demanding jobs
	Mental health conditions	Acclimatization
	Immune sensitivity	Use of protective clothing
	Medication use	Exposure duration
	Smoking or substance use	Insufficient workplace policies
	Hydration levels	
	Behavioral habits	
	Socioeconomic status	

Table 1 – Principal results of the study

* Urban setting

Consequences and risk modelling of NaTech in industrial environments

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Abstract

Industrial sites, especially when characterized by a long-lasting operation in the past when adequate environmental legislation was still not in place, have been the source of impact on the environment due to emissions to air, water and soil. Due to the enforcement of strict environmental legislation in the European community, the emissions of industrial activities are highly controlled (for example in the Environmental Integrated Authorization procedure concerning “big potential polluter” industries). Nevertheless, although emissions are within the limits imposed by the legislation, there is still a strong need to evaluate the environmental quality in a complex industrial context, characterized by potential impacts on the environment and on human health due to, for example, NaTech (Natural and Technological) hazards, which refers to industrial triggered by natural events such as storms, earthquakes, flooding and lightning.

Such a kind of assessment is needed for:

- correct planning of future industries and activities on the potentially affected land. This is, for example, the case of the environmental impact evaluation foreseen by the Italian/European legislation for the evaluation of specific projects (Italian Republic, 2006; European Union, 2014);
- the definition of technical interventions useful to contain the environmental impact of actual industrial activities (for example, in the framework of the integrated environmental authorization) (Italian Republic, 2006; European Union, 2010);
- the analysis of the current environmental impact of operating industrial activities. This is, for example, the case of the environmental health impact assessment foreseen by the Italian/European law for specific industrial installations (Italian Republic, 2006; European Union, 2014).

A comprehensive impact assessment of industrial sites requires to consider the contribution of diffuse sources from the operating plants and from the eventually contaminated subsoil, besides the usual conveyed emissions from stacks, plus to correlate the concentration at the point of exposure with the potential health risks on the receptor.

The modeling approaches used to deal with all emissions potentially produced at an industrial site, i.e. diffuse or concentrated emissions from the operating plant and diffuse emissions from the contaminated sites, are fairly different (Swartjes, 2015). Diffuse and conveyed emissions from industrial operating plants are usually evaluated using advanced dispersion models, which simulate the pollutant dynamics in the atmosphere (e.g. Gaussian or Lagrangian models like Calpuff, Spray, Aermoc and others). On the one hand, these models allow to simulate the pollutant dispersion in case of multiple and complex emission sources, non-steady atmospheric conditions, and variable orography. On the other hand, these tools require detailed input datasets of the meteorology and geophysical features of the area under study. Also, running these models requires a high effort in terms of human resources and computational time, and their use is limited to specialists in the field (Holmes and Morawska, 2006; Khan and Assan, 2021). Advanced dispersion models are currently applied to Health-Environmental Risk Assessment. Research activity has presently been taken to

improve such integrated approaches and the harmonization of these methodologies. The approach used to evaluate the impact of contaminated sites on the environment and potentially exposed human receptors is currently integrated into the Health-Environmental Risk Assessment. Health-Environmental Risk Assessment methodologies were internationally developed for contaminated sites (ASTM E1739, 1995; ASTM E2081, 2000) considering the evaluation of impacts due to specific chemical or physical agents in a particular site and time, with the aim of protecting human health at the local level. In Italy, the Health-Environmental Risk Assessment has been standardized for operators by ISPRA Public Agency with 2008 Guidelines and following modifications (ISPRA, 2008). Presently, national and international software are available on the market (e.g., Risk-net, RBCA, RISC and others) performing level II risk analysis, which relies on the description of pollutants dynamics in air, water and soil through over-simplified analytical equations, which generally provide an approximate, and usually overestimated evaluation of the impact on the receptors.

In this work an existing industrial plant is considered as an example case study. A potential damaging event resulting from a NaTech event will be applied to this scenario. To define the type of triggering event, a literature search has been conducted on the main existing NaTech databases. The results will include the representation of the consequences of a NaTech event in terms of risk and environmental indices, with a view to contributing to the development of a possible integrated prevention methodology.

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Vulnerability assessment of wastewater treatment plants using a territorial multi-hazard multi-scale approach

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Abstract

Extreme natural events are becoming increasingly frequent and intense due to climate change (Pilone et al., 2021). Their effects are projected to intensify in the coming decades, posing unprecedented challenges for infrastructure resilience. Climate impacts can not only devastate infrastructure during extreme events but also disrupt their operations and efficiency due to gradual environmental changes over time (Gupta et al., 2024).

In this scenario, wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) are a critical component of industrial infrastructure, particularly in Major Hazard Industries (MHIs) (Casson Moreno et al., 2018). These facilities play an essential role in public health and environmental protection, particularly in densely populated areas where large volumes of wastewater are generated.

To mitigate these impacts, a thorough knowledge of the combined effects of such events is an essential first step to improve WWTPs resilience. It focused on characterizing vulnerability scenarios, considering the bidirectional interaction between industry and territory (Castro Rodriguez et al., 2024).

To estimate the effects of extreme events it is certainly important to identify areas (location) and related infrastructures (function) that may be damaged by these events.

Focusing on the location factor, the methodology framework (Figure 1) considered five types of natural hazards: hydraulic, geomorphological, volcanic, seismic and tsunami.

Figure 1 – Methodologies framework of the function-location approach tailored to WWTPs

Focusing on the Sicilian region, each hazard map was harmonized so that H1 corresponded to the lowest hazard and H4 corresponded to the highest. The Sicilian territory was divided into a grid with 200 m x 200 m cells. Each cell is identified by an index i .

Specifically, the harmonized classes H_k ($k=1,2,3,4$) were assigned the following numerical values: $H_1=0.25$; $H_2=0.5$; $H_3=0.75$; $H_4=1$; thereby transitioning from a qualitative to a quantitative classification.

As mentioned before, five hazard types j are considered:

- Seismic hazard ($j=s$)
- Geomorphological hazard ($j=g$)
- Hydraulic hazard ($j=h$)
- Volcanic hazard ($j=v$)
- Tsunami hazard ($j=t$)

Each cell i is composed of portions that may belong to different hazard classes. The total area of the cell is denoted as A_i (40000 m²), while the area of the portion of territory associated with class H_k for hazard j is $A_{i,j,k}$.

For every cell, the relative weight of each hazard class is determined by the proportion of the cell area associated with that class, given by $w_{i,j,k} = \frac{A_{i,j,k}}{A_i}$.

This weight quantifies how much each class contributes to the overall hazard in the cell. To calculate the contribution of a specific class, we multiply its relative weight by its assigned numerical value H_k .

Summing up these contributions across all classes, we obtain the individual hazard indicator for hazard j within cell i :

$$HI_{i,j} = \sum_{k=1}^4 (w_{i,j,k} \cdot H_k)$$

This process is repeated for each type of hazard j .

The calculation of the individual hazard indicator is based on a weighted summation of the hazard classes within the cell. This method can be interpreted as an approximation of an integral over the cell surface, where the integrand represents the hazard level.

Finally, the multi-hazard index for cell i is computed as the weighted sum of individual hazard indicators by assuming an equal weight for each of them (0.20):

$$MHI_i = \sum_{j \in \{s,g,h,v,t\}} HI_{i,j}$$

A multi-hazard map was created to classify the territory into four distinct hazard levels, representing a gradation of potential threats. The classes are defined based on thresholds of the Multi-Hazard Index (MHI), which quantifies cumulative hazard levels. The thresholds are as follows:

- Class 1 (Low Hazard): $0 \leq MHI \leq 0.25$
- Class 2 (Moderate Hazard): $0.25 < MHI \leq 0.50$
- Class 3 (High Hazard): $0.50 < MHI \leq 0.75$
- Class 4 (Very High Hazard): $0.75 < MHI \leq 1$

Additionally, these hazard maps were overlaid with the locations of wastewater treatment plants in the

perspective of the functional-location approach. By combining the hazard classification with the spatial distribution of WWTPs, the study provided insights into which plants are most at risk, enabling the development of targeted strategies to enhance their resilience.

These topics are investigated within the RETURN project. Specifically, within the Spoke TS2-Multi Risk Resilience of Critical Infrastructures. WP 3 - Dynamic mapping of natural and climatic hazards over the infrastructure systems. T 3.2 – Robust hazard mapping over point critical infrastructures. Sub Task 3.2.2. Natural Hazards classification maps of point-like infrastructures of national relevance.

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A spatially-explicit modeling approach to simulate the spatial distribution of urban expansion as controlled by geomorphic and hydroclimatic drivers

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Abstract

The extent of urbanization is widely recognized, and future projections highlight significant sustainability concerns (Seto et al., 2011). Existing research acknowledges that various environmental, hydroclimatic, socioeconomic, and policy and institutional drivers influence urban growth, yet there is limited understanding of its detailed spatial and temporal dynamics. The ability to replicate observed patterns of urban expansion is crucial for projecting reliable future scenarios under changing climatic conditions.

Here, we develop an innovative spatially explicit probabilistic modeling framework based on an inhomogeneous Markov chain model to describe observed regional urban expansion dynamics (Ceola et al., 2024, see Figure 1). North-East China is selected as the study area to test our methodology, having experienced substantial urbanization over the past 30 years. We use nighttime lights (NTL), covering the period from 1992 to 2013, as a proxy for urban areas. NTL values range from 0 (absence of nocturnal luminosity) to 63 (maximum luminosity). Areas are classified as urban if NTL values exceed a threshold equal to 30. We derive the urbanization rate from urban data and model urban expansion dynamics in space through an inhomogeneous Markov chain, where the probability of urbanization varies in space and time to analytically account for main geomorphic and hydroclimatic drivers and existing urbanization patterns (Rybski et al., 2013)

We consider 128 different model combinations to explore the roles of geomorphic and hydroclimatic drivers, along with proximity to existing urban areas, in controlling the spatial and temporal dynamics of urban expansion. The comparison of different model settings is performed via formal model selection criteria in order to assess the relative importance of the considered drivers for urban expansion in the study area. Furthermore, we explore the predictive capability of our best performing model based on geomorphic and hydroclimatic data. We run forward simulations starting from the initial urban extent observed in 1992 and compare the statistical properties, including the distribution of urban cluster size (Gabaix, 1999), of the simulated and observed urbanization processes.

The spatially explicit modeling framework here employed, which is based on the multidimensional inhomogeneous Markov Chain method, proves capable of reproducing urbanization processes as controlled by geomorphic and hydroclimatic drivers. Our results indicate that elevation, terrain slope, distance from rivers, and distance from the sea are the most significant factors in the study area.

Figure 1 – Spatially explicit probabilistic modeling framework for urban expansion controlled by geomorphic and hydroclimatic drivers. Figure from Ceola et al., 2024.

Starting from the initial urban pattern in 1992, the estimated baseline rate of urbanization and the calibrated model parameters, the selected model (best AIC) provides reliable forward simulations of urban expansion dynamics (Figure 2). The spatial distribution and location of new urban areas from the ensemble of 100 forward simulations for any year within the study period shows strong agreement with observed patterns (Figure 2). The size distribution of urban clusters is satisfactorily reproduced by our model, further validating its accuracy. Despite some limitations, we believe our methodology to be a valuable tool for replicating and predicting the spatial distribution of urban expansion globally.

The valuable insights on the future locations of human settlements and the evolution of urban expansion can effectively support future planning strategies aimed at achieving more sustainable development under changing climatic conditions.

Figure 2 – Forward simulation of urban expansion dynamics. Comparison between data and model results for three different years (1999 - left column, 2006 - middle column, 2013 - right column) obtained simulating the selected model starting from the urban pattern observed in 1992 as initial condition. a)-c) Observed and d)-f) modeled urbanization dynamics, where urban grid cells in 1992 (i.e., the initial condition) are white, urban expansion to the considered year is depicted in red, non-urban grid cells are black. Panels d)-f) report the recall values (median and 5% - 95% values between parentheses) obtained from 100 different forward simulations starting in 1992. g)-i) Cluster size distribution for clusters with area >10 km² from data (red dots) and from forward simulations (grey lines), compared to those observed in 1992 (empty dots). j)-u) Cumulative distribution functions (CDFs) of geomorphic and hydroclimatic drivers in grid cells that became urban after 1992 as derived from data (red dotted line), forward simulations (grey lines), and in all grid cells (blue line). Figure from Ceola et al., 2024.

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Advancements on the variability of heatwave impacts on human thermal comfort in the urban context: an analysis in Bologna (Italy)

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Abstract

The 6th assessment report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) defines an extreme weather event as ‘an event that is rare at a particular place and time of the year’, and an extreme climate event as ‘a pattern of extreme weather that persists for some time, such as a season’ (Seneviratne S.I. et al., 2021). The latest IPCC report has demonstrated human-caused climate change has increased the frequency and intensity of weather extremes since the 1950s and additional warming will further increase their frequency and intensity. In particular, the Mediterranean region has long been identified as a climate change hotspot, particularly vulnerable to trends in precipitation and temperature extremes (Lazoglou et al., 2024). Of particular relevance and concern owing to the serious risks posed to human health, ecosystems and human activities including tourism and agriculture, the hot temperature extremes represent nowadays a widely studied topic. In this context, the WMO defines “a persistent period of abnormally warm weather for the time of the year” which can occur at any time of the year as a warm spell, or a heatwave if it occurred during the warm season, (WMO, 2023).

As concerns human health, the negative effects this kind of events poses on the vulnerable part of population are well known. Indeed, extreme heat exposure triggers a response in cardiovascular, endocrine and renal systems, which can cause critical health issues, resulting in increased morbidity and mortality (McGregor G.R. et al., 2015). In the last decades several compound biophysical indexes have been developed to understand and quantify the heat stress posed by persisting extreme hot temperatures. These indexes are defined to account for the fact that thermal comfort is not solely related to air temperature, but depends also on other variables such as humidity and radiation. Examples of such indexes are Heat Index, Humidex, Wet-Bulb Globe Temperature and Thom Discomfort Index, which provide a measure of thermal comfort considering humidity, wind speed, radiant temperature, as well as air temperature. By analysing data collected in the city of Bologna (44.495 N, 11.345 E) in the period between 1st January 2023 and 30th November 2023, this study focuses on the longest and most intense heatwave event that occurred in the study period.

The identification and characterization of the heatwave was performed based on two different indexes, i.e. the Warm Spell Duration Index (WSDI) and the Excess Heat Factor (EHF). The event occurred between 11th and 20th July 2023 and its impacts on thermal comfort were characterised in detail employing data from ERA5 reanalysis and observations from local weather stations. The synoptic analysis showed a geopotential pattern which encouraged the extension of African anticyclone over the Italian Peninsula, with the arrival of hot air masses to the Northern part of Italy. In this context, observations from official weather stations (ARPAE Regional Environmental Protection Agency) were integrated with data from amateur meteorological stations in order to have a wider spatial representation of the municipality of Bologna. This allows the creation of maps showing the spatial variability of biometrical indexes in the city during the heatwave event. As an example, the Heat Index (Figure 1) exhibited higher values in the east part of Bologna, densely urbanized, whilst the lowest values are found in the southern part of the city, i.e. the rural area

located on the Bologna hillside. The other biophysical indexes, namely Humidex, Thom Discomfort Index and Wet-Bulb Globe Temperature (simple algorithm) point out the same spatial distribution. The analysis of the spatial and temporal variability of such indexes points out very clearly the emergence of wide differences in the exposure of resident population to thermal stress, connected with the Urban Heat Island (UHI) phenomenon and its multiple scale intrinsic nature (Di Sabatino et al., 2020). Consequently, the correct use and interpretation of these indexes can help policy makers in the definition of measures and plans to mitigate the risks related to extreme hot temperatures.

Figure 1 – Heat Index colormap of the city of Bologna on 18th July 2023. Data were spatially averaged over statistical areas of the municipality of Bologna.

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Improving the PROPAGATOR Cellular Automaton Wildfire Simulator to Capture Transitions Between Surface and Crown Fires

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Abstract

PROPAGATOR is a wildfire spread simulator designed as a stochastic cellular automaton model, enabling rapid assessment of fire risk across diverse landscapes (Trucchia et al. 2020). It operates using raster implementation, incorporating detailed information on topography and vegetation distribution as main static inputs. By accounting for multiple vegetation types and their fire behavior characteristics in terms of spreading probability, rate of spread and fireline intensity, the model enhances its predictive capabilities in the wildfire-scenario making process. Essential dynamic inputs include wind and dead fuel moisture conditions, and ignition points to trigger the propagation process. Additionally, PROPAGATOR can include different firefighting interventions, such as altering fuel moisture content or strategically implementing firebreaks to contain fire spreading, to increase its usability during emergencies as a decision-support tool.

The probability of fire propagation is determined by a combination of factors regarding cell conditions and boundary conditions. The rate of spread is computed through an established Rate of Spread model, which helps quantify the speed and intensity of fire movement across the landscape. A spotting routine is also present, given its important effect in the fire spreading process and consequences on fire management strategies (López-De-Castro et al. 2024). Unlike deterministic models, PROPAGATOR generates multiple independent realizations of stochastic fire behavior, allowing for probabilistic assessments of fire spread to account for uncertainties in the modeling process and inputs. At each simulation step, it produces spatial probability maps indicating the likelihood of fire reaching specific areas, while also visualizing key fire behavior metrics such as potential spread rates and fire-line intensity. This information can support both emergency response and the wildfire scenario-making process for wildfire risk mitigation planning (Perello et al. 2024).

One critical aspect of fire behavior modeling is the transition from surface fires to crown fires, as canopy involvement significantly increases flame height, energy release, and propagation speed. This distinction is vital for both operational decision-making and the refinement of fire spotting submodels. To further enhance fire behavior predictions, Crown Fire Initiation and Spread Models will be introduced, complementing the existing framework, which primarily assume that in case of coniferous forests the fire propagates through the crown assuming the worst-case scenario for civil protection purposes. In the proposed framework the original model is going to be advanced by incorporating a more detailed fuel structure description that includes the vertical dimension (see Figure 1).

Figure 1 – The figure shows the conceptual schema of the next PROPAGATOR model enhancement, which will include the transition between surface and crown fires.

These adaptations will be based on established fire propagation models, modified where necessary to align with the stochastic nature of PROPAGATOR. Moreover, *Vertical Interaction Mechanisms* will be embedded within the probabilistic rules of the cellular automaton to simulate the conditions under which surface fires escalate into the canopy and, conversely, when crown fires revert to ground-level burning. Accurately capturing these dynamics requires integrating Canopy Fuel Characteristics, such as canopy base height, fuel load, bulk density, and foliar moisture content. However, this information is difficult to obtain for large areas and to keep them updated. While maintaining computational efficiency and considering the availability of this information, the model will incorporate these parameters using appropriate simplifications. Some experimental acquisitions of Lidar data from UAV have been carried out in pilot sites to generate input data.

The conceptual framework, modeling challenges, and implications of this development in PROPAGATOR are analyzed. The effectiveness of these enhancements will be validated through a combination of synthetic test cases and real-world fire scenarios, ensuring their practical applicability for end users, emergency responders, and fire management professionals. Through this improvement, PROPAGATOR aims to contribute to national and international efforts in wildfire risk management, strengthening research networks and fostering engagement in European and global strategic frameworks.

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A Comprehensive evaluation framework for effective decision making on risk mitigation

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Abstract

In the current context of climate change and often limited economic resources, effective risk mitigation necessitates the implementation of integrated measures that simultaneously address risk reduction in a multi-hazard context and promote economic, social, and environmental sustainability. Consequently, decision-making in risk mitigation must go beyond assessing the direct impact of a measure on overall risk levels. It should also incorporate a comprehensive evaluation of the broader benefits and potential drawbacks for at-risk communities, employing a multi-criteria analysis approach. This study presents a comprehensive framework for decision makers that incorporates all relevant criteria for identifying effective risk mitigation strategies. The framework was initially developed through interdisciplinary discussions among researchers from WP7.2 during a workshop held on 28-29 October 2024 and subsequently refined through several consultation meetings.

The framework distinguishes between intrinsic characteristics of the mitigation measures and their broader impacts in the context in which they are implemented, aligning with moral philosophy theories that differentiate procedural and consequential aspects (see Figure 1). In detail, the framework categorizes evaluation criteria into three main dimensions: **Implementability**, **Reliability**, and **Side Impacts**.

Implementability assesses the practical feasibility of implementing a given measure. It considers aspects such as commissioning, costs, fundability, technological and human resource availability, compatibility with existing plans, stakeholder involvement, and social acceptability.

Reliability evaluates the long-term effectiveness and sustainability of the measure. Key factors include lifespan, maintenance costs, adaptability, and reversibility upon the end of the project or decommissioning.

Side Impacts examines the broader implications of the measure beyond its direct risk-reduction function. It considers potential effects on local planning, existing infrastructure, the environment, local capacities, finances, cultural assets, societal issues, and macroeconomics.

This holistic approach ensures that decision-makers evaluate measures beyond their immediate mitigating purposes, considering their multifaceted implications, facilitating informed and balanced decisions.

Hydrology subdivides into surface water hydrology, groundwater hydrology (hydrogeology), and marine hydrology. Domains of hydrology include hydrometeorology, surface hydrology, hydrogeology, drainage-basin management, and water quality.

Figure 2 The evaluation criteria to a measure developed throughout the study

Odds to Escape Arrow

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Abstract

In our previous research and RETURN presentations, we discussed judgement aggregation rules. That is, methods that aggregate judgements of individual experts to a qualified collective judgement about events such as those posing natural risks. We discussed the advantages and disadvantages of two main approaches to judgement aggregation, weighted geometric and arithmetic mean, and argued for aggregating odds with the weighted geometric mean. However, we have not yet tackled any significant impossibility results, showing that an aggregation rule cannot simultaneously satisfy two or more desirable properties. The most famous impossibility result comes from Kenneth Arrow. Arrow's original result is formulated for preferences but can be reinterpreted and restated for judgement aggregation. This presentation shows that aggregating odds with the weighted geometric mean escapes Arrow's impossibility result.

Arrow's original result (Arrow K. J., 2012) is concerned with aggregating individual ordinal preferences into collective preferences. It shows that no aggregation rule for ordinal preferences into collective preferences can simultaneously satisfy the following four properties (Gaertner W., 2009): unrestricted domain, weak Pareto Principle, independence of irrelevant alternatives, and non-dictatorship. An unrestricted domain means no restriction on individuals' preferences. Non-dictatorship implies that no individual can hijack the decision process and make decisions irrespective of the preferences of others. The weak Pareto Principle says that if every individual prefers x to y , the collective preference also prefers x to y . Finally, independence means that preference between x and y does not depend on a third alternative. A big question in social choice theory is finding ways to escape Arrow's impossibility result without giving up one of the four aforementioned properties. We know we can escape Arrow's impossibility result in a couple of ways. The basic idea is to enrich the ordinal preference structure with more information. For example, we could use a graded ordinal scale (Balinski M. and Laraki R., 2007) or cardinal preferences with interpersonal comparability (Sen A., 2017).

Arrow's impossibility result can be translated into the judgement aggregation context (Dietrich F. and List C., 2007). Unrestricted domain and non-dictatorship have straightforward re-interpretations. Independence says that the collective judgement about any event depends solely on the individual judgements about that event. The weak Pareto Principle is re-interpreted as unanimity: if all experts believe x to the degree of y , then the aggregated degree of belief in x is also y . Consequently, we can ask: What mathematical structure of judgement aggregation can escape Arrow's impossibility theorem? We argue that a discussion about independence plays a significant part because it shows the difficulty of escaping Arrow's impossibility result by aggregating probabilistic opinions either

with the weighted geometric mean or, surprisingly, also weighted arithmetic mean, which is usually considered to satisfy independence. We will use this discussion to motivate the introduction of our aggregation rule, which is a weighted geometric mean that aggregates odds. We will show that odds and the weighted geometric mean have enough rich mathematical structure to escape Arrow's impossibility result. To interpret our results, we assume that the experts are Bayesians. Specifically, they use Bayesian conditionalisation to update their degrees of belief on new evidence. We, however, not only want to escape Arrow's impossibility result but also to preserve other desirable properties while doing so. Finally, we show that we do not need to sacrifice any good property of the weighted geometric mean when escaping Arrow's impossibility result with odds.

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Adapting to environmental hazards through urban green infrastructures: Evidence from the Functional Urban Area of Cagliari

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Abstract

This abstract summarizes some significant results developed under Task 5.4.3 “Green transition toward resilient and regenerative urban eco-districts” of Work Package 5.4 “Mitigation and adaptation for more resilient and livable cities” of RETURN Spoke 5-TS1 “Urban and metropolitan settlements”. Details of the results are contained in the Deliverable “Concept guidelines, design proposals and assessment protocols to monitor urban integrated resilience in compliance with NEB - New European Bauhaus principles” (referred to as “Deliverable” below).

The overall objective of the contribution to the Deliverable is to define a methodology to identify the correlation between the provision of certain ecosystem services (ESs) and the adaptation of the urban environment to risk conditions related to certain climate change impacts, with particular reference to hydraulic phenomena and heat waves. The methodology is applied to the spatial context of the Functional Urban Area (FUA) of Cagliari.

The methodology is based on the recognition of urban green infrastructure (UGI) as an implementation of the conceptual category of green infrastructure (GI) in the urban context. These are, therefore, networked systems, consisting of core areas and urban ecological corridors (UECs), characterized by an important, complex and diversified supply of ESs (Tzoulas et al., 2007). Green areas, especially if wooded or forested, are identified as peculiar characteristics of UGIs, as providers of ESs that, in the urban domain, offer significant benefits in terms of improving the quality of life. In the methodological approach defined and applied to the FUA of Cagliari, the following ESs are considered: urban heat mitigation, carbon capture and storage, habitat quality, runoff and flood control, and recreational opportunities (Nedkov, Burkhard, 2012; Isola et al., 2024). From this point of view, it should, therefore, be emphasized that plan policies in the urban sphere should, hopefully, be aimed at recognizing, in scientific and technical terms, the strategic relevance of urban greenery as a foundational element in defining narratives about the city's possible and desirable futures (McDonald et al., 2023).

Within this framework, theoretical and operational, the relevance of the quantitative profile relating to urban public green space should be recognized. The function of the endowment of green spaces, whether tree-lined or forested, linked by UECs, should, therefore, be taken as a structural reference for city planning. These policies should plan for a significant and widespread increase in green space, including through the identification and enhancement of UECs as key connective elements of UGIs (Kabisch et al., 2016).

The results of the contribution to the Deliverable indicate how the approach, unfortunately still widespread, that considers, in city analysis and planning processes, the arrangement of urban greenery as subordinate to that of built-up areas is, by now, obsolete (Valente et al., 2022). In other words, the maximization of land rents

should be progressively replaced, as a fundamental lever for planning the city's possible and desirable futures, with the maximization of the effectiveness of UGIs, thus with the maximization of the supply of ESs associated with them. The methodology developed here is configured as exportable to other urban contexts, particularly those identified as FUAs. The analysis of the supply of ESs, and the consequent identification of the functions of the UGIs, implemented with reference to the FUA of Cagliari, can be replicated in relation to other FUAs, especially taking into account that the ESs supply framework, on which the identification of the UGI of the FUA of Cagliari is based, constitutes an effective matrix in general terms, although not exhaustive. The spatial database on which the UGI of the FUA of Cagliari is based consists of data generally available in the urban contexts of FUAs, thus in the urban contexts of OECD countries.

Two promising avenues for the development of future research can be recognized. First, a refinement of the methodology for identifying UECs would be desirable, including through a comparative analysis of the results reported in the Deliverable with those derived from other methodological approaches. Second, it would be very important that the methodology for identifying UECs be refined. It would, therefore, be very important to critically reconsider the set of ESs assumed in the study developed in the Deliverable for the identification of the UGI of the FUA of Cagliari, refining the methodological approaches used to assess the supply of ESs and possibly including new types of ESs.

Figure 1 highlights the conceptual link between what is summarized here, and the detail of which is contained in the Deliverable, with the framework proposed in a Storyline, reported in Deliverable 5.3.1 “Reports and scenarios for multi-risk, cascading and compounding effects, and emerging risks,” in relation to heat wave and surface water flooding hazards.

Full info on this storyline is provided in DV 5.3.1, *Report and scenarios for multi-risk, cascading and compounding effects and emerging risks*, Chapter 5.1

Figure 1 – Storyline related to heat waves and surface water flooding.

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The dispersion of microplastics in coastal environments: the natural laboratory of Pino di Lenne (Taranto, southern Italy).

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Abstract

Pino di Lenne, part of the Stornara Nature Reserve, is a protected area in the Apulia Region (southern Italy) regulated by national and regional laws. It is also listed as a Site of Community Interest (SIC) and a Special Protection Area (SPA). The beach in this coastal sector remains almost untouched by human activity, with no bathing establishments or cleaning machines, as environmental modifications are prohibited. Due to its pristine condition, the beach was chosen for microplastic monitoring, with potential sources being the Lenne River or minimal human presence in summer. The backshore features intact dunes and rich biodiversity typical of river environments. The Lenne River, originating from a karstic spring at 23 meters above sea level, flows for 24 kilometers before reaching the sea in the Gulf of Taranto. This type of river, fed by surface water tables, is common between Taranto and Metaponto, but the Lenne River contributes to the area's unique and unspoiled landscape. Finally, the sedimentary environment is characterised by the presence of a worm bioconstruction built by polychaetes of the genus *Sabellaria*, capable of trapping sands and remains of anthropogenic origin. With the aim of investigating MPs distribution and environmental conditions in different beach sectors, sampling points at Pino di Lenne beach follow the beach profile from the emerged to the submerged zone. In the submerged zone, two transects (Transect A and Transect B) were made perpendicular to the shoreline from the foreshore to the offshore transition, using a diving technique. Additional samples were taken from the inner Torrente Lenne and the *Sabellaria* bioconstruction in the upper shoreface.

Once collected, samples were stored at UNIBA laboratories for pre-treatment analysis: first, they were dried at the 30-50°C temperature range for at least three consecutive days, and grain-size analyses were carried out following the international standard procedures. Then, sediments were treated with hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂ – 10 % and 30) in glass beakers for 24 hours for the digestion of the organic matter.

MPs identification was performed by applying a low impacting procedure proposed by Scopetani et al. (2020) based on the use of olive oil for the separation of plastic particles from the beach and marine sediments, as proposed in Rizzo et al. (2025). Sediment samples were mixed with H₂O and olive oil. Then, after 3 hours, the solution was frozen at -4°C. to extract the oil portion containing MPs. Then, a vacuum pump equipped with 2.7µm glass fiber filters was used to collect the MPs. To remove the oil portion from the particles, the filters were rinsed with ethanol. Finally, the filters were observed at the optical microscope for MPs classification. Sediment analysis indicates a stable beach environment, sustained by fluvial inputs from the southern Apennines and coastal drift. MPs degrade in the backshore due to environmental factors and later settle on

the seabed. Four MPs classes (fibres, film, fragments, and pellets) were identified through visual examination, with black and blue being the most common, alongside red, green, purple, orange, and yellow (Figure 1).

Figure 1 – Examples of MPs identified in the sediment samples collected at Pino di Lenne.

MP concentration was generally high compared to other studies, as olive oil effectively extracts MPs of various densities. Along Transect A, the submerged sector contained more MPs than the emerged sector, while in Transect B, the emerged sector had higher concentrations. MPs levels in the channel were similar to those in the submerged beach sectors. The highest MPs concentrations (>50 MPs) were found at specific points along the shoreline, dune bases, and winter storm berms, which act as MPs traps. Offshore, high MPs concentrations were found in a transition zone where sediment settles, suggesting that MPs accumulate in calmer seabed areas beyond the active beach zone. The number of MPs in the river channel is not comparable with the rest of the sub-environments analysed. The concentrations of MPs in the bioconstruction are comparable to the areas with the highest MP densities on the other sites of the beach analysed related to the trapping mode of the structure.

This study represents a first attempt for the analysis of sedimentology and MPs distribution at Pino di Lenne beach, a low anthropized area in the Apulia region. The preliminary results suggest that MPs particles accumulate by slow sedimentation or trapping below the beach closure boundary and in the worm reef and by abrupt events in areas where bottom traction occurs.

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Floods and the Metropolitan Context: Organizational Learning in Genoa After the 2011 and 2014 Floods

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Abstract

Climate change is reshaping extreme weather events, such as cumulative rainfall, making them more frequent, severe, and sudden. One immediately thinks of the events in Valencia, where a self-regenerating weather system (the Dana) dumped a year's worth of rain in a single day, causing rivers to overflow, dozens of deaths, and billions of euros in damage. This is a tragedy that Italy experiences, in terms of material losses if not always in lives, every year in different regions. Among these, Genoa stands out, having been hit eleven times in the last 50 years.

It is widely recognized that the climatic component of these events explains only a small part of their impacts. Floods, and their most severe consequences, are caused by anthropogenic factors interacting with natural elements. The case of Genoa exemplifies this particular "socio-ecological" interdependence: the covering of watercourses, illegal construction, and industrial encroachment have been contributing factors that, combined with extraordinary rainfall, led to the overflow of rivers with steep gradients and short filling times. To this must be added, and not as a secondary factor, a governance of alerts that only after repeated episodes has developed a performing organizational, communicative, and institutional architecture.

The analysis of causes is undoubtedly a scientifically fertile opportunity for refining a sociological perspective on floods, which can no longer be fully isolated within the "natural phenomenon-social impacts" logic. Similarly, the formation of "social formations" following catastrophic events, as well as their relationships with public authorities, are of particular interest. However, equally relevant, though perhaps still underexplored, is the level of learning within civil protection systems, where local actors, particularly municipalities, are on the front line. In contexts that repeatedly face the same type of hazard, what factors accelerate or hinder the adoption of adequate mitigation measures? What role and impact do "soft" measures—those involving cognitive processes (planning, communication, training) and organizational ones (networking, accountability, roles)—have compared to "hard" measures, which rely on massive investments often beyond the means of communities? How do cognitive and organizational innovations emerge, how are they validated and recognized, and, if so, transmitted to other contexts?

This presentation is based on the initial results of empirical research conducted within the extended RETURN partnership, which has examined the social mechanisms that have reshaped flood governance in Genoa following two disasters: the 2011 and 2014 floods. The research, after a literature review, is being developed through semi-structured interviews with political administrators and technical officials of the city who held decision-making roles before and after the two floods, as well as with privileged observers of the local context.

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The “geobiologist”: a new approach in the assessment of the risk posed by Elongated Mineral Particles of health interest

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Abstract

Asbestos is a generic term used to identify six silicate minerals of commercial and economic value. The most critical route of exposure is inhalation, leading to the development of Lung Carcinoma (LC) and Malignant Pleural Mesothelioma (MPM) (Schulte *et al.*, 2011). In Italy, the use and production of asbestos were banned in 1992. However, this is still a relevant problem because many contaminated sites are still present and the malignancies associated to asbestos exposure have a long latency period, and so exposed subjects are still at risk of developing a neoplastic disease. Another problem is posed by Natural Occurring Asbestos (NOA), to which bans and regulations cannot be applied. In recent years other types of Elongated Mineral Particles (EMPs), such as erionite and antigorite, have also drawn attention, as they share similar geometry with asbestos fibres and have been linked to high incidence of LC and MPM (Ballirano *et al.*, 2018). NOA and naturally occurring non-asbestos classified asbestiform mineral (NONA) are widespread in many areas of Italy and represent a source of potentially inhalable fibres (Belluso *et al.*, 2020).

Although the mechanisms of asbestos-induced carcinogenesis are still poorly understood, three main parameters determining fibre toxicity have been identified: (i) morphology, (ii) biodurability, and (iii) chemical reactivity (Schulte *et al.*, 2011). These characteristics can be affected by the interaction of fibres with the biological environment, with consequent impact on fibres toxic potential. Different Simulated Lung Fluids (SLFs) have been used to study the modifications of EMPs in the biological surroundings: although useful, these fluids represent an oversimplification since they lack specific molecules of the respiratory tract that may affect the dissolution mechanisms and biological activity of inhaled fibres (Zangari *et al.*, 2023; Innes *et al.*, 2021). A possible way to overcome this issue is using Biological Fluids (BFs), which are more complex and better represent the biological environment, and therefore could be more reliable for modelling the fibres behaviour in the human body. At present, there are no studies addressing the interaction between EMPs and BFs.

Here, we present an innovative approach that combines mineralogy and biology, with the aim of unveiling the mechanisms of EMPs-induced carcinogenesis. The general goal of this project is to gain valuable knowledge about the interaction of hazardous and potentially hazardous mineral fibres with biological fluids of the lung and pleural compartments, in particular Bronchoalveolar Lavage Fluids (BALFs) and Pleural Effusions (PEs). This will be achieved by investigating the fibres properties (biodurability, mineralogy, chemical reactivity, ability of protein adsorption) and how they change after incubation with complex biological fluids. The systematic investigation of possible EMPs modifications occurring in BFs more accurately reflects the *in vivo* behaviour of the material under investigation, increasing the knowledge about how the biological environment affects the properties of inhaled EMPs, since until now most studies have been focused on the effects caused by EMPs to the human body (Ghio *et al.*, 2008). In these experimental settings, the study of fibres of well-known carcinogenicity can help predict the toxicity and pathogenicity of unclassified fibres.

The relevance of this project also lies in the fact that it includes EMP samples from different Italian regions: by identifying the conditions for potential health hazards caused by these fibres, we can contribute to the assessment of the environmental hazards posed by natural mineral outcrops throughout the territory.

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Continuous monitoring of Aerosol optical properties from ground based infrared measurements

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Abstract

Aerosol particles interact with electromagnetic radiation both in the short-wave and in the long-wave spectral region. Aerosols also present direct and indirect effects, such as radiation absorption or chemical-physical interactions which have important consequences on the environment, human activities and health. Currently, significant uncertainties are still present in the characterization of urban aerosol distribution, vertical profile, and microphysical properties. These uncertainties represent a critical factor for both the definition of the aerosol radiative forcing and for the effectiveness of environmental management strategies. The combination of large aerosol concentration and extreme weather events like heat waves is not rare and constitutes a compound risk that need to be carefully monitored and assessed.

In this work, we illustrate a new methodology (see Figure 1) for the simultaneous and continuous monitoring of aerosol features and meteorological parameters in urban environments. A new inversion strategy based on the fast radiative transfer code σ -FORUM (Masiello et al., 2024) is introduced. The model implements scaling methodologies to account for the presence of scattering layers in the simulated scene (e.g. aerosols) and efficiently compute analytical Jacobians with respect to particle's microphysical properties, as well as the atmospheric state. The retrieval routine is applied for the derivation of aerosol properties from spectrally resolved radiances acquisition, with a particular focus on ground-based methodologies. This analysis is important for developing early warning systems and risk mitigation strategies for urban areas exposed to combined aerosol and heat wave hazards.

This study is performed in preparatory for the application of a ground-based commercial interferometer (Bruker EM-27) which is being purchased by the Department of Physics and Astronomy of the University of Bologna, as part of the PNRR multi Risk sciEnce for resilient commUNITIES under a changiNg climate (RETURN) project supported by Next Generation EU. The implementation of this monitoring system will enhance our ability to characterize the aerosol and heat wave hazard, and assess and manage environmental and health risks associated with aerosol pollution in urban environments.

Figure 1 – Schematic representation of the acquisition system and algorithm. The radiances, acquired by the EM-27 spectrometer, are elaborated by the retrieval algorithm and the target atmospheric quantities are estimated. The method allows for an almost-continuous monitoring of the atmospheric state in the urban areas.

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Selection of circularity indicators applicable to the remediation of contaminated sites: a SMART approach

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Abstract

Contaminated sites pose a widespread threat to the environment and health, with a particularly significant impact on our territory. This is a critical and complex sector that needs integrated strategies to reduce and mitigate the health and environmental risks posed by contamination. Also, in order to find the best solutions for reducing risks, it is necessary to guide interventions towards strategies and actions according to circularity and sustainability principles. However, to date at the regulatory level there is no reference on the definition of specific indicators that would allow the assessment of circularity within contaminated sites. Similarly, studies on the subject are absent in the literature.

The object of this study, in connection with the topics of Spoke TS1 of Return project, in the first phase involved the selection of circularity indicators from those provided in recent technical standards for measuring circularity processes, UNI/TS 11820:2022 and ISO 59020:2024. Once the selection is complete, the next stage, which is currently underway, is to apply the same indicators in a real case study.

In the first stage, a working group formed by experts on remediation technologies design, Life Cycle Assessment and Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis, selected specific indicators in order to evaluate the remediation processes in both an *ex-ante phase*, focused on the choice of the best applicable technologies and *ex-post phase*, concerning the steps following the start of the remediation procedure. The selected indicators followed the SMART criteria: data for each indicator has been checked to be Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant and Time-bound.

This selection procedure identified a total of 25 circularity indicators applicable in the *ex-ante* and the *ex-post* phases and suitable for application in contaminated sites remediation processes. Specifically, the indicators derived from the UNI/TS 11820:2022 standard are 16, of which 11 for both the *ex-ante* and the *ex-post* phases and 5 only for the *ex-post* phase. The indicators derived from the ISO 59020:2024 standard are 9, of which 4 for both phases and 5 only for the *ex-post* phase.

Currently, the working group is carrying out the next phase of the study, concerning the application of the previously selected indicators, chosen for *ex-ante* phase, to a real case study. The fundamental criterion for the valuation of these indicators is that the necessary data be available (directly or obtained indirectly) before drafting the remediation project. Moreover, since the circularity assessment approach is not based on impacts but on inventory data related to site management, it is important to specify that the reliability of this analysis is closely related to the quality and completeness of the data used.

Among the 17.340 remediation processes managed in 2023 at the regional level (ISPRA, 2024), one case study was taken from among those managed at national level by the project partner Eni Rewind.

The risks analysis and the remediation project relating to the case study were analysed by the working group, in order to collect the data necessary to assess the indicators previously selected and to evaluate their effective valorisation within the framework of a remediation project in the *ex- ante* phase. This study made it possible to select 9 circularity indicators from UNI/TS 11820 on the basis of the available data and, consequently, to proceed with the assessment of circularity in the *ex-ante* phase. Table 1 shows the indicators actually applicable to a case study.

Table 1 Selection of circularity indicators applicable to a real case study

Indicator Number	Description	Reference Standard
01	Self-produced secondary material resources, compared to total raw and secondary material resources	UNI/TS 11820:2022
02	Raw materials and secondary material resources purchased and/or acquired from local suppliers compared to total raw materials purchased and/or acquired	
04	By-products and/or secondary material resources (input) compared to total material resources (input)	
13	Electrical energy purchased from renewable sources, compared to total electrical energy purchased	
14	Thermal energy purchased from renewable sources, compared to total thermal energy purchased	
15	Amount of water from recovery and/or recycling compared to total water demand	
18	Special waste sent for material recovery in relation to total special waste generated	
24	Output resources (products, residues, by-products, waste, components, and materials) subject to reverse logistics at end-of-life, compared to total output resources	
32	Value of products and/or services placed on the market that have product and/or service sustainability and/or circularity certifications in year n compared to the total value of products and/or services placed on the market in year n	

In conclusion, the application of the circularity indicators to a case study made it possible to implement a further selection based on the availability of data, an essential factor in the quantification of each indicator.

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ISO/WD 59020 (2024) “Circular economy — Measuring and assessing circularity”

UNI/TS 11820 (2022) “Misurazione della circolarità – Metodi ed indicatori per la misurazione dei processi circolari nelle organizzazioni”

ISPRA (2024) “Siti oggetto di procedimento di bonifica regionale”

From urban expansion to multi-Risk management: First findings on Spatial dynamics and Environmental history of Soccavo and Pianura Districts

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Abstract

This poster proposal presents the preliminary results of an integrated analysis conducted within the framework of the RETURN Project – Spoke: TS1 - Urban and Metropolitan Settlements Project, within the WP6. The study focuses on the Municipality n.9 of the city of Naples, which includes the districts of Soccavo and Pianura—two neighborhoods located in the north-western periphery. The research aims to provide a comprehensive framework by integrating the study of the urban fabric with an analysis of the area’s environmental history.

As such, this study is characterized by an interdisciplinary approach that combines urban planning and environmental history, by integrating spatial analysis and thematic mapping with the study of natural events, environmental risk cultures and environmental policies. This approach allows us to develop a comprehensive understanding of the area’s critical issues and to provide solid bases for a qualitative and quantitative analysis of risk cultures and environmental policy frameworks.

The integrated approach here adopted seeks to overcome the traditional fragmentation of territorial analyses, by providing a perspective that acknowledges the interdependence between urban planning factors, environmental dynamics, socio-cultural change and environmental policies. On the one hand, mapping the built environment allows us to identify areas where the concentration of both infrastructures and social housing might expose local communities to environmental risks, especially in the event of a natural disaster. On the other, the study of environmental history provides fundamental insights into the relationship between human settlements and natural hazards, over time, by focusing on the development of multiple environmental risk cultures and historical responses to multi-hazard challenges in the past.

Specifically, the analysis of urban structures addresses both the historical evolution of the urban fabric in the Municipality n.9 and its current state, with a focus on the transformations that have affected the area. Through the development of multiple thematic maps, different structural and functional elements of the urban context have been mapped and characterized. The first step involved the collection of available data from major territorial information systems (SIT), in order to obtain reliable and up-to-date information on both the urban morphology and the spatial distribution of functions. After an initial phase of data systematization and quality assessment, the first analytical processes have been carried out, in order to construct a detailed profile of the urban fabric.

A key component of this research is the analysis of the historical evolution of the urban fabric, which is essential to understand the processes of urban expansion. At the same time, a study of the technical

characteristics of the buildings has been conducted, as an essential step for the application of risk assessment models and a useful tool in the definition of targeted intervention strategies. The buildings were further classified by function, distinguishing between residential buildings (with a focus on public housing) and other uses such as commercial, industrial and administrative. Subsequently, the focus shifted to the mapping of the main infrastructural elements, including schools, green spaces, public facilities and cultural assets, in order to assess their presence and spatial distribution.

Environmental historical analysis examines the urbanization process and its relation with the multi- risks that affected the Municipality n.9, with particular attention to hydrogeological, seismic and pollution risks. The methodology here adopted involves the analysis of archive data, grey literature and press reviews: these tools can be useful in reconstructing the diachronic framework of territorial vulnerability and the specific dynamics of every dangerous event that happened in the past.

Particular emphasis has been placed on understanding how structural factors and conditions contributed to the occurrence of critical events. The integration of these different types of information allows us to design a multi-risk profile, by highlighting how the evolution of the urban fabric interacts with natural, socio-political and policy dynamics.

In the first place, this research aims to establish a historical connection between territorial transformations and community engagement in environmental stewardship, while the area became increasingly urbanized. Secondly, it attempts to reconstruct political and social mobilizations for environmental protection, throughout the twentieth century, while highlighting potential continuities with present-day movements. A third key aspect of this investigation is the learning process through which local expertise has developed various responses to environmental multi-risk, which might have historically emerged in the area of the Municipality n.9 and the city of Naples.

In light of the above, this contribution not only aims to contribute in expanding present knowledge on a marginalized urban area, but it also serves as a practical tool to support territorial planning and multi-risk management. Ultimately, this study represents an initial step towards a deeper understanding of the interactions between urbanization and environmental multi-risk in the Municipality n.9 of Naples. By doing so, it might inform policy choices not only from a historical and urban planning perspective but also by promoting risk communication and by fostering social and institutional learning.

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Explaining to high school students how to deal with an earthquake emergency: a role-play in the Civil Protection Operations Room

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Abstract

Inspired by the constructive experiences acquired in past years with high school students (e.g. Peresan et al, 2023; Barnaba et al, 2018) the National Institute of Oceanography and Applied Geophysics - OGS, in collaboration with the Civil Protection of the Friuli Venezia Giulia Region (PCFVG) experimented a new educational project aimed at improving seismic risk awareness, prevention and mitigation. The objectives of this project include: 1) increasing students' awareness and knowledge of earthquakes in an area with a high seismic risk; 2) disseminating information on emergency plans and promoting appropriate behaviour in the event of an earthquake; 3) encouraging a broader involvement of citizens in emergency management.

The project was coordinated by OGS staff and involved two officials from the regional civil protection department. The involvement of these two bodies is fundamental in the event of an earthquake occurring in the region: the OGS in fact provides the earthquake parameters (epicentre, magnitude and ground shaking) in real time, while the Civil Protection has the task of coordinating emergency management (including the services and bodies responsible for maintaining roads and buildings).

An exercise was carried out in the operations room, where students were divided into groups and took on the “roles” associated with the different functions activated for the specific emergency, namely: Technical-Scientific support; Health and Social Assistance; Accessibility and Mobility; Press and Communication. This experience was particularly useful and engaging. Thanks to this “role play”, the students were able to understand the most important aspects to consider in an emergency (Fig. 1): how priorities are managed and how decisions are communicated. This type of exercise demonstrated how the active involvement of students can be an effective way to teach them how to deal with complex issues (e.g. earthquakes) and, most important, to turn them into active citizens, actors in their own and others' safety.

Figure 1 – The exercise in the operation room: some pictures and main outcomes of the students' experience.

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Towards developing a Social-psychological Approach to Resilience for Adaptation (SARA)

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Theoretical background: The contribution presents some conceptual steps towards the development of an integrative framework to conceptualise a Social-psychological Approach to Resilience for Adaptation (SARA), regarding environmental natural hazards. This conceptual model moves from a preliminary conceptualization by Bonaiuto and Ariccio (2020) and develops it with the incorporation of Luthans' (2007) Psychological Capital (Psy Cap) and Putnam's (1993) Social Capital (Social Cap), as well as the Conservation of Resources Theory (CRT; Hobfoll, 1998).

Research aims and objectives: The resulting SARA model includes all the crucial variables credited in the literature (with special attention to meta-analyses) to significantly predict one or more criteria (encompassing cognitive, affective, behavioural responses) in at least one of the resilience's three phases (i.e., prevention, response, recovery).

Methodology: SARA maps all the potentially significant predicting variables according to two dimensions: I) Psychological Capital vs Social Capital; II) General vs Risk-specific. Consequentially, each one of the relevant predictors conceptually clusters in one only of the following four clusters:

1) General Psychological Capital, 2) Risk-specific Psychological Capital, 3) General Social Capital, 4) Risk-specific Social Capital.

A semi-structured interview has been prepared to preliminary test, with descriptive qualitative analyses, the above mentioned SARA structure. The interview features about 30 open-ended questions covering the various predictors clusters and the resilience's phases. The procedure expects to pilot the interview with a small (a few tens) subjects (both with and without environmental natural hazards experience). Results will be used to get a first pilot qualitative empirical evidence of the SARA's structure and elements.

Expected Outcomes and implications: SARA is expected to offer a comprehensive model to map the elements constituting both the psychological and social capital that every inhabitant can possess in order to improve her/his own resilience and the collective resilience in face of impending environmental natural hazards. The four clusters of variables represent the resilience's leverages and they can serve as main organizing criteria for planning various kinds of interventions devoted to develop them. Further research efforts could address the potential compensatory effects among variables belonging to the four SARA clusters; as well as different population profiles in terms of clusters of resilience leverages.

Keywords: psychological capital; social capital; human resources; coping; resilience; adaptation.

Training Teachers on Disaster Risk Reduction Education: Designing a Quasi-Experimental Study on the Effectiveness of a Game-Based Lab

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Abstract

Introduction

According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) report, the increasing frequency and intensity of extreme weather events—such as floods, droughts, storms, and sea-level rise—are directly linked to climate change (IPCC, 2018).

In response to this situation, a specific educational approach, Disaster Risk Reduction Education (DRRE), has been developed since the 1990s. However, only a few studies have assessed the effectiveness of the designed strategies (Canlas & Karpudewan, 2023), and existing research often adopts a transmissive teaching approach, while educational research highlights the need for an interactive, experiential, and participatory methodology (Nakano & Yamori, 2021).

Digital technologies and extended reality (XR) simulations can provide immersive experiences for disaster preparedness. However, most studies on the use of XR technologies in DRRE lack specific instructional frameworks and primarily focus on the acquisition of knowledge and skills for risk management, without aiming at fostering an adequate perception of risk (Scippo et al., 2024). Risk perception, in fact, plays a crucial role in adopting appropriate coping strategies for disaster prevention and management. Therefore, it is essential to develop and validate DRRE programs based on interactive approaches that leverage technology and promote both knowledge acquisition and the development of functional attitudes toward risk reduction.

As part of WP 6 of Spoke TS3 in the RETURN project, a laboratory based on the use of a video game has been designed to enhance future primary school teachers' knowledge of hydrological risk management and their attitudes toward risk perception. Since teachers' attitudes significantly influence students' performance and personality development (Blazar & Kraft, 2017), it is expected that teachers with greater knowledge and a more functional perception of risk will, in turn, foster similar knowledge and attitudes in their future students.

Method

Research Design. To test the hypothesis that the lab contributes to improving future teachers' knowledge and attitudes, a quasi-experimental research design was adopted with a control group, pre-test, and post-test. The independent variable is the game-based lab, while the dependent variables include knowledge of hydrological risk and risk perception factors identified by Theodorou et al. (*submitted*). To improve the internal validity of the study, background variables such as gender, age, and the management of negative emotions will be controlled.

Participants. The laboratory will take place between late April and early June 2025, involving approximately 300 fifth-year students enrolled in the Primary Education degree program at the University of Florence. Based

on their scheduling preferences, students will choose to attend either the weekday edition of the lab (control group) or the Saturday edition (experimental group), where the training program on hydrological risk reduction will be implemented.

Independent Variable. The lab consists of two phases. In the first phase, the approximately 150 participants will be divided into groups of five. Each group will analyze the context of a third- or fourth-grade classroom where one of the members currently works or has relevant experience. Based on this analysis, each group will design a learning unit, potentially to be implemented in the following school year (2025-26), aimed at fostering knowledge and skills in hydrological risk management and developing an appropriate risk perception. To achieve this goal, the groups will engage in educational activities on the following topics: climate change, causes and dynamics of floods, territory analysis and risk mapping, warnings, and behaviors to adopt before, during, and after a flood.

In the second phase, the participants will play a video game specifically designed for this study and developed by a company (Whitesock Spa) selected through a cascading funding call. The game, titled *Virivi and the Shadow of the Rain*, is a 3D educational game featuring a ten-year-old protagonist, Donatella, who discovers that her town is at risk of flooding. The game unfolds over five days, during which Donatella gathers information by interacting with other characters, makes decisions, and solves problems. A mysterious sprite guides her in identifying at-risk locations in her town, which she photographs and collects in an album, along with the information she learns about hydrological risk management. Players' decisions influence the story's progression and are linked to a point system that rewards responsible choices and appropriate interactions.

Dependent Variables. The dependent variables include knowledge of hydrological risk and the following factors related to risk perception: pro-environmental orientation, biospheric and altruistic values, climate change awareness, and expected response efficacy.

Expected Results

The expected results pertain to two categories of variables. On one hand, they involve teachers' knowledge and skills related to hydrological risk management. On the other hand, since risk perception effectively supports the adoption of preventive behaviors only when it is appropriately balanced—neither too high nor too low—a more accurate risk perception, closer to the actual risk level in the teachers' local area, is expected to be observed exclusively in the experimental group.

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Reprocessing of Pb-Zn mine tailings for resource recovery and environmental risk reduction in abandoned mining areas

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Abstract

Over the centuries, mining has produced significant volumes of waste that, if not properly managed, are a source of pollution of soil, groundwater and air, posing serious hazards to human health and biodiversity. Among the main challenges facing both the mining industry and environmental quality control authorities globally are the sustainable management of mining waste and the rehabilitation of brownfield sites, a priority made even more pressing by increasingly stringent environmental regulations. In this context, the reprocessing of tailings becomes increasingly important as the disposal or securing approach is not fully consistent with the principles of sustainability and the circular economy. Consistently, research explores more sustainable approaches to reduce environmental impact and, in parallel, to recover resources from mining waste.

The territory of the region of Sardinia (Italy) is of particular interest in view of the extensive and massive presence of mining waste deposits. The subject of the present work is the combined application of chemical and chemical-physical processes for the reprocessing of tailings stored in the abandoned mining district of Montevecchio Levante (SW Sardinia) where, over the last century, millions of tonnes of waste were accumulated and stockpiled without adequate environmental protection systems. In particular, the integrated approach involved the application of processes typical of the mining industry (grinding, gravimetric separation, flotation, magnetic separation) and leaching processes using bioderived organic reagents (Whitworth et al., 2022; Oraby et al., 2023).

The aim is twofold: on the one hand, to declassify the waste, reducing the concentrations of heavy metals and their mobility in the liquid phase in order to make it feasible to reuse it also on the soil (backfilling, etc.), or at least, for disposal in landfills for inert waste and, on the other hand, to obtain a concentrate with a high zinc content that can be economically interesting for the metallurgical sector.

The results obtained indicate that it is possible to obtain concentrates of commercial interest with zinc contents of up to 53% and final tailings in compliance with the threshold contamination concentrations for soils and are characterized by the low potential for metal release in the liquid phase. The proposed solution offers a promising way to address the challenges associated with mining waste management, providing new perspectives for sustainable resource management, reclamation and reduction of environmental risk associated with abandoned mining areas.

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Rethinking asset management workforce training through design thinking and new technologies

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Abstract

The innovative learning framework adopted within the third-level “Digital Twin, Virtual Reality and Metaverse: technologies supporting the asset management workforce” course at Politecnico di Torino exemplifies the potential of combining Design Thinking with emerging technologies to transform asset management workforce training. Modern asset management now demand multifaceted expertise and up-to-date skills, including a robust understanding of digital technologies which can embrace a significant plurality of stakeholders and different objectives. Within Spoke TS2, the role of representation is explored through investigated concerning information and communication theories and techniques, particularly in applying virtual reality (including mixed, immersive, holographic, and augmented reality) to develop sustainable training pathways for the asset management workforce of critical infrastructures. The course reflects emerging research trends and strengthens the connections between Education and Research supporting young researchers in generating new ideas in the Education Technology framework. The activity involved the participation of 10 PhD students characterised by different levels of progression, research path and backgrounds and consists of 20 hours of lessons distributed in 6 sessions as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Course outline and working methodology.

The first lesson defines the aims and objectives and includes the presentation of students in terms of their background and research activities, which is considered essential to initiate a co-design activity effectively.

The second lesson is on the problem space empathy and definition. Students are asked to create a Problem tree diagram [9] to relate problems in a hierarchical order from bottom to top according to an analytical approach that makes explicit cause-effect relationships once the main one to start from

has been defined. Although engineers were inclined to examine the pragmatic, technical, and technological aspects initially, it was immediately evident that there were multiple dimensions to be considered to determine the success of a possible project proposal. Training should carefully consider the target audience it is aimed at, its characteristics, and the social, cultural and corporate context of reference. Therefore, the solution's user experience and feasibility are highly conditioned by aspects not directly linked to its technological quality. Consequently, the Stakeholder map technique has been introduced to force a visual representation and a clear understanding of all the actors involved or interested in a project, initiative or decision-making process. Students are then called upon to transform the diagram created by moving from each specific problem to a linked possible action. All the activities are conducted by providing time for individual reflection, collective discussion, as shown in Figure 2 and final individual reflection to stimulate participation and expression of everyone's opinion.

Figure 2. Problem definition workshop.

The third lesson provides an overview of the most promising technologies that can be used in training activities. Each technology has been framed from a theoretical point of view and pragmatically declined with real-life examples. At the same time, participants are also encouraged to investigate the state-of-the-art applications of these technological solutions in related contexts or through replicable approaches.

The fourth lesson demonstrates guided brainstorming techniques that allow participants to unleash their creativity and explore multiple perspectives. Specifically, the Analogy mapping and the SCAMPER list methods are explored. The multitude of ideas that emerge must then be grouped, combined and reduced to begin formulating real solutions to the problem that can be designed in more detail.

The fifth lesson encourage students to experience role-play prototype technique to quickly elicit the target audience's user experience for a project idea. The case study taken as a reference was a hydroelectric infrastructure, and the project included training tasks for management and maintenance workers and a dissemination scene for the community. Each participant impersonated one of the stakeholders potentially affected by the project, as shown in Figure 3. This plurality of public/private internal/external stakeholders is in line with the Stakeholder map that emerged in the previous phase and greatly diversifies the points of view involved. In the round table discussion, the different stakeholder perspectives have converged, identifying diverse needs and priorities. Through this exchange, it was possible to analyse the strengths and weaknesses of the idea and, consequently, seek solutions to refine the initial proposal on the feedback received. As

emerged from the Problem tree diagram, economic, social, and cultural aspects must also be taken into account. For example, issues not initially considered related to the valorisation of the worker who adheres to innovative technologies or how these training methods can contribute to the updating and certification of professionals have emerged. This collaborative atmosphere has encouraged creative thinking, enabling participants to conceptualise training solutions that are both innovative and pragmatic.

Figure 3. Role-play session.

The methodological approach experienced during the course has proven valid and replicable. Therefore, this schema will be transferred to the RETURN project framework by broadening participation to different stakeholders in risk management fields to expand the Problem tree diagram and generate research prototypes that can have a concrete strategic impact in the context of the critical infrastructure asset management workforce.

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From Fragile Territories to Antifragility Approaches for Disaster Risk Reduction.

A Methodological Proposal to Integrate Knowledge Processes and Planning Strategies through Co-Design

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Abstract

The contribution presents the contents of WP.4. Task 7.4.4, “*New approach in integrated planning based on co-design processes for DRR and CCA policies*”. The Task focuses on the integration of planning strategies (e.g., Civil Protection Plans and Municipal Emergency Plans; Territorial Governance Plans) to identify vulnerable and safe places, and an educational process of communities towards risk prevention.

The final goal is the development of antifragility strategies for fragile territories by integrating routine and emergency planning with a participatory approach and co-design actions. Within the Task, fragile territories are identified as those exposed to multi-risk scenarios, demographic decline and/or an aging population, and remoteness from essential services.

The approaches are centred around three main pillars: 1) Prevention and Resilience: Developing integrated strategies to prevent and mitigate risks, starting with a critical analysis of the spatial structure of municipalities, guiding the transition from planning to projects, and the definition of criteria for identifying safe places; 2) Regeneration: Promoting regeneration processes that lead to co-design activities to enhance the built environment and open spaces towards risks resilience (Till, 2005: 27); 3) Education and Participation: Strengthening community awareness and building a shared knowledge between citizens and specialists to enhance capacities in risk prevention and management.

In fragile contexts applying a standardized top-down procedure to investigate different territories often leads to critical issues in spatial and social dimensions. The research stems from an inductive process based on a specific Proof of Concept (PoC). Place-based and people-centred investigations and methods are applied in 12 small municipalities of Lomellina, Lombardy.

In the awareness of possible limitations related to site-specific analysis and strategies, the expected results aim to define tools (e.g., survey sheets) for the knowledge and enhancement of the built environment, heritage, and open spaces, while promoting community empowerment (Gangemi, 2019), within the framework of Disaster Risk Reduction and Climate Change Adaptation.

Based on the accessibility of Civil Protection Plans (PPC) and former Municipal Emergency Plans (PEC), the analysis of planning tools is conducted in Candia Lomellina, Breme, and Sannazzaro de' Burgondi. While the adoption rate of PPCs in the Lombardy region is 78%, it drops to around 40% in the province of Pavia. Among

the PoC municipalities, only 4 have a PPC, representing an implementation rate of 30% (Dipartimento della Protezione Civile, 2022).

The investigation compares the documentation and cartographic materials of PPCs and Territorial Governance Plans (PGT) to verify correspondences and discrepancies in the identification and classification of buildings and open spaces as either “safe” or “vulnerable”. Furthermore, a specific analysis of the classification of cultural heritage and its role in PPCs is currently ongoing. The information retrieved are then associated with the results of semi-structured interviews and a focus group, involving more than 30 stakeholders.

The analyses focus on identifying and evaluating “safe places” in both built and open spaces based on their typological and spatial characteristics. The evaluation considers their surrounding context and adjacent open spaces, which will contribute to the development of an atlas mapping these safe areas. This verification process initially involved local stakeholders through a focus group. Subsequently, the research team identified and listed potential discrepancies between PPCs, PECs, and community perceptions, integrating a third classification related to the built heritage and identitarian places into the analysis.

In Breme municipality, where most of the data has already been systematized, the investigations revealed a mismatch between “safe” or “vulnerable” buildings and open spaces with identitarian places. Notably, there was a correspondence between locations classified as safe and those identified in the 2017 PEC. Additionally, a comparative analysis of the 2017 PEC and the 2013 PGT showed that all sites designated for emergency functions in the PEC corresponded to locations listed in the “Piano dei Servizi” of the PGT. In fact, these sites were planned as “urban standard” areas required as public services and facilities for inhabitants, resulting in a high level of nomenclature alignment. However, discrepancies emerged from the focus group results. Despite the strong alignment in official planning documents, most of the sites classified as safe in the PEC were never mentioned during stakeholder interviews. This mismatch in Breme documents suggests a gap between technical assessments and community perceptions of safety and cultural significance, underscoring the need for a more integrated approach in planning and design strategies.

Whilst the analysis of the PoC is still ongoing, the research group expects to find similar results in the other two accessible PECs. The first step of this comparative analysis is the creation of thematic territorial maps, which illustrate the locations mentioned in the above-listed documents for each municipality in the PoC, to set a shift from the urban to the architectural scale. The next phases of the research will deliver the following outcomes: an Atlas of Safe and Vulnerable Spaces; a Toolkit for Participatory Planning (including survey forms, mapping tools, and educational materials); and Operational Guidelines for Integrated Risk Reduction, based on co-design, which can be replicated in other contexts.

Figure 1 – Emergency Plan and Focus Group analysis of Breme municipality: safe and vulnerable places

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BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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Methodological advancements in marine geohazard assessment for coastal risk mitigation

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Abstract

This study, developed within VS2 (Spoke 2 – “Ground instabilities”) discusses methodological advancements in marine geohazard assessment, with a focus on rapid submarine landslides, for improving nearshore to coastal risk mitigation. A key aspect of the research is the parametrization of the driving mechanism (preconditioning, preparatory, and triggering factors) responsible for the initiation of submarine landslides. This was achieved by implementing specific tools (e.g. algorithms, numerical models), derived from specific learning examples that integrate geomorphological, 2D seismic, and geotechnical data, to constrain various geological processes that reduce slope stability. The new interconnected workflow of tools (i.e. toolchain) offers new quantitative instruments for a more effective coastal hazard assessment and modeling. This approach establishes a tentative framework that connects key driving mechanisms responsible to initiate ground instabilities to their impact on coastal regions, critical areas of the continental margins. Additionally, the research examines multi-hazard and cascading hazards, where events like submarine landslides, tsunamis, and flooding interact, amplifying risks and triggering secondary impacts. The ultimate goal is to enhance coastal resilience against interconnected geomarine threats.

The validated toolchain will be used to model hazard scenarios within a Virtual Test Bed (VTB), a digital platform for testing, modeling, and analyzing real-world processes. Insights from VTB scenarios will support the development of the first Proof of Concept (PoC) for submarine landslides at both local (e.g. submarine canyon heads) and regional (e.g. open slope) scales. Beyond providing a conceptual model for nearshore rapid submarine landslides, the PoC aims to establish effective guidelines and frameworks for monitoring coastal geohazards, strengthening resilience, and reduce vulnerability to submarine landslide threats, through effective risk mitigation strategies.

Spoke2 (namely VS2) is closely linked to the other RETURN vertical spokes, particularly those addressing natural hazards and environmental impacts. It connects with VS1 (Water), as water-related processes like erosion or flooding can exacerbate soil instability. It also interacts with VS3 (Earthquakes and Volcanoes), since seismic or volcanic activity can trigger landslides and ground failure. Additionally, VS2 is tied to VS4 (Environmental degradation), as soil instability may both result from and contribute to environmental degradation. This interconnectedness underscores the need for integrated models that account for both natural and human-driven processes to improve risks assessment and resilience. Furthermore, transversal spokes TS1, TS2, and TS3 play a crucial role by providing insights into the resilience of coastal infrastructures, helping to mitigate the impacts of coastal instability in urban areas where critical infrastructures, densely populated communities, and tourism are concentrated.

Figure 1. The headwall of the Cirò Marina (Ionian Calabria) submarine canyon (1.5 km long and 50 m tall) incises the continental shelf up to 20 m water-depth, undermining the stability of the Cirò Marina harbor quay built in 2001. Storms, amplified by the steep morphologies of the canyon headwalls, are reported to recurrently damage the harbor infrastructure, which frequently requires repairs.

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Integrating climate models and stochastic models for the generation of future weather at local scale

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Abstract

Generating future weather at a local scale requires integrating climate model outputs with stochastic models. Here, we focus on sub-daily rainfall scenarios, proposing a simulation framework that combines a parsimonious calibration strategy with the flexibility to incorporate potential future changes in rainfall time series.

Traditional sub-daily rainfall simulation models depend on high-resolution data, typically limited to 20–30 years, which is insufficient for generating the long synthetic time series needed for high return period design value estimation. In contrast, longer records of daily rainfall and annual maxima, often spanning 50–80 years, are more widely available and form the foundation for Intensity-Duration-Frequency (IDF) curve derivation, a key element of hydrological practice.

This study presents a novel framework for simulating sub-daily rainfall time series using only daily rainfall records and IDF curves, eliminating the need for sub-daily observations. The method combines a daily rainfall simulation model, the Complete Stochastic Modelling Solution, calibrated with observed daily data, with a multifractal disaggregation scheme guided by IDF curves. This integrated approach provides a robust and parsimonious solution for generating sub-daily rainfall data.

By leveraging widely available datasets, this framework extends the applicability of sub-daily rainfall simulations to a broader range of hydrological and climate modeling applications, enhancing flood frequency analysis and related studies.

Reshaping water management in today's and tomorrow's urban areas: why taking care of micropollutants?

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Abstract

The transition towards water-wise urban systems introduces new challenges in water quality management due to the increasing interconnection of water flows and uses. Urban water systems are becoming more complex, integrating various sources such as groundwater, stormwater, and treated wastewater for multiple purposes. While these strategies aim to enhance sustainability, they can also increase the risks of cross-contamination if not carefully planned. This study assesses these risks in urban water systems when multiple uses are implemented without strategic oversight, with a particular focus on the release and fate of micropollutants.

The city of Milan (Italy) was chosen as a case study to evaluate the effects of different water management strategies, including groundwater use for energy, stormwater and wastewater separation, and the indirect reuse of treated wastewater for irrigation. These interventions, while individually beneficial, introduce new pathways for micropollutants, raising concerns about environmental and public health impacts. Climate change adds another layer of complexity, as variations in rainfall patterns can influence the transport and accumulation of pollutants. Understanding these challenges is crucial for developing sustainable urban water management frameworks that minimize contamination risks and ensure long-term water quality.

An integrated modeling approach was applied, focusing on the fate and transport of per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFOA, PFOS) and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs, represented by pyrene). The study simulated multiple urban water management scenarios, summarized in Figure 1, incorporating dynamic interactions between different water/pollution sources and pathways.

The model was calibrated using available water quality data from Milan's urban water network. It was designed to account for seasonal variations and potential future conditions influenced by climate change. Different scenarios were developed to assess how varying levels of heat pumps use and infrastructure modifications (sewer separation) influence micropollutant dispersion. Additionally, environmental quality standards (EQS) were used as reference values to determine the chronic and acute risks associated with micropollutant exposure in surface water bodies. The key focus areas include:

- **Groundwater discharge dynamics:** understanding the extent to which groundwater extracted for energy applications contributes to PFAS pollution in urban canals.
- **Stormwater separation impacts:** evaluating how the diversion of stormwater from combined sewer systems into separate networks influences PAH concentrations in receiving water bodies.
- **Climate change effects:** assessing how altered precipitation patterns affect the mobilization and distribution of micropollutants within the urban water system.

Figure 1 – 1-hour resolution concentration at each monitoring point (INLET, POST_GHP, POST_SW, POST_WWTP, OUTLET) in different scenarios (B, B+GHP, B+GHP+SS08, B+GHP+SS24), showed with different colors, for PFOA (top), PFOS (center), and pyrene (bottom). INLET: water entering the canal; GHP: groundwater heat pump; SW: stormwater; WWTP: wastewater treatment plant; OUTLET: water flowing out; B: baseline scenarios; SS: sewer separation for 8 and 24 km².

The key results include:

- PFAS contamination from groundwater discharge:** groundwater extracted for energy applications was found to contain high levels of PFAS, which were subsequently introduced into surface water systems without adequate treatment (Figure 1). This contributed to chronic contamination risks in urban canals.
- PAH pollution from stormwater separation:** while separating stormwater from wastewater reduced the burden on wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs), it also led to increased PAH discharges into surface water bodies, particularly during storm events (Figure 1). Pyrene concentrations were highest immediately downstream of stormwater discharge points, with contamination risks increasing in scenarios where larger urban areas transitioned to separate stormwater sewers.
- Climate change amplification of pollution risks:** altered rainfall patterns led to greater pollutant mobilization, particularly for pyrene, which exhibited significant spikes in concentration following heavy rainfall events. The increased frequency and intensity of wet-weather discharges heightened both chronic and acute contamination risks.

- **Risk assessment outcomes:** chronic risk levels for PFAS exceeded EQS thresholds in all scenarios involving groundwater discharges and WWTP effluent releases. Acute risk thresholds for pyrene were surpassed in stormwater separation scenarios, particularly in conditions with high rainfall variability. These findings underscore the necessity for enhanced risk mitigation strategies.

The study highlights the importance of strategic urban water management to prevent unintended cross-contamination. Effective mitigation measures include pre-discharge treatment of groundwater, adoption of stormwater treatment solutions, and regulatory enhancements for wastewater discharges. Interdisciplinary collaboration among urban planners, engineers, and policymakers is essential to ensure sustainable urban water systems.

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Consequences and risk modelling of Natech in industrial environments

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Abstract

NaTech events (Natural-Hazard Triggered Technological Accidents) arise from the interplay between natural phenomena and technological incidents involving the release of hazardous substances. Predicting occupational inhalation risks in industrial areas is particularly challenging in the context of NaTech events due to the difficulty in predicting concentration fields, due to the presence of built elements that induce air flow perturbation. This work was conducted within the RETURN project (Multi-risk science for resilient communities under a changing climate). In this study, the dynamics of a NaTech event in an industrial complex were simulated and evaluated. Considering a chemical industry located in central Italy as a case study, the effects of a major accident concerning the release and evaporation of a hazardous liquid substance were simulated. The results included the representation of the consequences in terms of risk and environmental indices, to contribute to the development of a possible integrated prevention methodology. In the industrial site, tetrahydrofuran was used, a solvent characterized by high toxicity and high volatility. The substance was stored in a cylindrical tank with a volume of 1600 m³. The simulated accident concerned the release and evaporation of the liquid from the storage tank due to a failure. Considering the meteorological data available, it was hypothesized that the event began on February 8, 2021 at 15:00. The release was simulated with vessel dynamics and mass transfer models. The Parallel Micro-Swift Spray (PMSS) tool was used to simulate the dispersion of pollutants in the atmosphere. The system includes PSwift, a diagnostic preprocessor that includes parameterization to reproduce the effects of wakes and recirculation induced by the presence of buildings. The dispersion simulation provided hourly concentration fields. Hourly averages were multiplied by a peak-to-mean factor to estimate the short-term inhalation risk to which any workers or people present on the site could be exposed. The peak concentrations thus calculated were finally compared with the exposure limit values published by the American Conference of Governmental Industrial Hygienists (ACGIH), specifically the Threshold Limit Value - Short Term Exposure Limit (TLV-STEL) values. Using this procedure, the areas of the plant within which the peak concentration exceeded the proposed limit were identified.

The application of the release and evaporation model provided a rather rapid dynamics of the event. Tetrahydrofuran took 8 hours to exit the tank and approximately 24 hours to evaporate completely. Depending on the atmospheric conditions, concentrations varied significantly, and the substance was dispersed even beyond the site boundaries. The highest peak concentrations occurred under stable atmospheric conditions (poor dilution). The values were however lower than the TLV-STEL limit values, with some exception in correspondence of the source (Figure 1).

In conclusion, the application of the proposed methodology made it possible to evaluate the short-term risk following the occurrence of an accidental event potentially caused by extreme and not easily predictable meteorological factors. Future research work could be directed towards evaluating further scenarios in which different types of events and different environmental sectors are considered, to contribute to the development of a possible integrated prevention methodology.

Figure 1 - Risk map for short term tetrahydrofuran inhalation.

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Towards a Proof of Concept for Modelling of Complex Urban Settlements: A Virtual Testbed for the Assessment of Vulnerability, Impacts, and Risk Mitigation

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Abstract

This contribution presents the development of a Proof of Concept, a feasible concept complying with specific requirements and objectives, designed to enhance the understanding and management of multi-hazard risk in urban system. The PoC takes shape as Returnville, a Virtual Testbed, conceived as a coastal city with a river basin, built by integrating real-world urban, infrastructural, and environmental data from multiple existing cities. Located in the fictitious Returnland, Returnville is designed as a patchwork of real urban areas, featuring a defined territorial morphology, subsurface geology, built environment, critical infrastructure networks, and climatic conditions.

As the testbed supports interdisciplinary interactions across various scientific domains, enabling the exploration of risk scenarios in a controlled yet realistic environment, a distinctive feature of Returnville is its integration of knowledge and methodologies from multiple thematic spokes within the RETURN project. This cross-spoke collaboration promotes a holistic and multi-risk perspective, making Returnville a flexible and scalable platform for testing risk scenarios under varying physical, social, environmental and infrastructural conditions.

The development of Returnville follows two interconnected phases: (1) the construction of the city itself, including the assembly and integration of heterogeneous datasets, and (2) the definition of multiple hazard scenarios and impact chains, aimed at assessing the consequences of different risk storylines. A crucial aspect of this process is the establishment of vulnerability models for the exposed elements of the city, forming a core component of risk assessment.

Within Work Package 3 of the RETURN Spoke TS1 “Urban and metropolitan settlements”, a dedicated deliverable has been produced, compiling state-of-the-art vulnerability models for the built environment under various hazard conditions. These models provide a toolbox that can be used for impact assessment within Returnville, ensuring a comprehensive evaluation of risk propagation mechanisms. A highlight of this research is the development of a novel vulnerability assessment tool, specifically designed within the RETURN project. This toolbox quantifies the volumes of collapsed infill walls of reinforced concrete structures and its

projected displacement distances, enabling an assessment of potential road obstructions and emergency accessibility constraints.

Beyond vulnerability assessment, the construction of Returnville also emphasizes risk mitigation and adaptation strategies, ensuring that each analysis conducted within Returnville is complemented by "what-if" scenario evaluations. Through the Work Package 5 of TS1, mitigation tools are being developed to assess the effectiveness of adaptation and intervention technical and design solutions, allowing stakeholders to compare different strategies and optimize urban resilience. This integrated approach ensures that vulnerability and impact assessments are not merely diagnostic but actively contribute to shaping robust risk reduction policies and strategies.

MARCUS - Mitigation and Adaptation in Resilient Coastal and estuarine integrated units

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Abstract

MARCUS (“Mitigation and Adaptation in Resilient Coastal and estuarine integrated units”) aims at providing coastal stakeholders with strategies and measures for the safeguard of coastal and estuarine areas and nearby human settlements. This requires unprecedented observations of real life cases, to be complemented by both laboratory and numerical models. The following objectives will be pursued, based on multiple approaches and on the concept of synchronicity of extreme forcings.

The project is being implemented in terms of 4 Work Packages (WP), while the team is made out of 4 research units, Università Politecnica delle Marche (UNIVPM), Politecnico di Bari (POLIBA), Università degli Studi di Parma (UNIPR) and Università di Catania (UNICT). Figure 1 illustrates the above.

Figure 1 – Project structure and Consortium composition.

An illustration will be provided of the results achieved for each WP during the first half of the project, with particular emphasis given to the importance of wave-current interactions for: a) the sea-river dynamics evolving at a river mouth and b) the compound flooding potentially evolving there.

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